

Investigation into employee motivation, engagement and retention in relation to employment attractiveness and emotional labour in the UK spa industry during the Covid-19 pandemic

By

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Abstract

Employee shortages, high turnover and low employee engagement are all common problems in the spa industry in the United Kingdom. As the spa sector continues to grow at a breakneck pace, challenges of recruiting and retention inevitably arise. Furthermore the Covid-19 pandemic has disrupted the UK spa industry and workforce. There is growing recognition among spa executives of the critical role that an engaged employees plays in both improving customer satisfaction and ensuring the long-term viability of a company. Organisational leaders must grasp how issues such as emotional labour might affect their employees' capacity for engagement. The aim of the study was to investigate staffing problems in the UK spa industry to identify and develop a commercially available model for employee engagement within the industry. The theoretical frameworks that helped guide the development of this study were employee engagement (Kahn, 1990), employer branding (Ibrahim et al., 2018), employer attractiveness (Ronda, 2018) and emotional labour (Hochschild, 2012).

An exploratory research design methodology has been adopted in this qualitative study, taking a pragmatic approach to analysis. Thirty-nine documents including grey literature have been identified and collected as the qualitative secondary data mainly using Google search engine. A documentary review was conducted using King's (2015) template.

Documentary review identified therapist shortages, skill gaps, employee reputation, work–life balance, and economic and development factors as the key challenges for employee engagement in the UK spa industry. It is clear that the UK spa industry has a high physical and emotional job demand where spa employees views themselves as wage slaves and money is often their key motivation. High emotional labour is leading to emotional exhaustion, depersonalisation, burnout and intention to quit among spa employees. Employee benefits and rewards are somehow keeping employees on loop from burnout to engagement but not all spa businesses are in the financial situation to offer attractive

benefits. Additional research into this phenomenon could contribute useful and insightful knowledge to both academia and commercial practice in this field.

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Author's declaration

I hereby declare that the work contained in this thesis was carried out in accordance with the University of the West of Scotland's requirements and is entirely original, except some references in the text. As the author of this work, no portion of it has been submitted for consideration for any other academic award or degree at this university or any other educational institution in the United Kingdom or elsewhere.

Additionally, I declare that my research was undertaken entirely on my own initiative with guidance from my supervisor, who assured that this work adhered to UWS academic policies and ethical behaviour.

Suman Tamang

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1 Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Background of the study

The twenty-first-century commercial world is highly competitive. Human capital accounts for a significant portion of the global economy, and effective management of accessible human resources is critical to the success of an organisation. One of the essential roles of the Human Resources department is to attract, motivate, engage and retain their employees to maximise their organisation's performance. Recruiting employees is more than just getting an employee to join an organisation. Finding appropriate employees is critical for any firm. The addition of talented employees dramatically enhances a company's success; therefore, it is essential to attract and retain talented employees. Organisations with talented employees can flourish if they help them develop their skills and maximise their potential. Andrew Carnegie, a nineteenth-century businessman, remarked that even if he lost everything, including his business and money, he could recoup everything if he retained his people (Carnegie, 2018). Richard Branson (2015), the creator of Virgin Group, emphasised the importance of employee well-being when he stated, 'If you take care of your employees, they will take care of your clients.'

Employee engagement is a hot issue for academic research since it is vital for any organisation because it is the driving force behind development and achievement of goals and objectives. Employee engagement, defined by Kahn (1990), is how employees feel about their work, which they express physically, emotionally and cognitively. It is the psychological presence of a person at work. Sloman et al. (2015) suggest that people are an organisation's most important asset, whereas Ganesh (2016) argues that organisations must maximise their employees' performance to their full potential to adapt to ever-changing competitive economic situations. Businesses must have employees devoted to meeting the demands of an ever-changing business environment.

Although employee engagement is becoming increasingly popular in research, studies reveal that the world of work is changing dramatically. Employees are becoming less

motivated to work, feeling burned out, and many even have the intention to quit (Stevenson, 2020). Many countries struggle with high employee turnover, exacerbated in today's competitive climate. Employee engagement is crucial to reducing employee turnover intentions (Walsh and Bartikowski, 2013) and organisational performance (Albrecht et al., 2015). People care about the reputation of the company for which they work; hence, to attract and keep great employees, a company must be a reputable corporation (Chiu et al., 2020). Attracting and retaining qualified employees has become critical for businesses competing to be an 'employer of choice' organisation (Reb, 2017). Employer of choice is a term that refers to the concept of employer branding (Turner, 2020). Employer branding is derived from marketing, which has developed into a critical sector for companies. In today's competitive environment, businesses have begun to leverage branding as a strategic tool. Firms are implementing the branding concept in various other contexts where branding plays a significant role (Zahra, 2018). The experts emphasise that a company with an exceptional employer brand has a competitive edge over other companies and this increases employee engagement and retention (Brown, 2018; Zahra, 2018; Turner, 2020).

Organisations are continually looking for new ways to attract and retain employees. Employer branding and attractiveness is a critical strategic tool in an organisation's fight to attract, engage and retain exceptional employees by creating a great workplace (Chiu et al., 2020). Employees, meanwhile, are constantly looking for a better opportunity. Berthon et al. (2005) identify five factors that potential employees look for in a job: interest, social, economic, development and application value. Organisations can provide career opportunities and advancement, foster a creative and innovative environment, engage in social responsibility projects, and offer more significant financial benefits to their employees to develop a strong employer brand, which will improve employer attractiveness and employee retention. Employees leave organisations because of low job satisfaction (Zahra, 2018), low wages (Brown, 2018), limited career opportunities and role stressors (Reb, 2017); therefore, employee engagement is key to retaining valuable employees (Turner, 2020).

Emotional labour is another concept that plays a vital role in employee engagement. Research into emotional labour has grown rapidly since Arlie Russell Hochschild published *The Managed Heart* in 1983 (Hochschild, 2012). Emotional labour is the management of emotion to generate publicly observable facial and bodily displays in a workplace (Hochschild, 2012). In other words, emotional labour is the process whereby employees manage and display their emotions to meet the 'organisational feeling rules' (Bratton and Watson, 2018). Employees use their bodies to perform numerous jobs simultaneously with their minds performing other tasks such as observing what a customer wants and ensuring they meet customer service regulations. Employees invest their emotions in their work in exchange for wages, while employers commercialise those emotions and sell them to a customer (Hochschild, 2012). Hochschild argues that employees are obliged to suppress their true feelings and ensure their displayed emotions are appropriate for a customer or professional setting (Hochschild, 2012). Human feelings have become increasingly commercialised. The modern capitalist society puts a lot of pressure on employees' emotional management capabilities, which may lead to emotional exhaustion, depersonalisation and burnout (Hochschild, 2012; Schutz and Lee, 2014; Bratton and Watson, 2018).

Like many other countries, the UK struggles with significant employee turnover, even more so in today's competitive environment, where employee engagement is viewed as critical to minimising employee turnover intentions (CIPD, 2017) and organisational success (Albrecht et al., 2015). The spa sector is thriving in the United Kingdom, where working at a spa requires a high level of emotional labour and a higher turnover rate than other professions (Kitto, 2018; Spa Life, 2019). The adverse effects of employee turnover are particularly unbearable in the spa business. The costs of learning and training spa therapists are high, and there is therefore a shortage of spa therapists in the United Kingdom (Cressy, 2013). Employee engagement is critical for motivating and retaining current employees and attracting new hires. The spa sector necessitates a greater degree of emotional labour, as

Mauno (2016) claimed that emotional labour has a critical influence on employee engagement. While the spa industry has received relatively few studies in the UK, the contribution to employee engagement and emotional labour is essential.

1.2 Industry background

The term 'spa' refers to various services and experiences, ranging from modest facial and massage businesses to huge pampering resorts. The term 'spa' was first used to refer to naturally occurring thermal springs in Ancient Greece and Rome. These bathing and leisure areas were beneficial to one's health and well-being, and little has changed in this regard to the present day. Global Wellness Institute (GWI) defines a spa as an establishment that promotes well-being by providing therapeutic and other professional services to rejuvenate the body, mind and soul (Global Wellness Institute, 2018).

In 2017, GWI projected that over 150,000 spas employed more than 2.6 million people and generated £118.8 million globally, rising at a compound annual rate of 9.9 per cent (Global Wellness Institute, 2018). There is a growing demand for spa services around the world as a result of rising personal incomes, increased tourism and other demographic changes (Global Wellness Institute, 2018). The unparalleled stress of modern life and a growing awareness of well-being have created a need for this ever-increasing market trend in which individuals can disconnect from their hectic daily lives and enjoy quiet time, reconnecting with nature and regaining their equilibrium (Global Wellness Institute, 2018). According to analysts at Global Data, British consumers are predicted to spend almost £487 per head on wellness spas by 2022. Demand is one thing; supplying services is quite another.

1.3 Problem statement

Since the 2008 economic crisis, the UK labour market has improved dramatically, resulting in a significant drop in unemployment, with the skilled trades experiencing the most significant gain in employment (ONS, 2019). The unemployment rate fell to an estimated 3.8 per cent in 2019, while female participation increased significantly to 71.8 per cent. This

unemployment rate is considered near to 'full employment' – a state in which practically everyone who wants a job has one, resulting in a highly competitive labour market (ONS, 2019). The most incredible difficulty facing the UK economy over the coming years is increasing labour supply, but this is a significant challenge given that tight labour market circumstances apply downward pressure on wages and the balance of bargaining power tilts toward employees.

There are over 7,000 job openings in the UK spa industry, but job listings are one thing; filling them is another, with just a small percentage of vacancies filled (Indeed, 2018; Bromstein, 2018). The number of spa visits climbed by 9.9 per cent in the UK in 2017, but the number of workers increased by just 1.3 per cent (PR Newswire, 2018; Statista, 2018). According to GWI, the global spa business will require an additional 80,000 spa managers/directors and 500,000 spa therapists by 2020 to meet the global spa service demand (Global Wellness Institute, 2018). The spa industry in the United Kingdom has been experiencing a staffing deficit. Employees are expected to work longer hours due to increased demand and scarcity of supply. Because spas are expected to be a leisure service, clients frequently visit during the evenings and weekends. Employees are expected to work evenings, weekends and bank holidays due to the anticipated increase in business during those times.

Employee turnover is one of the most severe issues confronting businesses today. Employee turnover in the United Kingdom continues to rise each year, reaching a record high of 15.5 per cent in 2017. (Beckett Frith, 2017). Employee turnover is significant in the spa industry in the United Kingdom. A spa therapist requires years of training and expertise to deliver an exceptional level of service, and replacing an experienced spa therapist is difficult and costly for spa businesses (Bromstein, 2018).

Emotion management is critical in the spa industry, as the services provided in a spa emphasise emotional relaxation. As a result, communication via body language and facial expression is crucial. Emotional labour is defined as showing positive emotions or acting

compassionately while suppressing negative emotions to achieve the desired objective, such as client satisfaction or loyalty.

1.4 Rationale for the proposed study

While employee engagement and retention are critical to an organisation's success, it is also crucial to recruit new employees. As previously stated in the problem statement section, the spa industry in the United Kingdom has struggled to attract and retain the necessary workforce due to a lack of human capital required to implement a standardised employee engagement and retention strategy (Bromstein, 2018). Until recently, spa wellness was viewed solely as a concept and a philosophy. Standard business and economics statistics do not provide a clearly defined wellness industry classification despite its existence. Because of the industry's recent emergence, there is a shortage of academic literature on the subject.

There is a growing body of literature on employee motivation (Dahou and Hacini, 2018; Habon et al., 2019), engagement (Kahn, 1990; Turner, 2020), retention (Griffith, 2019; Singh, 2019) but there are no studies on employee engagement and retention in the UK spa industry. Haupt and Harinarain (2016), Ganesh (2016) and Gilani (2017) have conducted research on traditional health care and wellness hospitality in general, but the spa industry has received scant research. Historically, studies and theories of engagement and retention have focused exclusively on motivating, engaging and retaining employees to maximise organisational productivity, with little regard for the employment attractiveness implications in the spa industry, which requires a high level of emotional labour.

Malmberg and Gyllered (2018) studied the effectiveness of rewards in recruiting young people to the Swedish construction industry. However, the spa industry still lacks an in-depth examination of how to attract, motivate and retain employees who perform emotionally taxing work. Moser et al. (2017) argue that the employer's offering is the critical factor in attracting potential employees. Still, they completely ignore that each industry has a unique

level of emotional labour and employment attractiveness. There has been limited research on the spa industry in a few countries, but there has been no prior research on the spa industry in the United Kingdom. Lagrason and Lagrason (2015) conducted research on quality management in the Swedish spa industry. They concluded that employee engagement is critical to quality management but did not address effects on the spa industry's employment attractiveness.

In spa literature, emotional labour and employee engagement are rarely discussed. Khadka (2015) looked at employee well-being in spas in Nepal where she found that job demands are high and the only motivation factor of spa employees is money which is affecting their well-being. Due to the poor standard of living, Peri et al. (2015) found that the motivation of spa personnel in Serbia is unsatisfactory and that the financial component is the most important motivator. Similarly, Craig (2018) found that spa therapists' work function in high-volume job environments has been linked to a reduction in wellness. Khadka (2015) conducted research in Nepal, while Peri et al. (2015) conducted research in Serbia. The living standards in both countries are similar, which may explain why the results and findings are the same. The UK has different living standards which may lead to different working environment and motivation outcomes. Blau et al. (2013) and Craig (2018) conducted a study within the UK spa industry which identified high physical work as the key factor leading spa therapists leaving the industry. Wisnom and Gallagher's (2018) study investigated the quality of work life (QWL) of 107 resort spa employees in the United States. Good working conditions, fair wages, appreciation, interesting work, and a sense of involvement were the most crucial factors in motivating employees, with compensation and benefits such as health insurance, retirement/pension plans, bonuses, and dental insurance also being essential. However, the study found that the resort spa industry fell short in providing fair wages, employee loyalty, and overall QWL. Smith and Wallace (2019) highlighted the importance of employee training, career development, and leadership in promoting employee motivation, with empathy and effective communication being critical qualities for spa managers. but

neither looked at the emotional side of work and lacked an in-depth investigation through the lens of employee engagement (Kahn, 1990) and emotional labour (Hochschild, 2012). The Covid-19 pandemic has further disrupted the workforce within the UK spa industry and a more pressing concern is how the industry will adapt and what shape it will take in the coming years. This issue introduces a gap in research concerning the impact of Covid-19 upon the spa sector and further clarifies the limitations of HR theorising on the issues and challenges for employee engagement, emotional labour, employee branding and attractiveness due to the global pandemic. This not only limited the nature of this enquiry in terms of primary research but opened new lines of thinking in terms of new contributions to understanding the business issues of employee engagement, employer branding, attractiveness and emotional labour.

Additionally, this study may assist not only the spa industry but also other industries such as restaurants and health care settings who are suffering from workforce shortages to devise a more effective plan for attracting and keeping top talent. While attracting new employees is critical, retaining existing employees requires keeping them motivated and engaged, as well as resolving the staffing crisis before it worsens. This research study may add a new way of formulating an employee engagement and retention area to the existing body of knowledge.

1.5 Novel contribution

The motivation and perception of individuals towards work, jobs or careers have been changing throughout history, depending on time and situation. Employee engagement is not a new area of study. Humans have been working since the prehistoric era where their motivation for hunt was to feed their families and to survive. There have been many changes in human history from the bronze age to the modern capitalist era, but the industrial revolution in the eighteenth century radicalised the world of employment and the employer and employee relationship started to emerge (Schuck and Wollard,, 2013). It was a time when people did not have many job opportunities and they were often willing to do anything to feed their families and to survive. Getting paid to feed their family was their key

motivation. Fear of losing a job played a key factor in their motivation towards work. Jaros and Culpepper (2014) and Sonar and Paliwal (2018) demonstrate that employees often show high levels of organisational commitment because of 'high sacrifices' and 'low alternatives'. They suggest that employees' organisational commitment is influenced not only by fear of losing their job, but also by a scarcity of available alternative jobs. That is not the case any more. Since the 2008 economic crisis, the UK labour market has improved dramatically, resulting in a major drop in unemployment, with the skilled trades experiencing the greatest gain in employment (ONS, 2019). The unemployment rate fell to an estimated 3.8 per cent in 2019, while female participation increased significantly to 71.8 per cent. This unemployment rate is considered to be near to 'full employment' – a state in which practically everyone who wants a job has one, resulting in a highly competitive labour market (ONS, 2019).

There has been a war of talent hunt where employers are offering attractive benefits to attract and retain the best talent. Kahn (1990), Culpepper (2014), Dijk et al. (2017) and Hossain (2017) have shed light on the importance of employee engagement. Jaros and Culpepper (2014) and Sonar and Paliwal (2018) have demonstrated why employees leave and how to prevent employee turnover. Hochschild (2012), Bolton (2005), Brook (2009), Maslach and Leiter (2016) and van Dijk et al. (2017) have all raised the concept of emotional labour and how it affects employees. Employee engagement and emotional labour have previously been studied separately. This research might get insights into the key factors within the UK spa industry through the lens of emotional labour. Since the UK spa industry experiences high employee turnover, it could be crucial to understand how emotional labour is affecting employees' motivation towards work and their intentions to leave. Filling the research gap and the results of this study could have a significant impact on the understanding of the importance of emotion management performed by spa employees. These findings could lead to practical solutions for staffing issues that the UK spa industry is facing. This research aims to bridge the gap by contributing to the investigation of employee

engagement through the lens of emotional labour. The results of this research project help to reflect and advance the findings of prior research studies.

It is important to highlight the originality and contribution of this thesis to the existing literature on employee engagement and emotional labour in the spa industry. Empirical, theoretical and methodological contributions of the study can be explained by drawing on the works of Guetzkow et al. (2004) and Phillips and Pugh (1994).

One of the key empirical contributions of this study is its focus on the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on employee engagement, emotional labour, burnout and alienation in the spa industry in the UK. This study is among the first to provide an examination of the impacts of the pandemic on the spa industry and the associated challenges for employee engagement, emotional labour and employee well-being. The findings of this study provide valuable insights into the challenges faced by spa employees and the implications for employers in ensuring employee engagement, well-being and motivation.

This study makes a theoretical contribution by considering existing theories of employee engagement, emotional labour, burnout and alienation to understand the impacts of the Covid-19 pandemic on the spa industry in the UK. The study applies the theory of employee engagement to examine the extent to which spa employees are engaged in their work and the impacts of the pandemic on engagement levels. The study applies the theory of emotional labour to examine the impact of the pandemic on the emotional demands faced by spa employees. The theories of burnout and alienation are introduced to examine the impacts of the pandemic on employee well-being.

This study makes a methodological contribution by adopting a document analysis approach, using thematic analysis as a tool to analyse the data. The study draws on a range of secondary data sources, including grey literature, to provide an examination of the impacts of the Covid-19 pandemic on employee engagement, emotional labour, burnout and alienation in the spa industry in the UK.

In conclusion, this study makes an original contribution to the existing literature on employee engagement, emotional labour, burnout and alienation in the spa industry in the UK. The study provides valuable insights into the impacts of the Covid-19 pandemic on employee engagement, emotional labour, burnout and alienation in the spa industry, offering implications for employers in ensuring employee engagement, motivation and well-being. The contributions of this study make it a valuable addition to the existing literature to the field of spa industry research.

1.6 Research aim and objective

The aim of the study is to investigate the impact of Covid-19 in terms of resourcing staff in UK spa industry. The intention is to identify and develop a model which engages with the impact of Covid-19 upon employee engagement within the UK spa industry.

Overarching/main research question: 'Further to the fundamental shift in employment further to Covid-19, what was the impact upon employee motivation, engagement and retention upon the ability of the spa industry to motivate and retain their employees?'

Sub-questions:

1. What were the key factors of the Covid-19 lockdowns in terms of their impact upon employee motivation, engagement and retention in the UK spa industry?
2. What were the commonly used employee motivation, engagement and retention strategies in the UK spa business pre-Covid-19?
3. What are the challenges faced by management in employee motivation, engagement and retention strategies as a result of the enforced lockdowns during Covid-19?

4. How can employment attractiveness be further developed in the UK spa industry relative to employee motivation, engagement and retention strategies post-Covid-19 lockdowns?

The research objectives serve as a road map, beginning with what has to be accomplished and ending with a likely outcome that answers a study question. The following are the objectives associated with the aim.

Objectives:

1. To determine the key factors and importance of employee motivation, engagement and retention in the spa industry with a focus on the period of Covid-19
2. To identify the most commonly used employee motivation, engagement and retention strategies within the UK spa business in terms of the impacts of Covid-19
3. To explore the challenges faced by management in employee motivation, engagement and retention strategies during and after the Covid-19 lockdown periods
4. To investigate how to develop future employment attractiveness in the UK spa industry by using employee motivation, engagement and retention strategies.

1.7 Thesis structure

There are six chapters in this thesis. The first chapter of the study begins with an introduction and provides an overview of the six key sections of the research. There is an introduction to the research framework in Chapter 1 that begins with the study's background and research problem statement, as well as its aims and objectives. The research will conclude with a brief summary of the research's significance in an easy-to-read manner. Chapter 2 is a literature review. Here, the notion of employee engagement (Kahn, 1990), emotional labour (Hochschild, 2012), employer branding and attractiveness (Bethron, 2005) and their relation to employee motivation, attraction, retention and turnover are examined. Employee involvement in the UK spa industry has been supported by a variety of theories

and models. Further research into the UK spa industry reveals the present gap in the literature.

The theoretical foundations of this research are examined in Chapter 3, and the research design and methodology of this study are also discussed. The initial plan was to conduct primary research but the data collection process via interview with UK spa personnel was not possible due to the Covid-19 pandemic and the series of national lockdowns. Therefore, a secondary research approach has been adopted. A pragmatism philosophy has been followed with a qualitative research design. Online databases and libraries such as government websites, spa association UK websites, newspaper articles and economists have been selected as reliable sources for collecting secondary data.

The documentary review was chosen due to Covid-19 social distancing procedures, which restricted face-to-face connection with participants. It was deemed acceptable for this study since it allowed for comparing multiple writers' views on staffing concerns and challenges in the UK spa business, ensuring that complete data was collected and correct conclusions were drawn on the subject. Thematic analysis using King's template was performed in this documentary review. There was no need for ethical approval before conducting this exploratory investigation because the documentary evaluation used secondary data sources that were already in the public domain.

In Chapter 4, which is based on the documentary review, the results and findings of the study are presented. Using the previous literature study, the theoretical framework adopted, and the grey literature sources, the findings are described in detail in Chapter 5. Chapter 6 concludes this thesis by providing a comprehensive summary of the entire project and a look back at the original research goals. This dissertation concludes with a full list of all papers cited in the text, as well as thoughts on the path to doctoral outcomes, impact on one's own analysis, reflection using Gibbs Reflective Model and contributions of the study.

2 Chapter 2: Literature review

2.1 Introduction

This chapter considers the major concepts, ideas and empirical research on employee motivation and engagement undertaken in the UK spa business. The goal of this study is to investigate and attempt to resolve staffing issues (attraction and retention of employees) in the spa industry in the United Kingdom. Maslow (1943), Herzberg (1959), McClelland (1961) and Vroom (1964) have previously shed light on employee motivation, and this chapter examines empirical research on employee engagement (Kahn, 1990), employer branding (Ambler and Barrow, 1996), employer attractiveness (Dabirian et al., 2019) and Hochschild's (2012) emotional labour theory as the key to employee engagement and motivation. The chapter begins with an overview of the spa sector and existing research. Following that, empirical research on employee engagement is reviewed, as well as employer branding and attractiveness. Theoretical perspectives on emotional labour: Hochschild's *The Managed Heart* (2012), as well as empirical studies on emotional labour will be explored. The final section summarises the review's findings of the effect of emotional labour on employee motivation and engagement, which serves as the conceptual framework for the research's empirical study.

The aim of the literature review was to examine the existing body of knowledge regarding the spa industry, the UK labour market, employee engagement, organisational commitment, motivational theory, employee turnover, employer branding and attractiveness, and Hochschild's emotional labour theory. To ensure that the most relevant literature was included, a comprehensive search was conducted using sources such as academic journals, books and online databases.

To further refine the search results, the following inclusion criteria were applied:

- Research that focused specifically on the spa industry or related industries.
- Research that was published before 2019.

- Research that was written in English.
- Research that was relevant to the research questions and objectives of the study.

On the other hand, the following exclusion criteria were applied:

- Research that was not directly related to the spa industry or related industries.
- Research that was not relevant to the research questions and objectives of the study.
- Research that was not relevant to employee motivation, engagement, staffing issues and emotional labour.
- Research that was published after 2020.
- Research that was not written in English.

The search terms used to identify relevant literature within spa industry: employee engagement, organisational commitment, motivational theory, employee turnover, employee branding and attractiveness, Hochschild's emotional labour theory.

In conclusion, the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the literature review were designed to ensure that the most relevant literature was included and that the results of the literature review were directly relevant to the research questions and objectives of the study.

2.2 Spa industry overview

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines wellness as a state of complete physical, mental and social health. The emergence of the wellness business is entirely a supply-and-demand tale. The macro-effects of an ageing population living longer with chronic diseases and an increase in obesity necessitate care, yet many nations' health systems are already overwhelmed (Nelson, 2019). While professional health care is still mostly used to treat illness, an increased interest in preventative measures demonstrates a change in wellness knowledge and behaviour. People are overdone as a result of modern-day employment and hectic lives, resulting in difficulty sleeping, stress, worry and sadness.

Increased awareness of health and well-being has led to an increase in demand for health and wellness goods and services (Global Wellness Institute, 2018). The worldwide wellness industry has a market value of \$4.2 billion and is growing at a pace of almost twice that of the global economy, which is growing at a rate of 3.6 per cent. The global wellness industry accounts for 5.3 per cent of global output (Global Wellness Institute, 2018). Wellness is a vast market that encompasses lifestyle, exercise and nutrition, while the spa industry is a growing industry that was selected as the focus of the study.

The wellness business is dominated by spas that offer services ranging from hydrotherapy to yoga to fitness to exercise to holistic treatments and massage to promote well-being and therapeutic advantages. Global Wellness Institute defines the spa as an establishment that promotes well-being by providing therapeutic and other professional services aimed at rejuvenating the body, mind and soul (Global Wellness Institute, 2018). Spas are the fastest expanding section of the hotel, leisure and wellness industries at the moment. There are approximately 150,000 spas worldwide, employing over 2.6 million people and generating \$118.8 billion in revenue at a compound annual growth rate of 9.9 per cent (Global Wellness Institute, 2018). While Asia-Pacific has the most spa enterprises, Europe has the largest overall spa income: \$33.3 billion in 2017.

In spas, massage therapy is the most popular service, presumably because of its ability to induce relaxation and well-being through the manipulation of soft tissue (Craig, 2018). When it comes to working as a spa therapist, you need a location to recuperate after putting in a lot of physical and emotional effort, and while spas are fantastic places to relax for the customer, they aren't necessarily the best places for an employee to heal (Khadka, 2015; Craig, 2018). A therapist will see as many as eight clients a day. Craig (2018) cites high volume-massage settings as a possible cause of therapist burnout, as well as inadequate working circumstances that lack enough illumination and space. Working in the spa industry exposes massage therapists to the danger of repetitive strain injuries (RSIs) such as upper limb disorders (ULDs), which can be caused by daily massage sessions that might last for

hours on end (Blau et al., 2013). Around 80 per cent of those who start a career in spa industry leave after just two years due to not possessing the physical stamina, which they cite as one of the reasons for their departure. As evidence, Craig's (2018) investigation into spa therapists' experiences working in the UK with high-volume massage reveals that physical discomfort and decreased well-being were the two most common reasons for leaving their positions. An additional finding was that nearly two-thirds of those polled had been injured while performing daily high-volume massages. To motivate and engage spa therapists, Craig (2018) recommends that employers need to create the right working conditions, surroundings and organisational environment. Although Blau et al. (2013) provide a general indication of the availability of legislation, this does not provide details about the frameworks in place for the regulation of spa therapists. In spite of UK government regulations and legislation protecting workers from workplace hazards in UK businesses, there is little or no evidence of regulations and legislation to protect the practice of spa therapists in the workplace (Blau et al., 2013).

In Wisnom and Gallagher's (2018) study, the quality of work life (QWL) of employees working in resort spas was investigated. The study included 107 employees from resort, hotel, and destination spas, primarily located in the United States. The study assessed QWL factors such as employee motivation, compensation and benefits, training, performance evaluation, and organizational culture. Results indicated that good working conditions, fair wages, appreciation, interesting work, and a sense of involvement were the most crucial factors in motivating resort spa employees to perform well. Additionally, the employees placed high importance on compensation and benefits such as health insurance, retirement/pension plans, bonuses, and dental insurance. However, the study found that the resort spa industry fell short in providing fair wages, employee loyalty, and overall QWL.

Similarly, Smith and Wallace (2019) emphasized the importance of employee training and career development, with economic incentives playing a crucial role in motivating employees. The authors also argued that leadership plays a vital role in promoting employee

motivation, with empathy towards employees and effective communication skills being the most critical qualities for a spa manager.

The wellness industry generates £26.3 billion to the UK economy, accounting for around 8 per cent of GDP (Statista, 2018). The spa industry is a tiny subset of the wellness sector, with an estimated 6,000 spas in the United Kingdom employing around 57,000 people (UK Spa Association, 2018). There are approximately 7,000 job vacancies in the spa business in the United Kingdom, but job listings are one thing; filling them is another, with just a small percentage of positions filled (Indeed, 2018). The number of spa visits climbed by 9.9 per cent in the UK in 2017, but the number of workers increased by only 1.3 per cent (PR Newswire, 2018; Statista, 2018). According to the Global Wellness Institute (GWI), the global spa business will need an extra 80,000 spa managers/directors and 500,000 spa therapists by 2021 to fulfil demand (Global Wellness Institute, 2018). The spa business is struggling to recruit new personnel since the public does not consider health and wellness as a realistic career choice and it has historically been regarded as a low-grade job (Bromstein, 2018). Additionally, the Covid-19 epidemic has wreaked havoc on the sector, and the way the spa industry operates may change as a result of new government regulations, staff and consumer behaviour. Spa jobs need close contact with consumers, and it is more challenging than ever to engage employees in the spa business in the United Kingdom. The chances of getting a virus is high in spas compared to other industries. Spa therapy is not a job where people can do work from home or by maintaining a social distance. Fear of getting a virus is relatively high and frequent cleaning and use of PPE could add even more job demands and job stressors which might lead to even more challenge in retaining and attracting employees: the ever-growing problem that the spa industry is facing. Employee turnover is a problem not just faced by the spa industry; therefore the next section explores the UK labour market condition to explore the spa labour force.

2.3 The UK labour market

Since the 2008 economic crisis, the UK labour market has improved dramatically, resulting in a major drop in unemployment, with the skilled trades experiencing the greatest gain in employment (ONS, 2019). The unemployment rate fell to an estimated 3.8 per cent in 2019, while female participation increased significantly to 71.8 per cent. This unemployment rate is considered to be near to 'full employment' – a state in which practically everyone who wants a job has one, resulting in a highly competitive labour market (ONS, 2019). The greatest difficulty facing the UK economy over the coming years is increasing labour supply, but this is a significant challenge given that tight labour market circumstances apply downward pressure on wages and the balance of bargaining power tilts towards employees and unions.

Employee turnover is one of the most serious issues confronting businesses today.

Employee turnover in the United Kingdom continues to rise each year, reaching a record high of 15.5 per cent in 2017 (Beckett Frith, 2017). Employee turnover is significant in the spa industry in the United Kingdom. A spa therapist requires years of training and expertise to deliver an exceptional level of service, and replacing an experienced spa therapist is difficult and costly for spa businesses. It is stated that policymakers must continue to focus on labour shortages and employee retention in industries such as the spa business. Payroll cost rises are a serious threat to the profitability of the spa industry in the United Kingdom, and this increase is mostly due to a labour scarcity caused by low overall unemployment rates, which forces spa businesses to provide a premium wage in order to recruit and retain workers. Employee turnover is estimated to cost roughly £11,000 per person on average in the United Kingdom and the talent shortage has resulted in wage auctions, which do not increase retention in the long run. Due to the labour shortage big businesses are offering attractive salaries and benefits to attract and retain top talents but this poses a big question about how small and medium-sized businesses can offer high salaries and attractive bonuses.

Spa is a labour-intensive industry that requires a range of skill sets from the unskilled to the highly skilled, as well as critical customer service skills (Khadka, 2015). Customer

satisfaction, service quality, customer loyalty, competitive advantage and overall organisational success are all affected by the human element in the spa sector (Craig, 2018). Labour-intensive employment is a critical component of the spa sector, and retaining high-performing employees is critical to service delivery. The spa industry's reliance on the human component has resulted in a high rate of employee turnover (Bromstein, 2018). Despite this, spa employers frequently blame macroeconomic, societal or political causes rather than taking responsibility for the high levels of staff turnover (Bromstein, 2018). The spa sector is plagued by a high rate of staff turnover, which is largely due to the perceptions of low earnings, a lack of job security, terrible working conditions and a lack of prospects for advancement in the field (Craig, 2018; Global Wellness Institute, 2018; Bromstein, 2018). The necessity to retain employees in the spa business, which has a high turnover rate, has elevated the importance of organisational commitment, and it is recommended that employee engagement in the spa industry is a strategic issue for gaining a competitive edge. Therefore it is necessary to look at employee engagement as a possible solution for attracting and retaining spa employees.

2.4 Employee engagement

Employee engagement was coined by Kahn (1990) in his 'Psychological circumstances of personal engagement and disengagement at work' in the *Academy of Management Journal*. Khan identifies three psychological factors associated with employee engagement and disengagement at work: meaningfulness, safety and availability. According to Khan, employee engagement is about how employees feel about their jobs through physical, emotional and cognitive involvement (Kahn, 1990). 'William Kahn's (1990) research on employee engagement has garnered significant attention from academics and practitioners' (Markos and Sridevi, 2010). Employee engagement is concerned with determining how committed people are to something or someone at work, how hard they work, and how long they stay as a result of that dedication (Sun and Bunchapattanasakda, 2019). According to de Clercq et al. (2014), employee engagement is a collection of pleasant feelings that foster

congruence and a laser-like concentration on goal alignment, hence reducing organisational non-conformity. The alignment of the employee–supervisor relationship is a significant aspect affecting goal congruence (Babalola, 2016). Along with the employee–supervisor objective alignment, employee engagement is influenced by the employee's thoughts, ideas and perspectives about his or her employment. Employee engagement results in enthusiasm, a sense of pride in one's work and a sense of accomplishment (Alvi et al., 2014). Due to the multiple operational differences, such as job engagement, personal commitment, organisational involvement, staff engagement and work engagement, developing the employee engagement construct has proven problematic (Truss et al., 2014). Since then, employee engagement has grown in popularity, as evidenced by various research studies (Macey and Schneider, 2008; Anitha, 2014; Carrillo, 2019; Sun and Bunchapattanasakda, 2019).

Employee engagement is a vital component in organisational success, as demonstrated by Stoyanova and Iliev (2017), Al Mehrzi and Singh (2016) and Sun and Bunchapattanasakda (2019). It is critical to keep employees happy, motivated and engaged. Turner (2020) claims that organisations should prioritise employee engagement because it improves employee performance and work satisfaction, which has a positive effect on organisational performance. Thus, employee engagement is critical for any business, as people are the organisation's most precious assets and are critical to increasing the organisation's productivity. Additionally, Geldenhuys et al. (2014) discovered a significant correlation between employee engagement and aspiration for work. Employers and employees should evaluate each other's needs and develop personalised and robust procedures and regulations to meet those demands (Carrillo, 2019).

Employees operate in a complex work environment that may have a negative effect on an organisation's success (Sun and Bunchapattanasakda, 2019; Balwant et al., 2019).

Individual employees may have challenges with their personal ability to work, with their supervisory authority, or with personal trauma that they must manage on the job (Kazimoto,

2016). Often, organisations focus exclusively on the financial aspect of employees in order to accomplish their objectives. However, Kazimoto (2016) notes that organisations' performance will be enhanced if they examine both financial and non-financial factors. In line with this, Kandulna (2016) also emphasises the importance of work engagement in terms of organisational performance, efficiency and effectiveness in accomplishing organisational goals. Additionally, concentrating on employee engagement will aid organisations in surviving and possibly succeeding through economic downturns (van Rooy et al., 2011). According to Turner (2020), employee engagement promotes employee growth, hence improving an organisation's overall performance. In general, it is obvious that highly engaged employees exert physical effort in pursuit of organisational goals and are cognitively attentive and emotionally linked to the organisation (Bello et al., 2018; Kahn, 1990).

According to Kahn (1990), the work environment has an effect on how much an employee's physical, cognitive and emotional self is applied to their task. This notion can help us better comprehend how we act when we are in roles we don't choose for ourselves (Kahn, 1990). In order to determine how work circumstances affect employee behaviour, it is crucial to know how employees respond while performing their jobs (Kahn, 1990). Kahn's (1990) engagement theory hinges on how much one is mentally present when performing work tasks. Psychological work experiences shape attitudes and behaviours, which in turn are influenced by elements inside the individual, within groups and within the organisation as a whole. For example, most people like to express themselves in an authentic manner while displaying authentic thoughts and feelings. Kahn (1990) argues that employees are more likely to feel like they are important and valued when they can express themselves authentically in a meaningful and safe setting. It is the employer's responsibility to make it a meaningful job where employees who are actively involved in their work are better able to carry out their responsibilities because they are more emotionally and mentally present

(Kahn, 1990). Spa employers must therefore provide therapists with a meaningful work that will aid in employee engagement.

Anitha (2014) claims that a decline in employee engagement can have a detrimental influence on an organisation's performance. According to Ukil and Ullah (2016), people want more meaning in their professional lives than in their personal lives, and hence the employer should make work meaningful to their employees. It is critical for employers to provide clear instructions for empowering employees and resolving any issues that arise so that employees feel valued for their contributions (Robbins et al., 2013). Babalola (2016) and Kammerhoff et al. (2019) previously demonstrated that effective leadership has a beneficial effect on job perception and satisfaction, hence increasing staff retention. According to Aguenza and Som (2018), employee engagement has a beneficial effect on employee retention. Hom et al. (2017) argue that employee turnover has a detrimental impact on organisational effectiveness and financial performance since it begins at the very beginning of the recruitment process and is a never-ending process in which job attractiveness is also a major factor.

There are several advantages to having a motivated workforce. The challenge stems from the problems around keeping the workers engaged. Certain job demands might deplete a person's energy in a negative way. The physical, social or organisational components of a job that needs ongoing physical or mental energy are called job demands where various physiological and psychological expenses are linked to certain job demands. Job resources are components of the job that assist employees in reaching their goals. Additionally, some job resources have the ability to lessen the physical and psychological burdens of some job requirements (Hom et al., 2017). Employees who are actively involved in their work have a much better track record of mobilising their work resources to reduce the likelihood of unfavourable consequences.

According to Zhang et al. (2015), the term 'engagement' may play a facilitative function in the interaction between employee commitment and intention to leave. In that regard,

organisations today are attempting to promote employee commitment through skill development and the facilitation of great work experiences, as losing people and failing to maintain employee commitment is costly for the organisation (Meyer, 2014; Zhang et al., 2015; Hom et al., 2017).

Many studies on employee engagement have focused on the advantages and factors of engagement (Geldenhuys et al., 2014; Aguenza and Som, 2018). However, the difficulties of implementation and the perspectives of employees on involvement are given scant attention. The bureaucratic structure of companies has a considerable impact on the ability of an organisation to engage its employees. Furthermore, poor management and inefficient communication are the primary obstacles to employee engagement when it comes to heavy workloads. Employees' perceptions of their work environment may be a challenge in fostering employee engagement (Turner, 2020). Employee engagement is all about whether employees are willing to give their all to their work. Employees are either engaged or actively disengaged at work (Hisel, 2020). Employees who are passionate about their work are more likely to be engaged. Indicators of an engaged workforce include things like a commitment to the company's mission, a drive to enhance their work, a grasp of the company's goals and a willingness to share ideas and work together with co-workers. Engaged employees put in extra effort at work and are always looking to improve their skills and expertise (Turner, 2020). Workers who are only there for the money are deemed time-serving and lack a passion for their job (Hisel, 2020). Employees that are actively disengaged are unhappy at work, and they express this dissatisfaction in the workplace through deviant behaviours.

Having a sense of being valued is the most important factor in employee engagement (Cattermole, 2018). The voice of the employee must be listened to and the needs, issues and values of employees must be taken into consideration by organisations. Involvement in decision-making, the capacity to express one's thoughts, development opportunities and the degree to which a business shows concern for its people are all important factors in making employees feel appreciated.

Herd et al. (2018) identify a number of generalisations that contribute to varied levels of employee engagement within firms. As employees age, their participation reduces in comparison to their youth. Similarly, there is an indirect relationship between engagement and period of service. This means employees' participation decreasing as time of service increases. Herd et al. (2018) further argue that minority and ethnic employees are often more engaged than native white people.

To begin their investigation into what factors contributed to job happiness, researchers devised a theory called organisational commitment (Lolitha and Johnson, 2015; Sonar and Paliwal, 2018).

2.5 Organisational commitment

Organisational commitment refers to an employee's psychological attitude toward the organisation (Greenberg and Baron, 2008). Employee organisational commitment happens when employees align their aims and beliefs with those of the organisation. These employees consistently perform above management's expectations in an effort to integrate themselves into the organisation. Organisational commitment is critical in evaluating whether an employee will remain with the company for an extended length of time and work tirelessly to accomplish the business's goals (Lolitha and Johnson, 2015). Organisational commitment is composed of the three basic components model (TCM): affective (desire), continuance (need) and normative (obligation) (Sonar and Paliwal, 2018).

Affective commitment (AC) is the intensity of an individual's willingness to work for an organisation simply because they agree with it and wish to do so (Greenberg and Baron, 2008). It is associated with employee commitment to an organisation's basic principles, such as its mission and vision statements (Sonar and Paliwal, 2018). AC refers to an employee's emotional commitment to the organisation, and it entails a demonstration of readiness to exert effort in order to continue with the organisation (van Gelderen and Bik, 2016).

According to van Gelderen and Bik (2016), employees demonstrate AC as a desire of

incentive distribution, organisational support, providing high-quality services, role clarity and decision-making decentralisation.

Continuance commitment (CC) is the level of commitment at which an employee believes that leaving the organisation would be costly. When an employee's level of commitment remains constant, they feel obligated to remain in the organisation for a longer period of time since they have already spent adequate effort and feel emotionally and mentally connected to the firm. For instance, a person develops an attachment to his or her job over time, which may be one of the reasons why an employee may be reluctant to quit owing to his or her emotional investment. Jaros and Culpepper (2014) argue that employees engage in continuance commitment for two reasons: 'high sacrifices' and 'low alternatives'. This suggests that employees' CC is influenced not only by fear of losing investment and benefits, but also by a scarcity of available alternative jobs (Sonar and Paliwal, 2018).

Finally, normative commitment (NC) is concerned with 'workers' wants to continue working for an organisation because they feel obligated by others to do so' (Greenberg and Baron, 2008). The obligation to remain with a company may be motivated by ethical or moral considerations (Robbins et al., 2013), or by concerns about co-workers' perceptions (Meyer and Allen, 1991). Employees with this perspective take into account their perceived obligation to their organisations. NC can be compared to 'reasoned-action models of behaviour' (Meyer and Allen, 1991), an 'indebted responsibility' (Jaros, 2007), or a type of psychological contract (Guest, 1998) in which employees believe that continuing their employment with a business is the proper thing to do. For example, employees whose organisations have provided scholarships or training may believe it is ethical and moral to continue with the institution until the agreed upon employment terms and circumstances expire.

Today's workforce is distinct from previous generations in that it seeks meaningful outcomes (Gifford and Bailey, 2018). Today's employees seek employment that give them a sense of accomplishment as well as a sense that their salary is commensurate with their skills.

Employees who are aligned with and supportive of the organisation's culture and goals are in the right job. When managers pick individuals with the appropriate skill set and an understanding of the organisation's mission and goals, tangible benefits accrue to the organisation (Gifford and Young, 2021). According to Whittington and Galpin (2010), employees possess a strong desire to engage in meaningful work. According to Watson (2012), providing employees with meaningful work results in greater organisational commitment, increased production and decreased turnover. Employees may see meaningful work if they believe their efforts contribute to the organisation's success. Employees may also encounter meaningful work if the task they execute is consistent with their self-identification.

It is also important to look at the motivational theories to understand what motivates employees and how spa employers can motivate employees.

2.6 Motivation theory

Motivation is the process by which an individual determines the intensity, direction and perseverance of his or her efforts towards achieving a goal. Motivation is frequently triggered by an unmet need. When a person's basic requirements are addressed, he or she receives some sort of reward, whether intrinsic or extrinsic. For example, a person may be motivated to perform a task because they desire to avoid a punishment or receive a reward. Employee motivation is the most important factor in determining how well an employee performs at work. A study by White (2011) found that employees are motivated to stay because of what they can provide whereas those who are disengaged stay because of what they can get. When people are self-motivated, the motivation and enthusiasm to work override compensation models and performance monitoring systems.

Maslow (1943) developed a psychological motivational theory which is often known as the hierarchy of needs. Maslow's (1943) hierarchy of needs has five stages: 1) Physiological needs – biological requirements for human survival; 2) Safety needs – protection from

elements, security, order, law, stability, freedom from fear; 3) Social needs – feelings of belongingness; 4) Esteem needs – esteem for oneself and the desire for reputation; and 5) Self-actualisation needs – a desire to become everything one is capable of becoming. Maslow (1943) suggested that once a certain level of need is met, it ceases to serve as a motivator. The next level of need must be engaged in order to motivate a person (Maslow, 1943). Maslow's theory has a significant impact on employee engagement and leadership since it states that if you don't meet your first- or second-level needs, you won't be able to meet your higher-level demands (Shuck, 2011). Leaders don't always fulfil the requirements of their followers; instead, followers are driven by their most basic, unmet needs. If a follower's effort leads to the fulfilment of these lower-level wants, the leader can and should establish environmental circumstances that allow the worker to meet these needs.

Frederick Herzberg (1966), a psychologist, extended Maslow's theory and developed a new theory of motivation. This is a two-factor theory also known as Herzberg's motivation hygiene theory. Herzberg found that there is a strong correlation between positive feelings and job satisfaction, whereas negative feelings are connected with job dissatisfaction.

Herzberg refers to job satisfiers and job dissatisfiers as motivators and hygiene factors, respectively. Herzberg's two-factor theory of motivation consists of motivators (advancement, recognition, work itself, responsibility, achievement, growth) and hygiene factors (interpersonal relationships, supervision, working conditions, salary, status, security).

In Herzberg's (1966) theory, employees' basic needs in the workplace are conceptualised as extrinsic hygiene factors. Fair pay and working conditions are some examples of hygiene factors, as are a reasonable level of security and trust in the leader (Herzberg, 1966).

Employee dissatisfaction can be attributed to a variety of hygiene factors, such as the belief that they are not receiving a fair wage, poor working conditions, or a lack of job security.

Employee dissatisfaction can be avoided if basic hygiene requirements are met (Eke, 2018).

Herzberg (1959) proposed that dissatisfaction and satisfaction are not diametrically opposed concepts, but rather are the polar opposites of distinct continuation constructions

experienced as distinct emotive states. According to Herzberg (1968), employees are more likely to engage in their work to the extent that they have access to intrinsic factors (such as the importance they place on their own personal development, growth and recognition, as well as collaborative work environments), which are essentially higher-order needs.

However, it is important to keep in mind that adequate attention must be paid to extrinsic factors that do not cause any employee dissatisfaction. Before employing intrinsic motivation variables to increase satisfaction, leaders should first address lower-order hygiene demands.

Motivating employees can be a challenge in the workplace. Leaders in a business must be involved in the learning process of their employees in order to motivate their workforce.

Employees' performance is assessed using a variety of metrics, including appraisals, monitoring, feedback, compensation, job security, training and development. Habon et al. (2019) argue that empowerment is the critical factor in motivating employees. Enabling employees to engage in the development of organisational decision-making is known as empowerment. Giving employees the autonomy and freedom to do their jobs more effectively is what it means to 'empower' them. When employees are given the authority to decide how their work is done, this is the first step toward empowerment. Employees want to be valued and empowered at work, and they want to feel like they have a stake in their work (Jena et al., 2019). Dahou and Hacini (2018) argue that employees feel appreciated and proud of their work when they are given more responsibility and authority.

Employee motivation can also be analysed through social exchange theory (SET) (Yin, 2018). Initially, social exchange theory was primarily used to demonstrate how humans interact through their attitudes and behaviours (Emerson, 1987). Chernyak-Hai and Rabenu (2018) extended the theory by arguing that SET might be viewed as the basis connection between organisation members and the organisation. Its fundamental concept is that human relationships are created on the basis of subjective cost–benefit analysis, which means that people tend to repeat activities that have previously been rewarded, and the more frequently a given conduct has been rewarded, the more likely its recurrence. Relationships that are

mutually beneficial and respectful contribute to productive work habits and excellent employee attitudes. As long as both parties follow a set of 'rules of exchange', the core principle of SET suggests that relationships can develop over time into ones characterised by mutual trust, loyalty and commitment (Chernyak-Hai and Rabenu, 2018).

When a business commits to providing rewards, respect and fairness to its employees, the employees develop a greater trust in the organisation. This increases their motivation to work hard and, as a result, the employees return the organisation with improved job performance. Employees' expectations of high or low levels of job engagement and rewards are based on social exchange theory, which states that the relationship between employees and the organisation is based on an equal social exchange relationship; thus, when employees are engaged actively, they are more likely to perform well on the job (Kim et al., 2015).

Employees frequently exchange their participation for employer-provided resources and benefits. Therefore, when employees have autonomy, receive support and have possibilities for growth, they are more likely to reciprocate by demonstrating increased levels of engagement (Kim et al., 2015). Employees who believe their employer cares about their well-being through sufficient resource allocation are more likely to be motivated and engaged.

2.7 Employee turnover

In the workplace, employee turnover refers to the process through which an existing employee leaves and is replaced by a new one. According to recent reviews of employee turnover research (Anvari et al., 2014; Lo, 2015; Nelissen et al., 2017; Sun and Wang, 2017), the majority of these studies focus on voluntary employee turnover. Voluntary turnover is when employees voluntarily leave their positions. Employees may resign for a variety of reasons. They may be dissatisfied with their position or compensation, wanting a change in careers, or having accepted another offer (Nelissen et al., 2017). Voluntary

turnover, on the other hand, is typically caused by competent people abandoning their jobs, as opposed to involuntary turnover, which is frequently the result of sub-standard performance. As a result of the costs connected with recruiting and hiring a new employee, voluntary turnover may be rather costly for a business (Sun and Wang, 2017).

Numerous empirical studies have established the detrimental effect of high voluntary employee turnover on an organisation's productivity and profitability (Zylka and Fischbach, 2017; Hom et al., 2017), workforce performance (Selden and Sowa, 2015), instrumental communication and behavioural commitment (Porter et al., 2019), and social capital (Brien et al., 2015). Waldman et al. (2015) and Sun and Wang (2017) discovered that leadership involvement partially mediated the connection between human resource development methods and intention to leave. Employee turnover rate reflects both the economic and social consequences of human resource management in various types of organisations (Nica, 2016). This indicator is regarded as a critical measure of an organisation's overall management effectiveness and, more specifically, human resource management effectiveness. Given that excessive voluntary employee turnover has a detrimental effect on an organisation's economic and social operations, the critical function of human resource management in reducing employee turnover (Nica, 2016).

On the other hand, involuntary turnover occurs when an employee is released from a job (Hom et al., 2017). Poor job performance or inappropriate conduct are two of the reasons why employees may be terminated from their positions (Hom et al., 2017). Numerous concerns that contribute to involuntary turnover can be mitigated by the use of pre-employment exams throughout the hiring process (Hom et al., 2017). For instance, one of the leading reasons of involuntary turnover is the inability of new employees to adequately absorb and apply training. Ability and skill tests can indicate a candidate's learning capacity and likelihood of completing training effectively (Hom et al., 2017).

Sun and Wang (2017), Akgunduz and Sanli (2017), Porter et al. (2019) and Brown (2018) have all sought to answer the question of what motivates people to leave their jobs, but their

findings have been inconsistent due to the diversity of occupations studied. Employees leave one organisation for another for a variety of reasons, among them are work-related variables. Porter et al. (2019) established that economic factors, the working environment, performance appraisal and career growth all influence an employee's intention to leave. Zahra (2018) asserts that work-related pressure, a low organisational commitment and job discontent are the primary reasons for people to quit their jobs, indicating that these are individual decisions made by employees. Brown (2018) argues that people leave organisations for economic reasons, and that economic models may be used to forecast employee turnover in a market where large organisations can offer employees better opportunities for promotion and higher pay.

Additionally, job pressures contribute to employee turnover (Reb, 2017). 'Role ambiguity' refers to the discrepancy between the expectations of employees and what they believe they should be doing. Employees' proper position may be questioned because of a misinterpretation of what is anticipated, how to meet those expectations or the employee believing that the job should be performed in a different way from what is expected (Reb, 2017). How to do their jobs well, what their peers and supervisors expect them to do, how they are judged, how much work they have to do and what their job duties and responsibilities are may make employees unhappy and disengaged with their jobs, less committed to their organisations and more likely to leave them (Reb, 2017). Employers need to clearly define employees' roles or else this increases the likelihood of employees quitting their jobs due to a lack of job clarity (Kalkman, 2018). Uncertainty inside the organisation has been a significant factor in increasing employee turnover. Numerous studies have demonstrated that employees are more likely to depart when their work environment is uncertain (Abolade, 2018). According to Ahmed et al. (2017), people are constantly on the lookout for stable organisations that offer opportunities for career progression. Additionally, Ahmed et al. (2017) assert that effective communication within an organisation plays a critical influence in employee turnover. Reb (2017) claims that employees must be properly

informed and communicated with effectively in order to feel comfortable and remain longer. According to Brown (2018), economic variables have a negligible influence on employee turnover. Employees frequently resign when they believe their superior work is not appropriately rewarded. This shows that spa employers need to provide a role clarity to their employees, job security and appropriate pay and rewards to retain valuable employees. Since the outbreak of Covid-19 and the national lockdowns, job security and the survival of the UK spa industry have come into question.

According to Ahmed et al. (2017) and Kalkman (2018), there is a positive association between leadership and intention to leave. Seibert et al. (2013) conclude that leadership departure has a positive relationship with staff turnover; Heaphy et al. (2018) reveal that if there is high bond and exchange between leaders and members, it is more likely that subordinates will leave when the leader leaves. Jin et al. (2016) concludes that leadership change reduces employees' reliance on the organisation, which results in turnover intention. According to Ng and Feldman (2013), the loss of leadership creates a sense of insecurity about the future, which causes employees to do nothing at work and ultimately diminishes employee job satisfaction. In a study of enterprise managers' career plateaus, Bai (2016) reveals that job satisfaction is negatively associated with staff turnover intention. Yu et al. (2018) established that job satisfaction had a detrimental effect on the intention of employees to leave. According to Liu et al. (2018), the more satisfied employees are with their jobs, the lesser their intention to leave. Job turnover is related to job satisfaction or dissatisfaction: if an employee believes that another job offers more opportunities for satisfaction and fewer opportunities for dissatisfaction than their current role, and if their organisational commitment is low, they are more likely to leave the organisation. This is partially true when the employee believes that another job offers more opportunities for satisfaction and fewer opportunities for dissatisfaction than their current role. Mitchell et al. (2001) coined the term 'job embeddedness' in order to provide light on why individuals stay and so complement the age-old question of why people depart. Individuals become

ingrained in a variety of ways. The more connections they have with their company and their personal life the more likely they are to remain engaged, optimistic and devoted to the organisation. Although leaving is the polar opposite of staying, they argue that the motivations for leaving and staying are not necessarily diametrically opposed. Employees who have a more prestigious network reputation are more likely to stay with their employers (Ballinger et al., 2016). Additionally, embeddedness theory promotes the development of theoretical generalisations to explicate various modes of staying (Ghosh and Gurunathan, 2015). Huysse-Gaytandjieva et al. (2013) discuss how being trapped in an unsatisfying job has a detrimental effect on employees' mental health. It is found that work-related stress, low job commitment and work discontent are the primary reasons for people to quit their jobs. People are constantly on the lookout for stable organisations with opportunities for career progression. There are a variety of factors that influence an employee's decision to remain with or leave an organisation (Kalkman, 2018). Therefore, customer-focused industries, such as the spa business, must ensure job satisfaction for its staff. Failure to do so may jeopardise both the quality of service and the social capital delivered by employees.

To further explore how to engage employees the next section explores the concept of employer branding and attractiveness.

2.8 Employer branding and attractiveness

Employer branding is the strategy to make an organisation the greatest place to work for current and potential employees (Lievens and Slaughter, 2016). Employer branding is critical for many organisations including the spa industry, since they all want to attract, develop and retain the best employees. Employer branding must attract and communicate to both future and current employees. In today's borderless, technology-driven and rapidly changing business environment, satisfying the increased need for employees is one of the most significant organisational challenges (CIPD, 2019). Organisations' survival and success are contingent upon the quality of their staff (Gilani and Cunningham, 2017). Employer branding, as defined by Theurer et al. (2018), is a strategy employed by various businesses to retain

current employees and recruit new ones. Employer branding initiatives that are effective can give a firm a strategic edge by producing engaged employees who are loyal and devoted to the organisation and work towards accomplishing organisational goals (Mouton and Bussin, 2019). Employer branding, as defined by Biswas and Suar (2013), is the process of managing employer–employee interactions. It incorporates the employee's employment history from the beginning of the partnership in order to aid in the retention of talented employees. Mouton and Bussin (2019) define employer branding as a management approach for maintaining current employees and attracting the best personnel. Employer branding is a strategy for retaining employees that affects the whole employment experience while promoting a positive workplace culture and lowering voluntary turnover.

Historically, branding efforts have been directed at the establishment of company and product brands from a consumer standpoint (Tanwar and Prasad, 2016). The restriction and limitation on branding are no longer limited to products. Historically, corporations used branding to sell their products and services; more recently, branding tactics have been applied to human resource management with organisations using branding to attract and retain top personnel. Organisations have recognised that the most effective method to increase their attractiveness in the labour market is to develop a powerful, distinct and transparent employer brand (Biswas and Suar, 2013; Tanwar and Prasad, 2016; Lievens and Slaughter, 2016; Mouton and Bussin, 2019).

Additionally, research indicates that an organisation's overall image and impression in the minds of its employees influences a variety of organisational outcomes, including retention, employee engagement, loyalty and improved talent attraction (Mouton and Bussin, 2019). Biswas and Suar (2013) state that an employer brand must be effective in order to retain its existing employees. Mouton and Bussin (2019) conclude that organisations can provide career opportunities and advancement, foster a creative and innovative environment, engage in social responsibility projects, and offer above-average financial benefits to their employees in order to develop a strong employer brand, which in turn will improve employer

attractiveness and employee retention. According to Bakanauskiene et al. (2016), effective employer branding increases employee job satisfaction and their tendency to remain loyal to the firm. Employer brands that are more actively involved in recruiting are often better managed and have employees who are engaged, constantly learning and growing.

Employment attractiveness is inextricably linked to the concept of employer branding, since it relates to the advantages and benefits that prospective employees perceive as a result of working for a certain organisation (Reis and Braga, 2016). The organisation's image, initial offering and publicly available information all have an effect on the job selection decisions of prospective employees (Berthon, 2005). Age, experience, academic credentials and the success of a corporation are just a few of the characteristics used to determine employment desirability (Bakanauskiene et al., 2016). Linn (2019) suggests that organisational performance, employee relationships, treatment of minorities and affinity with society and environment all impact potential employees' decisions to apply for and accept jobs in an organisation. CSR has a favourable effect on employer attractiveness (Klimkiewicz and Oltra, 2017). Attractive employment benefits the organisation in two ways. One goal is to maintain current employees, while the other is to attract new ones. The most often employed tactics for increasing job attractiveness include strengthening the brand name, upgrading the organisational culture and enhancing the organisational offering (Sommer et al., 2017). Employer branding advantages include learning, growth, advancement, flexible work arrangements, job autonomy, job security and other work culture and practices that employees seek, and each of these comes at a price, so employers must prioritise how best to allocate resources to each of these areas in order to ensure that employees get the most out of their employer branding efforts (Alnaçk et al., 2014). A strong employer brand and attractiveness can be achieved through investing in training and development and reducing employee turnover.

Employer attractiveness, as Linn (2019) argues, is a complex concept. A study by Dabirian et al. (2019) reveals that there are a total of eight different ways in which employers can

communicate their value propositions. **Interest value:** This dimension reflects an individual's level of commitment to a certain employer. Employees in this dimension place a premium on an interesting work environment, creativity and the ability to develop in order to deliver high-quality products and services. **Social value:** The social dimension evaluates the factors of working for a certain organisation. They are referring to the work environment and the nature of the connections with co-workers (fun, happy, collegial, atmosphere, etc.). **Economic value:** The economic dimension is concerned with monetary gains. For prospective employees, it is critical that the organisation offers a competitive compensation, employment security and advancement prospects. **Development value:** Within the growth dimension, factors such as acceptance, self-worth and confidence are used to determine the degree of perceived attractiveness. The possibility of personal growth, as well as the possibility of future employment at another job, is significant. **The application value** reflects the extent to which employees can apply and impart their accumulated knowledge. The potential employee often asks if the job is meaningful and does it provide opportunities to apply knowledge and skills. **Management value:** Leadership skills influenced employees' perceptions of their workplaces. Managers' ability to motivate and inspire others, as well as their expertise and a clear vision, were among the traits noted by employees. **Work-life balance:** Employees want to balance their work-related and non-work-related commitments, such as family and leisure activities. This plays a vital role in perceptions of a workplace. **Brand image:** A brand's image is how it is viewed by its target audience. Overall brand image has a bigger impact on being seen as the best place to work. People have the desire to work for an exciting, cool and bigger organisation in a great location (Dabirian et al., 2019). Therefore, it is essential for service industries including the UK spa industry to enhance employer attractiveness by offering these eight value propositions as developed by Dabirian et al. (2019).

Employer branding and employee engagement can be explained using social exchange theory (Chernyak-Hai and Rabenu, 2017). The basic premise of the social exchange theory

is that a win-win situation can be achieved through mutually beneficial social interaction. Positive employee behaviours and attitudes can be fostered in the workplace if a company can cultivate an employee-friendly culture. Employees aim to reciprocate with higher levels of involvement if the organisation delivers autonomy, support and adequate opportunities for growth and development. In exchange for these benefits, employees demonstrate their commitment to the organisation (Chernyak-Hai and Rabenu, 2017). Because of this, in order to win this 'war for talent', companies plan to implement creative techniques to create a highly motivated and committed staff that is focused on achieving the company's long-term goals (Griffith, 2019).

A strong employer brand evolves during the process of becoming an employer of choice, one who thinks that employees are one of the sustainable competitive advantage resources (Griffith, 2019). Energetic and secure, an engaged employee lives the company's 'brand' since they are in sync with their work environment psychologically. Employees are more likely to be engaged with their work when they are surrounded by a positive work environment, and this can contribute to increased productivity in the workplace (Chernyak-Hai and Rabenu, 2017). The favourable working environment offers employees an experience that may be difficult for competitors to reproduce (Griffith, 2019).

If an employee chooses to work and stay with a company, this is what is meant by retention. Businesses are increasingly dependent on their ability to attract and retain talented workers. Organisations rely heavily on skilled and experienced staff to maintain a competitive edge. Employers want to keep their best employees in order to meet their business goals, as outlined by Singh (2019). Talented, high-performing workers are in high demand in today's job market. Therefore, employers must consider the possibility of losing qualified employees who are in search of new opportunities. A lack of talent necessitates that companies differentiate themselves and sell their brand to potential workers so that they can meet their workforce needs in a timely and effective manner (Singh, 2019). Employee retention is just as critical to an organisation's success as employer recruiting. According to Cloutier et al.

(2015), a company's branding, managerial performance and link to staff retention all have a substantial impact. Chernyak-Hai and Rabenu (2017) support this conclusion by stating that employer branding also has a direct effect on staff retention. Linn (2019) observes that a company's brand name can have a considerable impact on an employee's decision to enter and remain at the organisation. Internal branding has a favourable correlation with staff retention. Employer branding has an effect on employee retention, as Arasanmi and Krishna (2019) demonstrate. According to Reis and Braga (2016), increased views of employer branding are associated with higher retention rates and lower compensation expectations among employees. Lievens and Slaughter (2016) discovered that employer branding, which encompasses compensation strategy, people orientation, leadership and development, is a strong predictor of talent retention. Retention strategies should be developed to ascertain why employees work, depart, and prefer to work for other businesses rather than their current ones. Therefore it is essential for the spa industry to enhance employee retention strategies with strong employer attractiveness. However, Dabirian et al. (2019) argue the two most important elements affecting employee retention are career growth and image, which has been a major issue for the UK spa industry (Bromstein, 2018). Additionally, spa jobs demand high levels of emotional work; therefore, in order to explore more employee attraction, engagement, retention problems a decision was made to review Hochschild's emotional labour theory (Hochschild, 2012) in the following section.

2.9 Hochschild's emotional labour theory (2012)

Study in emotional labour has grown rapidly since the *The Managed Heart* was published by Arlie Russell Hochschild in 1983 (Hochschild, 2012). Workers generally have to manage and regulate their own emotional reactions in order to maintain a caring work atmosphere and achieve other organisational goals, according to Hochschild (2012). The act of managing emotions in the workplace to follow the organisational display rules is called emotional labour. With its harsh, neoconservative climate in Reagan's United States, *The Managed*

Heart shows and opposes the harm caused by a growing demand for 'customer service', where human emotions are turned into commodities that can be bought (Brook, 2009).

Emotional labour is a conceptual tool to evaluate employees' emotions at work (Bratton and Watson, 2018). Hochschild (2012) argues that any human emotions that arise in an organisation can be termed 'emotion labour'. Hochschild's (2012) *The Managed Heart* is focused on the jobs of a flight attendant and bill collector and how they present socially desirable emotions. Hochschild argues that emotion management is very hard and employees can get alienated due to emotional labour (Hochschild, 2012). Empirical understanding of emotional labour is essential for employees and employers where jobs that require a high degree of emotional labour can lead to burnout (Niven, 2017). This procedure requires sustained and considerable mental effort, which has been associated with emotional tiredness, a loss of interest and dissatisfaction in the profession, and a possible rise in stress-related disorders and employee burnout. A study by Lee et al. (2018) shows that high emotional overload at work leads to depersonalisation whereas Yin et al. (2019) find emotional exhaustion and a sense of ineffectiveness in employees required to perform high levels of emotional labour.

Hochschild's (2012) emotional labour theory is the process where employees manage and display their emotions to meet the 'organisational feeling rules'. She argues that employees are obliged to suppress their true feelings and ensure the displayed emotions are appropriate for particular personal or professional settings (Hochschild, 2012). According to Bratton and Watson (2018), employees need to follow certain 'display rules' set by the organisation. Hochschild (2012) explains that flight attendants are specifically paid to smile, serve food and drinks and provide a wonderful experience full of happiness to travellers to meet the display rules set by the organisation. She found that air hostesses are capable of managing emotions in order to provide a great customer satisfaction. Brook (2009) argues that employees need to manage and create a publicly observable emotion display; which is sold for wage which has exchange value. Organisations are driven by profit where profit is being

pursued by excellent customer satisfaction and customer satisfaction is achieved by exploiting emotional labour (Brook, 2009; Hochschild, 2012; Bratton and Watson, 2018).

2.9.1 Display rules and feeling rules

Organisations do not openly admit that they control and regulate employee emotions (Dahling, 2017). Hochschild (2012) characterises this control as being exerted through feeling and display rules, which are both formal and informal expectations and norms that govern the employee's emotional experience. Hochschild (2012) examines how emotions are regulated socially and individually and makes a distinction between universal norms and rules specific to certain social groups. Individuals' feelings and display rules also affect and govern their social interactions. Display rules are guidelines or standards of behaviour that specify which emotions are appropriate for a certain scenario and how they should be displayed (Niven, 2017).

Hochschild (2012) claims that display rules generate emotional inauthenticity where employees are often caught between what they feel and what they should feel. Bhowmick and Mulla (2016) argue that internal and private emotions are seen as authentic where displayed emotions are a demand of the organisation. Displayed emotions are defined as those that are expressed by facial expression, tone of voice, body gestures and the language employed, and frequently demand the outward expression of one feeling while suppressing an alternate, inner and real emotion (Niven, 2017). This is frequently done in order to influence the emotions of others in order to induce compliance on the part of the employee (Brook, 2009). Employee emotion management is inextricably linked to the concept of competitive advantage (Walsh, 2019). Walsh (2019) argues that appropriate emotional expression by service employees results in business success, as these service employees represent the organisation's brand. To establish a positive corporate image, it is vital to realise that 'emotional display rules' define criteria or guidelines for proper emotional expression in particular contexts (Walsh, 2019).

Display rules are rules about how people should feel and show their emotions. Organisations will use a variety of ways to monitor and enforce these rules, such as bonuses and promotions, or in the workplace's culture, where people who show bad emotions are challenged by their co-workers (Akanji, 2016). In some organisations display rules are clear instructions about how to act, where Hochschild (2012) found that cabin crew members were trained on how to regulate their emotions during customer interaction. Additionally she found that employees were either enforced to suppress their authentic feelings or match their feelings through surface acting and deep acting. Hochschild (2012) argues that we all manage and display our emotions in our private life and we are not obliged or forced to do so. But in a workplace employees do not have choice as their emotions are dictated by organisational display rules.

2.9.2 Surface acting and deep acting

Employees are obliged to follow organisational display rules at work where Hochschild (2012) illustrated emotional labour in a distinction between 'surface acting' and 'deep acting'. The way that the employee knows how to show their feelings and emotions appropriately is defined by the feeling rules of the organisation. When the employee's natural feeling does not match the 'feelings rules, surface acting or deep acting strategy is required which is called emotional management' (Niven, 2017).

'Surface acting' refers to pretending or faking an emotion where employees display the emotions required by the job (Schutz and Lee, 2014). Employees have to put on a fake emotion and suppress their true feelings because employers frequently demand that employees follow display rules. While an employee may be having a poor day and experiencing negative effect, he or she can conceal these emotions at the workplace by smiling or seeming pleasant. Surface acting is also used strategically by employees attempting to comply with display rules or retain their jobs, rather than for the business or consumers (Shanock et al., 2013). Past studies shows that surface acting is more effortful, exhausting and emotionally demanding which can lead to emotional exhaustion through

continuous suppression of true feelings and putting on fake emotions for a period of time (Hochschild, 2012; Schutz and Lee, 2014; Akanji, 2016). Thwaites (2017) also argues that surface acting may generate an emotional dissonance indicating a difference between what an employee feels and what they ought to feel. Surface acting has been linked to detrimental employee outcomes such as burnout, problems with well-being, intention to leave, and stress (Sadien, 2010; Petree, 2014; Thwaites, 2017; Walsh, 2019).

On the other hand, 'deep acting involves an effortful process where employees change their actual feeling to align with "feeling rules" expected by the organisation' (Schutz and Lee, 2014). Hochschild's (2012) deep acting appears when employees look for comfort space free from the risk of emotional exhaustion (Walsh, 2019). Hochschild (2012) postulates that employees engage in deep acting by attempting to feel and experience desired emotions or by recalling similar emotions from memory or imagination.

Ashforth and Humphrey (1993) suggest a third strategy, 'genuine acting', where employees' genuine feelings match the organisation's feeling rules. When an employee expresses true feelings, he or she does not experience emotional dissonance; hence, the emotion may be expressed with little or no effort, and the employee may avoid the negative consequences associated with professions requiring significant emotional labour. Although deep acting necessitates a significant investment of time, energy and resources, the rewards for people who engage in deep acting are frequently beneficial. Deep acting has been shown to provide beneficial consequences for employees and employers, or at the very least to delay the occurrence of negative effects of emotional labour (Huang et al., 2015).

Kinman and Leggetter (2016) argue that emotional labour is a major issue for the organisation which requires strong emotional display where excessive customer contact can lead to negative employee well-being. Employees are required or even forced to modify their emotional expression as part of their job to enhance organisational performance (Alsakarneh et al., 2019). Emotional labour can be further explored by looking at the concept of alienation (Feuerbach et al., 1997; Brooks, 2009; Hochschild, 2012).

2.9.3 Alienation

The theory of alienation was first introduced by Karl Marx in 1944 when he discussed four aspects of alienation of labour in a capitalist society (Feuerbach et al., 1997). Alienation from the product of labour is one; alienation from the action of labour is another; alienation from one's own unique humanity is a third; and alienation from others in society is the fourth (Feuerbach et al., 1997). Karl Marx famously argued that the essential relationship between employees and money generates alienation (Feuerbach et al., 1997). Hochschild's (2012) emotional labour theory explains two types of alienation. She argues that employees are alienated from the emotional labour product and the emotional labour process.

Emotion work is the process where employees manage and display emotions in their private realm where emotional labour involves the commercialisation of employees' emotions which is consumed by the customers. This management process has the cost of employees being alienated from their emotional product (Bratton and Watson, 2018). Hochschild (2012) uses the perception of Karl Marx's alienation theory where she argues that human feelings have become increasingly commercialised and this modern capitalist society is putting too much pressure on emotional management capabilities of employees, which may lead to employees being alienated. Employees do not have ownership of their own feelings, where employers hold control of employees' feelings and emotions (Schutz and Lee, 2014).

Hochschild (2012) argues that there is uneven emotional exchange relationship between employees and customers where the 'customer is always right'. Everyone is free to negotiate their emotion exchange in their private life but in professional and public work life, employees often need to accept the uneven exchange of emotion and tolerate being treated with anger, disrespect and humiliation by consumers (Sadien, 2010). Hochschild (2012) argues that employers codified the 'display rules' for employees in order to provide the highest customer satisfaction. These rules dictate the emotional display of the employees where employees are alienated from the emotional product and the emotional labour process where employee may experience 'burnout', feeling 'phoney' and 'emotional

deadness' (Hochschild, 2012; Dahling, 2017). These effects of emotional labour and alienation on employees is further explored in following section.

2.9.4 Effects of emotional labour

Past studies have shown both positive and negative effects of emotional labour on employees (Sadien, 2010; Schutz and Lee, 2014; Mayer et al., 2016; Dahling, 2017; Alsakarneh et al., 2019). From the organisational point of view, emotional labour is likely to positively increase business productivity and customer satisfaction (Lee et al., 2018). Studies by Bratton and Watson (2018) and Mayer et al. (2016) argue that emotional labour has a positive relationship with job satisfaction where non-verbal and expressive behaviours (e.g. smiling, eye contact and pleasant vocal tone) that are compatible with organisational display standards have been linked to customer satisfaction. Hochschild (2012) suggests that emotional labour has human cost attached to it where intensive emotional burden on employees may lead to a psychological impact on their feelings towards work. Thwaites (2017), Pandey and Singh (2016) and Jeung et al. (2018) support this by stating that emotional labour can drastically obstruct the performance and well-being of an employee which can lead to emotional exhaustion, frustration, stress, fatigue, burnout and depersonalisation. Furthermore, Hochschild (2012) argues that emotional labour leads to lower job satisfaction and lower self-esteem. Brook (2009) and Yorulmaz et al. (2015) argue that employees who are expected to express or feel emotions they do not feel naturally will experience 'alienation' from their own feelings, resulting in psychological harm to their health. Additionally, emotional labour can result in a decline in service quality, a high rate of employment turnover and low motivation (Marques et al., 2018).

Studies have shown that there are positive individual outcomes as well. For example, Bratton and Watson (2018) found that deep acting is beneficial to physical and mental health of employees. Wen et al. (2019) also claim that deep acting has positive relation with employee job satisfaction on the one hand, while, on the other hand, emotional labour is likely to have negative outcome for employees, especially when engaging in surface acting

(Wen et al., 2019). The process of emotional labour can drastically obstruct the performance and well-being of an employee, leading to emotional exhaustion, frustration, stress, fatigue, burnout and depersonalisation (Thwaites, 2017; Marques et al., 2018). Mayer et al. (2016) state that emotional labour has a negative outcome in the absence of emotional intelligence. Display rules dictated by the organisation have negative outcome on employees, especially when employees are required to suppress negative emotions, since hiding negative emotions leads to high blood pressure and stress (Hochschild, 2012; Taxer and Frenzel, 2015).

Several scholars have highlighted job satisfaction and burnout as the focal points of emotional labour (Song, 2014; Ybarra et al., 2014; Mayer et al., 2016; Marques et al., 2018). Job satisfaction refers to the employees' feelings toward the job. Hochschild (2012) argues that emotional labour is associated with job satisfaction where previous research on emotional labour and job satisfaction have mixed results. Song (2014), Ybarra et al. (2014) and Mayer et al. (2016) argue that emotional labour helps to increase job satisfaction. Alternatively, Taxer and Frenzel (2015), Thwaites (2017) and Marques et al. (2018) suggest that employees who perform higher emotional labour have lower job satisfaction. Most of the past studies agree that surface acting leads to low job satisfaction leading to emotional exhaustion, depersonalisation and burnout (Song, 2014; Ybarra et al., 2014; Thwaites, 2017; Marques et al., 2018). However, there are mixed findings in the relation between deep acting and employee outcome (job satisfaction or burnout). Multiple studies have reported that deep acting has a positive relation between deep acting and job satisfaction which reduces emotional exhaustion and burnout (Mayer et al., 2016; Bratton and Watson, 2018; Wen et al., 2019). Other studies from Hwa (2012) and Schaible and Six (2016) argue that there is no relation between deep acting and burnout. Xin et al. (2017), meanwhile, found that emotional labour can be psychologically demanding and that prolonged deep acting can result in burnout.

2.9.5 Burnout

Burnout has been dubbed the greatest workplace hazard in the emotional labour model (Kinman and Leggetter, 2016). Work-related stress can cause burnout, a psychological tiredness syndrome that results in a decline in physical energy and increased job dissatisfaction. Burnout occurs as a result of persistent work-related stress (Marques et al., 2018). Overwhelming feelings of exhaustion, animosity toward work and a lack of personal accomplishment are all symptoms of this job-related malaise (Maslach and Leiter, 2009; Schaufeli et al., 2018). Burnout, which was initially examined in the medical and psychiatric disciplines, has become more common in a wide range of professions and enterprises. Burnout has harmful implications that transcend beyond employees' particular emotions and experiences (Schaufeli et al., 2018). Burnout has been linked to lower individual, team and organisational performance (Palenzuela et al., 2019), as well as impeded creativity and innovation (Noworol et al., 2017) and workplace errors, accidents and injuries (Zadow et al., 2017). Burnout is also linked to detrimental work practices such as increased absenteeism and employee turnover (Lambert et al., 2010; Hoff et al., 2019).

Burnout, has been the primary focus of academics researching the effects of emotional labour on employees (Hoff et al., 2019). Employees experience burnout when they feel their job obligation is higher than their capacity (Schaufeli et al., 2018). When a job has extensive emotional obligation and employees do not possess emotional intelligence, it will be likely to lead to employee burnout (Mayer et al., 2016). According to Schaufeli et al. (2018), burnout can be measured by analysing three dimensions: emotional exhaustion, depersonalisation and diminished feelings of accomplishment. Emotional exhaustion is a type of role conflict in which people are pressured to act in ways that are incompatible with their genuine feelings (Maslach and Leiter, 2009). Depersonalisation is a negative affective state in which an employee suffers a prolonged and acute level of exhaustion and attempts to prevent additional losses of personal resources by emotionally distancing oneself and viewing others as impersonal objects rather than persons (Zadow et al., 2017). As a result, people develop

a cold, dehumanised, cynical and uncaring attitude towards employment in general, and the people who use their services in particular. Personal achievement is the employees' sense of value and accomplishment at a job (Schaufeli et al., 2018). Emotional dissonance is one of the primary outcomes of performing emotional labour, which has resulted in a variety of undesirable results (Noworol et al., 2017; Zadow et al., 2017). Emotional dissonance occurs in the workplace when there is a disagreement between felt emotions and emotions expressed to conform to display rules.

It is no secret that employees need to deal with difficult customers. As a result of the frequent occurrence of unpleasant behaviour by customers, many employees experience an increase in their level of anxiety. When dealing with clients, employees try to disguise their unpleasant emotions by putting on a show of surface acting, which reduces their overall well-being (Zadow et al., 2017). Employees often try to hide their negative emotions while dealing with difficult and nightmare customers, thus they engage in more surface acting (Simillidou et al., 2020). Therefore it is essential to equip employees with emotional intelligence to cope with emotional exhaustion (Mayer et al., 2016).

'Emotional intelligence is the ability of an employee to successfully comprehend and regulate their own and their customers' emotions' (Mayer et al., 2016). Emotional intelligence is defined as a person's ability to recognise and respond to their own emotions, as well as the emotions of others. Emotional intelligence can be developed and generated with minimal cognitive functioning and strain through ongoing learning in the workplace (Serrat, 2017). Emotional intelligence, according to Mayer et al. (2016), can be improved by practice, education and exposure to different emotional situations. When it comes to performing emotional labour in the workplace, employees may benefit from the natural regulation process known as 'emotional intelligence'. Mayer et al. (2016) measure three components of 'emotional intelligence': emotional self-awareness, emotional other-awareness, and emotion management. Employees' emotional self-awareness refers to their capacity to comprehend their own feelings and to identify the source of those feelings. Emotional other-awareness

refers to an individual's capacity to comprehend the emotions of others. Emotion regulation is the process of controlling one's emotions in order to accomplish goals. Organisational performance improves when employees have higher levels of emotional intelligence (Lopes, 2016; Mayer et al., 2016; Serrat, 2017).

In an effort to mitigate the harmful effects of emotional labour, authors have focused on the role of job autonomy (Bhowmick et al., 2016; Han, 2018; Simillidou et al., 2020). It is the degree to which an employee's employment provides the employee with freedom of choice, independence and discretion in performing and carrying out job obligations (Badolamenti et al., 2017). Having a degree of job autonomy means that an employee can apply their own ideas and devise their own methods for completing various duties (Simillidou et al., 2019). A modest degree of autonomy in the workplace can help staff cope better with clients' unpleasant behaviour and emotional labour (Han, 2018). Employees who have a sense of autonomy in their jobs tend to be happier and more satisfied with their work (Han, 2018). Job autonomy will alleviate the strain and tiredness caused by surface acting's attempt to regulate one's emotions. Employees' energy drain when confronted with emotional dissonance can be mitigated if they have a high degree of job autonomy. When employees believe they have little or no control over some aspects of their jobs and have very little or no autonomy, this results in more severe consequences, more stress and discontent when confronted with challenging situations and being forced to engage in surface acting (Han, 2018).

2.10 Summary

In this chapter, literature on employee engagement (Kahn, 1990; Markos and Sridevi, 2010) employer branding (Lievens and Slaughter, 2016) and attractiveness (Ambler and Barrow, 1996; Bethron, 2005; Alnaçk et al. 2014), emotional labour (Hochschild, 2012; Brook, 2009) and spa environment were reviewed. The chapter begins with the overview of the UK spa industry. Increased awareness of health and well-being has led to an increase in demand for spa facilities. As a result, the spa business is booming with an annual growth rate of 9.9 per

cent, but the number of workers has increased by just 1.3 per cent in the UK (Statista, 2018: Global Wellness Institute, 2018). There are more than 7.000 job vacancies in the spa industry but demand is one thing and filling them is another. It is clear that the spa industry is not attracting employees. Attracting employees is one thing but employee retention is also a major problem for the UK spa industry. Since there are no past studies on the UK spa industry, the focus in this study moves to the literature on employee engagement, employee turnover, employer branding and attractiveness and emotional labour to identify the staffing problems of the UK spa industry.

Employee engagement is about how employees feel about their jobs through physical, emotional and cognitive involvement. Khan (1990) identifies three psychological factors associated with employee engagement and disengagement at work as meaningfulness, safety and availability. Ibrahim and Falasi (2014) argue that employee engagement helps encourage and link people emotionally, cognitively and physically to the organisation.

Employee branding is considered as the key employee engagement strategy as it helps to attract potential employees and retain current valuable employees. Dabirian et al. (2019) identify eight factors that potential employees look for before applying for a job: interest, social, economic, development, application, management, work-life and brand value.

Organisations can provide career opportunities and advancement, foster a creative and innovative environment, engage in social responsibility projects, and offer greater financial benefits to their employees in order to develop a strong employer brand, which in turn will improve employer attractiveness and employee retention. Employees leave an organisation because of low job satisfaction (Zahra 2018), low wage (Brown, 2018), limited career opportunities and role stressors (Reb, 2017). Therefore employee engagement is key to retaining valuable employees (Turner, 2020).

The opposite of engagement is burnout. Hochschild (2012) argues that emotional labour has a human cost behind it and this can lead to employee burnout. Emotional labour refers to the process through which service workers' emotional displays conform to managerially imposed

organisational feeling rules. Jobs that require a high degree of emotional labour can lead to emotional exhaustion, depersonalisation and burnout (Blau et al., 2012). Emotional labour is inducing an emotional state in another person while also controlling one's own emotions. Hochschild (2012) differentiates emotional labour into surface acting for the purpose of deception and deep acting for the purpose of eliciting genuine feelings in workers, as needed by organisations.

Most of the past studies agree that surface acting leads to low job satisfaction leading to emotional exhaustion, depersonalisation and burnout (Song, 2014; Ybarra et al., 2014; Thwaites, 2017; Marques et al., 2018). However, there are mixed findings in the relation between deep acting and employee outcomes (job satisfaction or burnout). Multiple studies have reported that there is a positive relation between deep acting and job satisfaction which reduces emotional exhaustion and burnout (Mayer et al., 2016; Bratton and Watson, 2018; Wen et al., 2019). Other studies from Hwa (2012) and Schaible and Six (2016) argue that there is no relation between deep acting and burnout. On the other hand, Xin et al. (2017) found that emotional labour can be psychologically demanding and prolonged deep acting can result in burnout.

Employee engagement is a crucial aspect of organisational success and should be considered as a top priority by organisations. Engagement is defined as a positive and fulfilling emotional and intellectual connection employees have with their work and workplace (Kahn, 1990). It is characterised by a level of involvement and enthusiasm that leads to high levels of productivity and job satisfaction. The benefits of employee engagement are well documented and include increased job satisfaction, better morale, reduced employee turnover and increased productivity (Alvi et al., 2014; Carrillo, 2019). These benefits are not only beneficial to the employees but also to the organisations as they result in increased profits, improved customer satisfaction and a more positive organisational culture. In order to support employee engagement, organisations need to understand the drivers of engagement. These drivers include factors such as clear communication, opportunities for

growth and development, recognition and rewards, work–life balance and a positive work environment (Markos and Sridevi, 2010). By addressing these drivers and creating a workplace culture that prioritises employee engagement, organisations can create a positive, productive and profitable work environment. In addition, emotional labour and burnout are also crucial elements that affect employee engagement. Emotional labour (Hochschild, 2012) refers to the regulation of one's emotions in response to job demands, while burnout is characterised by feelings of exhaustion, cynicism and decreased professional efficacy. Both emotional labour and burnout can have a negative impact on employee engagement and it is important for organisations to address them in order to promote engagement and prevent employee turnover (Ibrahim and Falasi, 2014). Overall, employee engagement is a complex and multi-dimensional concept that is essential for organisational success. By understanding the drivers of engagement and addressing emotional labour and burnout, organisations can create a work environment that supports employee engagement and benefits both the employees and the organisation.

2.11 Literature gap

In spa literature, emotional labour and employee engagement are rarely discussed together. Khadka (2015) looked at the well-being of spa employees in Nepal where she found that spa job demands are high and the only motivation factor of spa employees is money which is affecting their well-being. Due to the poor standard of living, Peri et al. (2015) found that the motivation of spa personnel in Serbia is unsatisfactory and that the financial component is the most important motivator. Similarly Craig (2018) found that spa therapists' work functioning in high-volume job environments has been linked to a reduction in wellness. Khadka (2015) conducted research in Nepal, while Peri et al. (2015) conducted research in Serbia. The living standards in both countries are similar, which may explain why the results and findings are the same, but UK has different living standards which may lead to different findings concerning working environment and motivation. Blau et al. (2013) and Craig (2018) conducted a study within the UK spa industry and identified high physical work as the key

factor leading spa therapists to leave the industry. Furthermore, Wisnom and Gallagher's (2018) study investigated the quality of work life (QWL) of 107 resort spa employees in the United States. Good working conditions, fair wages, appreciation, interesting work, and a sense of involvement were the most crucial factors in motivating employees, with compensation and benefits such as health insurance, retirement/pension plans, bonuses, and dental insurance also being essential. However, the study found that the resort spa industry fell short in providing fair wages, employee loyalty, and overall QWL. Smith and Wallace (2019) highlighted the importance of employee training, career development, and leadership in promoting employee motivation, with empathy and effective communication being critical qualities for spa managers. None of the previous studies have looked at the emotional side of work and both lack an in-depth investigation through lens of emotional labour (Hochschild, 2012).

The Covid-19 pandemic has disrupted the workforce within the UK spa industry. The more pressing concern is how the industry will adapt and what shape it will take in the coming years. This presented an emerging research gap concerning the impact of Covid-19 upon the spa sector and further clarified the limitation of HR theorising on the issues and challenges for employee engagement, emotional labour, employee branding and attractiveness due to the global pandemic. This not only limited the nature of this enquiry in terms of primary research but opened new lines of thinking in terms of new contributions to understanding the business issues of employee engagement, employer branding, attractiveness and emotional labour. To address these concerns a qualitative methodology was adopted to address the aim of the research:

to investigate the staffing problems in the UK spa industry in order to identify and develop a commercially available model for employee engagement within the industry.

The research objectives serve as a road map, beginning with what has to be accomplished and ending with a likely outcome that answers a study question. The following are the sub-questions associated with the aim:

1. To determine the key factors and importance of employee motivation, engagement and retention in the spa industry with a focus on the period of Covid-19
2. To identify the most commonly used employee motivation, engagement and retention strategies within the UK spa business in terms of the impacts of Covid-19
3. To explore the challenges faced by management in employee motivation, engagement and retention strategies during and after the Covid-19 lockdown periods
4. To investigate how to develop future employment attractiveness in the UK spa industry by using employee motivation, engagement and retention strategies.

This is reflected in the following conceptual framework:

Figure 1: Conceptual framework

The conceptual framework presented in Figure 1 suggests that employee engagement and burnout are two opposite outcomes of employee motivation towards work, with emotional labour playing a crucial role in employee burnout. Studies have shown that surface acting can lead to low job satisfaction, emotional exhaustion, depersonalisation and burnout (Song, 2014; Ybarra et al., 2014; Thwaites, 2017; Marques et al., 2018). However, there are mixed findings regarding the relationship between deep acting and employee outcomes, with some studies reporting a positive relationship between deep acting and job satisfaction, which reduces emotional exhaustion and burnout (Mayer et al., 2016; Bratton and Watson, 2018; Wen et al., 2019). Nevertheless, prolonged deep acting can lead to burnout as emotional labour can be psychologically demanding (Xin et al., 2017).

In terms of addressing burnout and promoting employee engagement, employer branding and attractiveness strategies can play a significant role (Alvi et al., 2014; Carrillo, 2019). By improving the attractiveness of the work environment, such strategies can increase employee engagement, resulting in job satisfaction, employee retention and attraction. Overall, the conceptual framework highlights the importance of emotional labour in understanding employee motivation, burnout and engagement, and the role of employer branding and attractiveness strategies in promoting positive employee outcomes.

3 Chapter 3: Methodology

The research methodology section details the steps taken by the researcher when conducting the study, including the identification, selection, analysis and presentation of the study's data findings. This study investigates the staffing crisis in the spa industry in the United Kingdom to find and develop a commercially viable model for employee engagement in the spa sector in the United Kingdom. The study will conduct extensive research involving the suitable selection of research philosophy, methodologies and design and sample procedures and frame, which is explained in more detail in the following sections.

3.1 Research philosophy

Research philosophy focuses on the source, nature and development of knowledge (Saunders et al., 2016). In other words, research philosophy is a set of beliefs on the collection, analysis and use of facts about a topic. In management and business study, the term 'research philosophy' has been frequently used to clarify the research design and recommend the method of data collecting and analysis (Easterby-Smith et al., 2018).

Research philosophy enables the identification of each research approach's limitations and the identification and development of new designs. According to Saunders et al. (2019), research philosophy is the essential beginning point for any research process.

Tsoukas and Chia (2011) claim that there is no one optimum philosophy for business and management research in which scholars cannot agree on a single best philosophy. Each philosophy excels at distinct tasks. It is critical to comprehend philosophical debates to establish our philosophy and, more importantly, to comprehend the concept of the research paradigm while designing a research approach (Saunders et al., 2019). Understanding the research philosophy might aid in the study's design (Easterby-Smith et al., 2018). It can assist researchers in determining what data is necessary for the research question, how the data should be collected and how the research question should be answered. Saunders et al. (2012) state that a 'research onion' clearly distinguishes the key research philosophies as pragmatism, realism, positivism and interpretivism.

Figure 2: Research onion (Saunders et al., 2019)

It is crucial to understand the difference between different research philosophies. Saunders et al. (2012) suggest that ontological, epistemological and methodological questions must be considered and answered to understand and determine the philosophical position of this work.

Assumptions concerning the nature of reality are known as ontologies. According to Gomm (2009), ontology is the 'study of being' that explains what it means to exist. According to Don-Solomon and Eke (2018), ontology is the study of what is 'real' and what can be learned about it. Ontological assumptions shape the research objects researchers observe and study (Saunders et al., 2019). Ontological assumptions significantly affect how researchers view and explore their research. Thus, the researcher's ontological assumptions determine how the researcher views the world of business and management and the research topic (Saunders et al., 2019).

Ontology refers to a set of beliefs representing the researcher's understanding of what makes a fact. It is a concept that refers to what we consider to be reality. Ontology is concerned with the essential issue of whether social phenomena must be viewed objectively or subjectively (Saunders et al., 2019). In other words, within the scope of a study, the researcher must decide whether the world is external to the social world or whether social actors' perceptions and behaviours create social phenomena. The reality of the objectivist stance may be quantified, tested and established since social actors who are concerned about their lives exist in an external world (Don-Solomon and Eke, 2018). On the other hand, subjective reality refers to social phenomena that are generated as a result of social actors' perceptions and actions (Don-Solomon and Eke, 2018). This study adheres to the subjectivist perspective, which holds that realities are multiple and socially produced. The perceptions and subsequent actions of the spa industry's various stakeholders, including personnel, employers and consumers, shape realities or social phenomena. The researcher approaches subjects under enquiry to learn more about the issue and how to fix it. Because everything is contextual, qualitative methodologies with small samples enable in-depth exploration (Easterby-Smith et al., 2018). Therefore, the researcher collects and analyses different documents (news, articles, reports, grey literature) regarding the UK's spa industry to have more prosperous and more valid data. When analysing the many perspectives on what defines reality, the researcher's following questions are how that reality will be evaluated and what constitutes knowledge of that reality. The next part will explore epistemology.

Epistemology is a broad term that encompasses both assumptions and theories of knowledge. It begs the question of what constitutes acceptable, valid and legitimate knowledge and how knowledge is transferred to others (Don-Solomon and Eke, 2018). While it may appear to be somewhat abstract at first glance, the relevance of epistemology is much more precise and obvious. The epistemological assumption is about how the researcher

gains knowledge of reality and what may be known or represented as knowledge (Saunders et al., 2012).

The research onion structure proposed by Saunders et al. (2019) was used in this study because it enables the development of distinct concepts and connections throughout the research layers. Saunders et al. (2019) produced a framework that is extremely useful due to its broader idea of methodology, a systematic approach to research methodology that logically expresses philosophical perspectives and methods to any research. There are five different philosophical approaches to developing research: positivism, critical realism, interpretivism, postmodernism and pragmatism (Saunders et al., 2019). Many scholars, such as Saunders et al. (2019), Easterby-Smith et al. (2018) and Bell and Waters (2018), contend that the term 'paradigm' is open to many different interpretations in academic research. It has been suggested that a paradigm is a collection of beliefs that controls what and how research is conducted (Bell and Waters, 2018). It is essential to understand the difference between different paradigms, where the following table illustrates five different paradigms.

Table 1: List of research paradigm Source (Saunders et al., 2019)

Ontology (nature of reality or being)	Epistemology (what constitutes acceptable knowledge)	Axiology (role of values)	Typical methods
Positivism			
Real, external, independent One true reality (universalism) Granular (things)	Scientific method Observable and measurable facts Law-like generalisations Numbers	Value-free research Researcher is detached, neutral and independent of what is researched Researcher maintains	Typically deductive, highly structured, large samples, measurement, typically quantitative methods of analysis, but a range of data can be analysed

Ordered	Causal explanation and prediction as contribution	objective stance	
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Critical realism

Stratified/layered (the empirical, the actual and the real)	Epistemological relativism Knowledge historically situated and transient	Value-laden research Researcher acknowledges bias by world views, cultural experience and upbringing	Retroductive, in-depth historically situated analysis of pre-existing structures and emerging agency. Range of methods and data types to fit subject matter
External, independent Intransient	Facts are social constructions	Researcher tries to minimise bias and errors	
Objective structures Causal mechanisms	Historical causal explanation as contribution	Researcher is as objective as possible	

Interpretivism

Complex, rich Socially constructed through culture and language	Theories and concepts too simplistic Focus on narratives, stories, perceptions and interpretations	Value-bound research Researchers are part of what is researched, subjective	Typically inductive. Small samples, in-depth investigations, qualitative methods of analysis, but a range of data can be interpreted
Multiple meanings, interpretations, realities Flux of processes,	New understandings and worldviews as contribution	Researcher interpretations key to contribution Researcher reflexive	

experiences, practices			
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Postmodernism

Nominal	What counts as 'truth' and 'knowledge' is decided by	Value-constituted research	Typically deconstructive – reading texts and realities
Complex, rich	dominant ideologies	Researcher and research embedded in power	against themselves
Socially constructed through power relations	Focus on absences, silences and oppressed/	relations	In-depth investigations of anomalies, silences and absences
Some meanings, interpretations, realities are dominated and silenced by others	repressed meanings, interpretations and voices	Some research narratives are repressed and silenced at the expense of others	
Flux of processes, experiences, practices	Exposure of power relations and challenge of dominant views as contribution	Researcher radically reflexive	Range of data types, typically qualitative methods of analysis

Pragmatism

Complex, rich, external	Practical meaning of knowledge in specific contexts	Value-driven research	Following research problem and research question
'Reality' is the practical consequences of ideas	'True' theories and knowledge are those that enable successful action	Research initiated and sustained by researcher's doubts and beliefs	Range of methods: mixed, multiple, qualitative, quantitative, action research
Flux of processes, experiences and practices	Focus on problems, practices and relevance	Researcher reflexive	Emphasis on practical solutions and outcomes
	Problem solving and		

	informed future practice as contribution		
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Positivism is the philosophical stance of the natural scientist and demands working with visible social reality to develop law-like generalisations (Saunders et al., 2019). The technique employs objective methodologies and necessitates the observer's independence from the observed subject (Kock et al., 2017). In this case, a quantitative method must be used, which requires testing hypotheses and statistics (Saunders et al., 2019). The positivist emphasises a strictly scientific empiricist method intended to produce pure data and facts, free of human interpretation or bias. Those who support this paradigm view the world as real and consider it steady (Saunders et al., 2019). Positivists hold that there is objective reality separate from social reality and that this reality is not a product of the human mind.

Essentially, positivism holds that examining the social world in the same manner as the physical one is the only approach to uncover new knowledge and this ought to occur in a value-free manner. This means that acquiring an in-depth understanding of how and why individuals act the way they do is impossible. It doesn't appear to be the best research strategy for this project.

Realism is a term that refers to scientific investigation that places a premium on the reality projected as truth by our senses. It holds the belief that objects exist independently of the human intellect. The method is cognisant of the various constructions and meanings that individuals ascribe to their own experiences and the reasons for those distinctions (Saunders et al., 2019). Realists believe that the world exists regardless of our understanding of it.

Realists put information in a variety of different contexts. In other words, data are made and analysed in light of different beliefs and theories (Fletcher, 2017).

Interpretivism is a way of thinking about how people are and how they interact with each other in the world. The interpretivist looks at the social roles of other people through our own set of meanings or perspectives. It has been taken by a 'feelings' researcher, who is

interested in studying people's emotions and how they interact with each other. The idea is that our knowledge of reality is made up by people who live together. According to this view, value-free data can't be found because the person who is looking for it uses their own thoughts to help them with their search. Furthermore, the researcher interacts with the people who are the subjects of the research, which changes both people's perspectives (Saunders et al., 2019). This perspective implies that individuals cannot be separated from the social contexts in which they exist (Bell and Bryman, 2007). Additionally, they emphasise that the most significant way to understand individuals is to examine their perceptions of theory and activities. Finally, Bryman and Bell (2007) note that researchers include their values and interests in their work, making them subjective because they are a part of what they see.

Pragmatists might mix positivist and interpretive viewpoints within a single research framework by considering the research questions and aims. The pragmatist is not bound to any one system of reality and is free to choose among paradigms to best fulfil the research demands (Klassen, 2012). A pragmatic approach to research entails selecting the method that appears to be the most appropriate for the study problem (Saunders et al., 2019). The approach implies that the most important part of the study is the research question or topic (Saunders et al., 2019). The researcher who adopts a pragmatism approach disassociates themselves from the never-ending philosophical arguments over truth and reality (Parvaiz et al., 2019) by acknowledging the various approaches to viewing the world and performing research. Pragmatists acknowledge that there are many ways to see the world and do research where no single point of view could show the whole picture unless many realities were used (Bell and Waters, 2018). Pragmatic researchers can employ any method, strategy or technique associated with qualitative or quantitative research. Additionally, numerous research pragmatically combines qualitative and quantitative methodologies (Saunders et al., 2019). This does not mean that pragmatics always use a lot of different methods. Instead, they use the method or procedures that allow them to get credible, well-founded,

dependable and relevant data that helps with their research (Kelemen and Rumens, 2008).

Practical solutions that influence current practice are the goal of pragmatic research, beginning with the identification of a problem (Saunders et al., 2019).

It appears that the pragmatism approach is the most relevant to this research. The study aims to investigate the staffing problem in the UK spa industry to identify and develop a commercially available model for employee engagement within the industry. Using the pragmatism research philosophy, the researcher could mix several research approaches into one study. Additionally, the pragmatist philosophy was deemed valid since it ensured that the perspectives of various stakeholders, including employees, managers, employers and customers, could be elicited to investigate the spa industry's staffing challenges in the United Kingdom. Historically, research has taken a variety of forms. There are numerous techniques to study, and researchers typically use the most appropriate approach for their research. However, they frequently take the most appropriate one for them personally (Ali, and Birley, 1999). These approaches demonstrate the relationship between theory and data (Kelemen and Rumens, 2008).

This study adopts a pragmatic approach, which prioritizes practicality over absolute truth or reality (Weaver and Olson, 2006). The early proponents of pragmatism rejected the notion that a single scientific method could provide access to the truth of the real world, and instead believed that truth could be evaluated based on its consequences (Weaver and Olson, 2006). The pragmatic paradigm is particularly beneficial for directing research design when combining different approaches is philosophically contradictory (Salkind, 2010).

The pragmatic approach allows researchers to find solutions to real-world problems in innovative and dynamic ways (Morgan, 2014). By focusing on “what works” rather than absolute truth or reality, researchers can explore complex phenomena and address problems that may not have clear-cut solutions (Weaver and Olson, 2006). This approach is particularly relevant to the staffing problems in the UK spa industry, which requires a tailored approach to find effective solutions which is to identify and develop a commercially available

model for employee engagement within the spa industry. The spa industry in the United Kingdom is a prime example of a dynamic and constantly evolving industry where staffing issues can arise due to various factors such as employee shortages, high turnover rates, and the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. The findings of the study can be used to develop policy recommendations, new environmental initiatives, or social change (Salkind, 2010).

A pragmatic approach that values diverse perspectives and recognizes that knowledge is socially constructed is well-suited for this study (Morgan, 2014). In this study, the researcher aims to gain a deep understanding of the staffing problems in the UK spa industry and provide practical solutions to overcome them. Thus, it is well-suited for investigating complex phenomena and exploring the subjective experiences of individuals, such as spa employees and employers. The study will be conducted using an exploratory research design methodology, which allows for a flexible approach to data collection and analysis (Salkind, 2010).

Pragmatic research paradigm provides a suitable framework for the researcher to tailor various research approaches, both qualitative and quantitative, to gain a deep understanding of staffing problems in the UK spa industry and provide practical solutions (Salkind, 2010). Qualitative research is well-suited for investigating complex phenomena and exploring the subjective experiences of individuals, such as spa employees and leaders. The theoretical frameworks that guide the study, such as employee engagement (Kahn, 1990), employer branding (Ibrahim et al., 2018), employer attractiveness (Ronda, 2018), and emotional labour (Hochschild, 2012), are well-suited for a qualitative investigation of staffing problems in the spa industry. These frameworks provide a theoretical basis for understanding the factors that influence employee engagement and retention, can help guide the development of a commercially available model for employee engagement within the industry. The researcher will use a documentary review methodology to collect a range of secondary data, including grey literature, to provide a broad perspective on the challenges facing the UK spa industry. This exploratory qualitative research design allows for a flexible

and iterative approach to data collection and analysis. By using existing documents and data, the researcher can obtain a broad range of perspectives and experiences without the need for direct engagement with research subjects. This approach also allows for a more cost-effective and efficient research process (Salkind, 2010).

Critics of qualitative research often argue that its findings lack generalizability and are too subjective (Maarouf, 2019). However, a pragmatic approach to qualitative research recognizes that the goal is not necessarily to generalize findings to a larger population, but rather to gain a deep understanding of a particular phenomenon and provide practical solutions (Morgan, 2014). The subjective nature of qualitative research is also recognized, but this is seen as an advantage rather than a limitation, as it allows for a deeper understanding of complex factors contributing to staffing problems in the industry (Maarouf, 2019). Overall, a pragmatic approach to qualitative research is crucial in achieving the study's objectives of gaining a deep understanding of staffing problems in the UK spa industry and developing practical solutions to overcome them.

Deductive, inductive and abductive are the three types of research approaches that can be used (Saunders et al., 2019). The deductive method verifies an established theory (Collis and Hussey, 2013). Saunders et al. (2019) also support the claim which implies a top-down method in which the study question is distilled into a series of hypotheses to investigate. Deductive reasoning generates no new hypotheses and is regarded as a positivist philosophy (Goswami, 2011). The deductive method is predicated on existing theories and hypotheses and uses them as a starting point (Goswami, 2011). The deductive approach focuses on universal rules of cause and effect, typically given inside an explanatory framework. It presupposes and supports the notion that the world is composed of objectively defined and explicable facts (Ali and Birley, 1999; Ormerod, 2010). When a researcher uses the deductive technique, he or she begins with a collection of theoretical viewpoints that comprise the hypothesis. The conclusions generated from deductive research are comprehensive and explicit statements that address whether the hypotheses formed from

theory are true and correct. This type of research develops a theory and focuses exclusively on a hypothesised link between variables. This precludes the researcher from developing other unforeseen elements that may exist but have not been found yet (Wengraf, 2001).

On the other hand, induction is a bottom-up approach. the inductive technique is not entirely founded on pre-existing theory, in contrast to the deductive approach (Kovács and Spens, 2005). Inductive reasoning is a method for generating new theories (Hodkinson, 2008).

Typically, researchers employing an inductive methodology seek out phenomena that have either never been investigated or have been researched in a restricted capacity. The objective of inductive research is to develop a theory about a subject that has received little attention or examine the phenomenon under study from a fresh perspective to identify and explore novel variables or factors (Goldkuhl, 2012; Mingers et al., 2012). When an inductive approach is used, no hypotheses are formed, and the researcher does not use pre-determined variables to look for and comprehend a particular event under study. Rather, the researcher attempts to comprehend the rationale behind specific areas in need of development through in-depth interviews with study participants or other strategies. As a result, in contrast to deductive approaches, inductive approaches emphasise qualitative tools for doing research, whereas deductive approaches emphasise quantitative procedures.

The abductive approach is a hybrid of both deductive and inductive approaches. This method employs creativity and intuition to arrive at a novel theory. Abduction is the analysis and evaluation of existing phenomena, followed by a fresh viewpoint on them (Kovács and Spens, 2005). As a result, abductive theory, in contrast to inductive theory, accepts current theoretical findings from the literature and argues that these findings can aid in the analysis of new ones (Andreewsky and Bourcier, 2000). Abductive reasoning differs significantly from inductive reasoning since it is subject to change based on empirical research findings and unexpected outcomes obtained not only from that research but also from theory as it develops during the process.

Given the research question, in addition to testing an existing theory, the objective of the study is to develop a new one. Therefore, this study uses abductive approaches. The researcher has a well-defined theoretical framework and research questions to help lead the investigation. On the contrary, this study is more concerned with eliciting the sentiments and experiences of spa staff rather than just relying on a theoretical framework. Here, Khan's (1990) employee engagement theory, Bethron's (2005) and Turner's (2020) employee branding theories, and Hochschild's (2012) emotional labour theory are evaluated. Different views and perceptions of different individuals, including spa employees, employers and customers are explored to answer the proposed research question where this study can result in a novel idea and theory that subsequent researchers can test and expand upon. The abductive strategy is used in this research, incorporating qualitative data collection and analysis using exploratory methodology, as all data is retrieved from secondary sources (Saunders et al., 2019).

3.2 Research design

Here, research design process is discussed, in which the research question is transformed into a specific topic of study by the researcher. Quantitative, qualitative or mixed-methods research can be influenced by a researcher's philosophical viewpoint, study strategy and methodology (Creswell, 2009). According to Saunders et al. (2019), the research philosophy and research approach will affect how the researcher chooses to answer the critical questions. It is critical to understand that a research design must be not only rational but also cohesive to ensure that the study's findings are relevant to the research question at hand. The research questions will then guide the study strategy, data collection method, analysis and the research project's timeline. The researcher's research design is a general plan for attempting to answer the study questions. The study's objectives are included in the research design, as are the sources from which the researcher wants to collect data.

The first methodological choice is to use a quantitative, qualitative or mixed design. The distinction between numerical and non-numerical data can help researchers tell apart

quantitative from qualitative study. It is common to use the term 'quantitative' to describe any data collection or analysis technique that produces or uses numerical data. An alternative to quantitative methods is qualitative methods, which rely on non-numerical sources of data, such as written or visual data.

If data gathering methods are well planned and organised, quantitative research tends to be connected with the positivist philosophy often featuring a deductive approach to test a theory (Saunders et al., 2019). The inductive method may also be used when data are used to form theories. Statistical and graphical tools are used in quantitative research to analyse the correlations between numerically measured variables. In an experimental design, it is common to include controls to assure the validity of the data in the same manner (Saunders et al., 2019). Data are collected consistently; thus, questions must be phrased so that all participants understand them. Questionnaires or structured interviews are the quantitative data collection method.

On the other hand, qualitative research examines participants' meanings and interactions through various data gathering and analysis approaches to produce a conceptual framework and theoretical contribution frequently coupled with an interpretive philosophy (Denzin and Lincoln, 2011; Saunders et al., 2019). In this form of study, researchers must make sense of the subjective and socially created interpretations offered about the issue or topic they are investigating (Saunders et al., 2019). This type of research is sometimes referred to as 'naturalistic' since it necessitates the participation of researchers in a real-world situation in order for them to have a deeper understanding of the subject matter. Using a naturalistic and emergent research design, the researcher can make new theories or improve an existing one. However, a deductive approach is used in some qualitative research strategies to evaluate an established theory using qualitative methods (Yin, 2015). Another research design initially proposed for this study and discarded later is a mixed method which is the combination of using both quantitative and qualitative methods in a single research study.

In most cases, exploratory, descriptive, explanatory or evaluative research is the type of research that the researcher will do when they are trying to answer a research question where the goal of the research may change over time (Saunders et al., 2019). The exploratory research design is employed to conduct this study. According to Denzin and Lincoln (2011), exploratory research is typically used to study a research problem that lacks preliminary data from previous studies conducted by other researchers on the subject or when just a few studies existed that might be used as references. An exploratory study is an effective method for posing open enquiries to ascertain what is occurring and obtain insight into a subject of attention. The exploratory research design was chosen because it effectively conducted an in-depth analysis of the research topic, exploring the employee engagement issue within the spa industry in the United Kingdom, due to its information-rich and unstructured nature that examined the theoretical idea of a research problem. For the experimental research design, the primary purpose is to clarify the precise nature of the research problem to be resolved.

3.3 Methodological constraints

Due to a series of countrywide lockdowns put in place in response to the outbreak of Covid-19, primary research could not be conducted during this study. Due to the study's constrained timeframe, budget and word count, secondary research was conducted in areas where primary data collection on the views, opinions and perceptions of spa sector employees, managers and owners was impossible.

Access to participants, as stated by Shenton and Hayter (2004), entails obtaining admission into businesses and making sure that the researcher has the opportunity and access to extract information or data from the participants. They believe that this is a widespread problem. Due to lockdown and social distancing restrictions, this research was constrained by access, notably the impossibility of doing primary research at the chosen spa business. As a result, it was not possible to conduct in-depth interviews with participants to elicit detailed information about the study issue. Online surveys and interviews would have been

feasible, but spa personnel and employers were under extreme time constraints, making access to participants similarly impossible.

After the initial lockdown, spa businesses in the United Kingdom were permitted to reopen in July 2020. Spas were under tremendous pressure following lockdown due to staff shortages, fear of getting a virus and illness-related absences. However, other participants refused to participate in the crisis because they were working overtime and felt it was not the right time for a face-to-face or even online interview. The researcher hoped to perform primary research following the first lockdown, but the government announced more restrictions and a second countrywide lockdown in September 2020. As a result, a documentary review was decided upon. As a result, the sorts of data that could be collected were limited, making it impossible to make sense of any anomalies discovered throughout the analysis of the chosen papers. Finally, the researcher could not employ additional researchers and had to rely on secondary sources from grey literature to close the study gap. Due to the time constraints imposed by the lockdowns, it was clear from reviewing methodological sources that a documentary review (Saunders et al., 2019) would have to be employed in conjunction with the systematic study of grey literature, as Brewis et al. (2017) did.

3.4 Data sources and data collection methods

There are two types of data: primary and secondary (Saunders et al., 2019). Primary data is first-hand data which has been acquired by the researcher directly from primary sources. Data that has previously been derived from primary sources and made available to other researchers for their own investigations is referred to as secondary data (Saunders et al., 2019). Due to the Covid-19 pandemic and national lockdowns, access to primary data has been restricted, and this study thus relies on secondary data. Secondary data may be quantitative or qualitative (Saunders et al., 2019), where the researcher relies solely on secondary qualitative data. Collecting and storing data is a constant process that requires considerable time and effort, but most organisations require it to sustain their operations (Saunders et al., 2019). Newspapers, journals, articles and books are all forms of secondary

data. It would have been helpful to conduct a questionnaire survey and interviews of spa employees and employers to gain more insight into how it feels to work in the spa industry and the managers' challenges in managing employee engagement in the UK spa industry. Since access to primary data was not realistic, secondary data research was adopted.

The current study collected data from various documentary sources and analysed it to form relevant research topic findings. The study included a search approach that enabled the researcher to find and select relevant secondary data sources, including published materials on the research issue, such as journals, articles, government reports and scholarly sources. The next stage in developing the search strategy was determining which databases held these secondary sources.

Data on billions of daily queries is gathered by search engines like Google. Similarly, social networking platforms like Facebook maintain web pages for specialised interest groups, including those founded by organisations, and preserve them with the postings and photos of other group members. Secondary data for this study is gathered from various documents maintained in an online library. Numerous newspaper articles are critical tools for understanding current changes and effects in the United Kingdom. Additionally, several case studies, survey results and government data sources are necessary to investigate how employee engagement might help alleviate the spa industry's employment challenges in the United Kingdom. Grey literature and archival records are also excellent sources of secondary data.

Establishing the definition of grey literature is necessary. Historically, grey literature was known as 'fugitive literature' due to its elusiveness and retrieval difficulty (Pelzer and Wiese, 2003). Although the relevance of grey literature is essential, there are disadvantages to consider. Rothstein and Hopewell (2009) argue that non-written materials such as podcasts or video clips are important secondary data which are difficult to retrieve. However, a new era is upon us based on the expansion of institutional Google search engine, Facebook pages, online blogs and wikis, as well as the introduction of Slideshare presentations

(Soldani et al., 2018). A key disadvantage is that these are not peer-reviewed and not indexed in major bibliographic repositories. However, grey literature does not have to match the standards of peer-reviewed publications, which is an important distinction (Rothstein and Hopewell, 2009). Grey literature, despite its lack of academic rigour, is often authored by specialists in the subject matter. This also makes grey literature mining a good idea because it deals with information that has been around for a while because of the lengthy lag between research and publication. The researcher needs to use traditional evaluation methods to make sure the information he or she gets from grey literature is accurate and valid.

Researchers need to learn how to judge the quality and credibility of a website in the same way that they judge a scholarly article. It is essential to examine the author's background, institutional affiliation, research methodologies, data collection techniques, hypothesis testing, data collection, statement of findings and source in order to determine the trustworthiness and correctness of the information presented (Pappas and Williams, 2011).

According to Stokes and Wall (2017), reputable sources result in high-quality findings. Therefore, government websites, Spa Association UK websites, newspaper articles, and economists are identified as reliable sources for collecting secondary data. Government survey data and reports are readily available in aggregated form for download on the internet, as governments permit free access to the data they gather. Similarly, Spa Association UK, Professional Beauty and Massage Warehouse are independent bodies comprised of members and partners from the spa, beauty, salon and wellness industries in the United Kingdom that publish essential reports, articles and blogs that are widely accessible online. Also, various organisations such as *The Economist*, *The Guardian*, the BBC and the *Financial Times* are essential secondary data collection sources.

In order to narrow the scope of a search, Peters et al. (2020) suggest employing Boolean operations like AND, OR and NOT to refine the search strategy. There are two types of search operators: AND and OR. The operator AND is used to identify articles covering two or more study topics, while the operator OR is used to determine either of two research

concepts. Because of the technique of employing Boolean operators, terms like ‘spa industry’ and ‘employment issue’ can be generated, as well as phrases such as ‘spa industry’ and ‘employee turnover’, which aids the researcher in focusing their search on the most pertinent documents for the investigation.

Conducting the search strategy included constructing detailed eligibility criteria that defined the sources included in the study and those excluded and defining the methodological model (Brewis et al., 2017). Table 2 shows the strict inclusion and exclusion criteria that helped to narrow down the results to the most relevant documents to answer the research question.

Table 2: Inclusion and exclusion criteria adopted from Brewis et al. (2017)

Criteria	
As a whole or at the very least in the title, keywords, or abstract of the work, when predetermined keywords are present	Inclusion
Documents written in English	Inclusion
Documents that show evidence on staffing problems related to spa and beauty salon	Inclusion
When the documents address at least one employee motivation, engagement, attraction and retention indicator	inclusion
Documents published after 2019	inclusion
In the search results, documents that are identical to each other	Exclusion
Documents that are not accessible	Exclusion
Non-English documents	Exclusion
Documents published before 2019	Exclusion
Documents that require purchase to access	Exclusion

Documents that are not in a public domain	Exclusion
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Secondary qualitative data was gathered mostly from published sources in libraries and the internet using desk-based research methods. According to Berends (2006), a desk-based research approach focuses on studying and examining relevant secondary materials from a desk rather than moving around, where the researcher collects and reviews published information from the internet and libraries. Accordingly, a desk-based study can save time and money because data can be easily accessed online after devising an effective search strategy. Using the desk-based approach, the search strategy section outlines how to find suitable secondary sources to draw on during the research process. The documentary review also aids in assessing the effects of Covid-19 on the spa industry and employment in the United Kingdom. A significant drawback of using documentary reviews is that the researcher does not have control over the quality of data and therefore assumes that the writers of selected publications followed ethical norms and the proper process in acquiring the data (Saunders et al., 2019).

3.5 Document analysis

As mentioned previously, the study used qualitative data gathered from online sources, in which the researcher analysed public materials containing pertinent information about the research problem. According to Aspers and Corte (2019), a documentary evaluation of secondary sources enables researchers to comprehend the theoretical underpinnings of the study problem based on the results of other scholars. The documentary review was chosen due to the Covid-19 pandemic and social distancing procedures, which restricted face-to-face connection with participants. It was deemed acceptable for this study since it allowed for comparing multiple writers' views on staffing concerns and challenges in the UK spa business, ensuring that complete data was collected and correct conclusions were drawn on the subject.

Document analysis is a process for researching and assessing documents in a methodical manner. Document analysis, like other qualitative research methods, demands the examination and interpretation of data in order to obtain understanding and factual information (Corbin and Strauss, 2008; Rapley and Silverman, 2011). The researcher was not involved in the creation of these documents, which include both written and photographic content. Documents are referred to as 'social facts' by Bowen (2009) because they are generated, traded and used in a social context. There are numerous types of documents that may be used for documentary review as part of a study. As mentioned earlier, newspapers, journals, articles and books are all forms of secondary data. Books and brochures, diaries, journals, event programmes, printed outlines, letters to the editor and memos to the editor, maps, charts, press releases, programme proposals, application forms, radio and TV show scripts, organisational or institutional reports, survey data from organisations or institutions are all secondary data that comes from other sources, like public records (Soldani et al. 2018).

Thematic analysis is performed in this documentary review because this study required the collection of qualitative data. Thematic analysis is a sort of data pattern identification in which emerging themes are used as the categories for the study of the data (Fereday and Muir-Cochrane, 2006; King, 2014). The data must be re-read and re-examined with greater attention to detail. Accordingly, the reviewer conducts coding and categorisation of the selected data to identify relevant themes in the context of a phenomenon. An alternative to using predefined codes is to use them as a complement to other research approaches. It is possible to use interview transcript codes to analyse the content of documents, for example. Through codes and the themes developed by the researcher, diverse information is brought together. Using thematic analysis, the researcher can conduct an in-depth examination of the qualitative data set based on emerging themes related to employee engagement issues and challenges in the spa industry in the United Kingdom.

Thematic analysis is an efficient method for analysing qualitative data. It gives a flexible and systematic means to understand, analyse and draw meaningful conclusions from the concepts and theories revealed in each data set (Fereday and Muir-Cochrane, 2006). After an examination, King's (2014) template is considered a good match for the current study. Template analysis, according to King (2014) is more adaptable than the alternatives since it requires fewer steps and can thus be customised to fit the needs of any project. There are numerous reasons for this, the most important of which is that it provides a flexible template for addressing the historical themes of employee engagement (Kahn, 1990), employer branding (Bethron, 2005) and emotional labour (2012) in regards to issues of employee attraction, engagement and retention in the spa industry in the United Kingdom. Additionally, it was thought that the template's flexibility would allow for discovering new themes. The use of grey literature as documentary review allows for the scrutiny and emergence of themes that the historical literature review could not have captured given the lag on publication post-pandemic and within the industry.

According to King (2014), template analysis can be used to identify themes. King's (2014) template analysis is a type of qualitative data theme analysis that may be used for any kind of textual data, usually in the form of interview transcripts but, in this case, in the form of text documents. An emphasis is placed on categorised coding, which uses broad themes to cover progressively smaller areas. It is common for analysis to begin with a priori codes, which in this case were derived from the literature review's conceptual framework. King (2014) suggests that these codes may be updated or discarded if they were not helpful or appropriate and revised. The researcher began by looking through the data for segments that seemed pertinent to the investigation. This research set out to find a solution to staffing problems in the UK spa industry. The researcher specifies the three key issues regarding employee engagement (Kahn, 1990) in the UK spa industry: employer branding and attractiveness (Bethron, 2005; Alnaçk et al., 2014), emotional labour (Hochschild, 2012), and outcomes of emotional labour. The literature review informed these three topics. Therefore, it

seems reasonable to suggest they provided a starting point to use those topics as the a priori themes when analysing employee engagement in the UK spa industry. After collecting relevant documents, the researcher can read through and apply the coding method.

All the texts can be copied and pasted into Microsoft Word, and codes are assigned to relevant text and data using the comments function. From this process a researcher can generate new themes which can be added to the initial template. After coding all documents and generating themes from both the literature review and the documentary review, the final template provides the structure for writing up the results and findings of the study (King, 2014).

3.6 Scoping study

A scoping study is a pre-project assessment used to define the size and scope of a project (Levac et al., 2010). It is very important to figure out what the main idea of a research field is and where and how the researchers get the data they need. Thematic analysis of the text is used in this study to explore staffing problems in the UK spa industry in order to identify and develop a commercially available model for employee engagement within the industry and to investigate how employee involvement has changed in the spa industry in the United Kingdom since the Covid-19 outbreak. To understand how employee engagement can be used to tackle staffing challenges in the UK spa industry, it is critical to understand the impact of Covid-19 on the spa sector. Grey literature is unpublished or unreleased content that has been published informally or for non-commercial purposes. Grey literature includes government reports, data, patents, conference papers and even non-written resources such as posters and infographics (Rothstein et al., 2009).

This phase involved developing a search strategy and executing the search. The search strategy aids in defining appropriate search terms and identifying relevant databases for the collection of pertinent documentation. The number of databases available for document searches can be specified and limited, although the issue area's nature heavily influences

the number of databases available. This search aims to identify and collect numerous documents that aid in investigating staffing issues in the spa business in the United Kingdom. The primary search engine used in this study is Google.

Before searching for documents, a scoping search should be done to make sure the search terms are specific enough to cover the study's goals. As a result, a pilot search is conducted prior to deciding on which search engine to use and narrow down the search terms. During a test search, the number of results from Google's databases was large, which suggests that there are a lot of relevant articles. Expanded time periods and broader search phrases, as well as the fact that each database result was also autonomous, made this possible. Also the objective of the research is also to explore the impact of Covid-19 on UK spa employment, so only documents published between 2019 and 2021 were searched. The search was undertaken using several keywords, such as 'the impact of covid19 on spa/effect on spa staff/issues in the spa sector', to obtain relevant information from various publications.

Furthermore, the UK spa industry has not gained enough popularity with the government or the public. Therefore there are limited quality data available online. Additionally, spas in the UK are often viewed and studied as part of the beauty industry. Beauty salons and spas are inextricably linked, as both are classified as part of the wellness industry. Both spas and beauty salons do comparable tasks and have been equally affected by the Covid-19 pandemic. As a result, all data or documents on the beauty salon business are examined for documentary review. Additionally, the researcher discovered confidential documents that would be useful for the research topic but required payment to access. The researcher did not acquire financing for this study, and it would be pretty costly to do research. Therefore, the researcher adopted inclusion and exclusion criteria presented earlier in Table 2 to narrow the search.

The following table shows the different documents categorised into five groups: website materials, newspaper articles, corporate reports, government reports, and blogs. However,

the number of documents used in the final analysis will be determined by the search criteria used by the researcher and the goals of the research. By applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria, papers that fulfilled the inclusion criteria were selected for further investigation and content assessments. Table 2 above lists the predetermined criteria for document inclusion and exclusion in order to complete this documentary review. The following table is the list of documents including grey literature sources that have been identified for template analysis using inclusion and exclusion criteria mentioned in above Table 2.

Table 3: Identified documents for documentary review

Dates	Sources	Document
	Website materials	
01/06/2020	(Spa-uk.org, 2020)	Covid-19 re-opening guidelines resources
14/01/2021	(Eve Oxberry, 2021)	Beauty, hair and spa achieve Government representation under new Personal Care sector
01/04/2021	(Spa Industry Association, 2021)	Why Employee Welfare Should Be Your No. 1 Priority In 2021
25/07/2021	(Davidson, 2021)	Employees Refusing to Return to Work Due to COVID
01/08/2021	(Whitby, 2021)	Pandemic's impact on US spa industry highlighted in ISPA's 2021 Industry Study
02/12/2021	(Professionalbeauty.co.uk. 2021)	Coronavirus (Covid-19): support guide for beauty salons, spas and self-employed therapists
07/12/2021	(Page and McCann, 2021)	Emotional styling: How can hairdressers help?
	Newspaper and articles	

15/04/2020	(Dean, 2020)	Covid-19 and 100 days that transformed the world: the 17 April edition of <i>The Guardian Weekly</i>
30/05/2020	(Kearney, 2020)	Coronavirus 30 May: at a glance
01/09/2020	(<i>The Economist</i> , 2020)	Covid-19 has forced a radical shift in working habits
23/09/2020	(<i>Independent</i> , 2020)	Coronavirus: Timeline of key events since UK was put into lockdown six months ago
14/12/2020	(Safi, 2020)	Covid Timeline
29/12/2020	(<i>Telegraph</i> , 2020)	Britain reports record number of daily cases
14/01/2021	(Eve Oxberry, 2021)	Beauty, hair and spa achieve Government representation under new Personal Care sector
08/04/2021	(<i>The Economist</i> , 2021)	The rise of working from home: The shift to a hybrid world of work will have a big impact on managers
08/04/2021	(Callaghan, 2021)	Feeling good: The future of the \$1.5 trillion wellness market
01/07/2021	(Kate Morgan, 2021)	The great resignation: How employers drove workers to quit
21/07/2021	(Volini et al. ,2021)	The worker-employer relationship disrupted
01/08/2021	(Williams, 2021)	Reimagining Work: Insights from Deloitte's 2021 Global Human Capital Trends Report
20/08/2021	(<i>The Economist</i> , 2021)	So far, ending pandemic unemployment aid has not yielded extra jobs
27/08/2021	(Christian, 2021)	The great resignation is here, and no one is prepared
08/09/2021	(de Smet et al., 2021)	'Great Attrition' or 'Great Attraction'? The choice is yours
01/11/2021	(Brignall, 2021)	'The great resignation': almost one in four UK workers planning job change

	Corporate reports	
01/04/2020	(McGroarty et al., 2021)	Global Wellness Trends 2020
28/05/2020	(Professional Beauty, 2020)	74% of UK beauty salons and spas are ready to reopen by July 4
01/06/2020	(Grzesk, 2020)	What's Next For Wellness
01/06/2020	(Murphy, 2020)	CV-19 Spa Report: June 2020
11/02/2021	(Leckie et al., 2021)	The effects of the pandemic on the hair and beauty sector report
	Government Reports	
24/11/2020	(Ons.gov.uk. 2021)	Hairdressing and beauty by district
14/01/2022	(Gov.uk. 2022)	Working safely during coronavirus (COVID-19)
21/06/2021	(House of Commons Library, 2021)	Beauty and Wellbeing Sector workforce
	Blogs	
14/01/2020	(Jenkins, 2020)	Is the life of a massage therapist's career really only 8 years?
15/01/2020	(Seago, 2020)	The recruitment crisis
16/02/2020	(Downton, 2020)	the challenges of spa recruitment
02/07/2021	(Jenkins, 2021)	How to handle a challenging massage client? Ask the Muscle Whisperer Series
30/09/2020	(Jenkins, 2020)	What was the biggest lesson you learnt as a business owner during Covid-19?
13/08/2021	(Young, 2021)	Why do we have a problem displaying honesty and

		vulnerability?
20/09/2021	(Young, 2021)	Where have all the therapists gone? A high turnover industry
03/12/2021	(Appointfix, 2021)	9 Ways to Motivate Your Salon Staff and Grow Your Business

The above table shows the various sources identified for this study. Sources are grouped into five different categories: website materials, blogs, government reports, magazine articles and corporate reports. For the purpose of additional enquiry and documentation, papers that met the inclusion requirements were selected based on the inclusion criteria.

3.7 Validity and reliability

Validity and reliability are used to assess the quality of research. Hong et al. (2019) recommend that researchers need to pay close attention to validity and reliability to obtain precise findings that accurately reflect the work's quality. The phrase 'data validity' refers to the appropriateness of the data collection procedure, the analytical methodologies employed and the methodology. The methodology used must be appropriate for the type of research being conducted. The research question must align with the study objectives to yield the desired outcome. To be a valid study, the research design should be consistent with the methodology, with the suggested technique capable of producing guidelines for answering the intended research question (Saunders et al., 2019).

Reliability relates to the extent to which the researcher can rely on the data source and, consequently, the data itself. A reliable source of information is one that can be relied on to provide accurate information that is backed up by solid evidence. Consistency is the most important indicator of reliability. Thus, in literary accounts, the source's reputation is crucial. The data collected should be dependable and consistent, providing the same information each time. The researcher must ensure that the data has been acquired from a reputable

source and that the analysis or interpretation offered has the identical information available in the source (Saunders et al., 2016).

The validity of this study will be maintained by collecting data only on the spa industry and employment in the United Kingdom. Meanwhile, research reliability refers to the consistency with which data are collected, suggesting that other researchers can obtain comparable data if they follow the established approach (Saunders et al., 2019). To ensure the research's reliability, data sources will be acknowledged appropriately, and references will be provided to allow readers to verify the data used in the analysis.

3.8 Ethical considerations

Ethics in research is essential in protecting the dignity, rights and welfare of research participants, ensuring scientific integrity and maintaining public trust in research (Irwin, 2013). Everyone has different morals and values. It can be determined that these are born from culture, tradition and everyday life experiences. When carrying out research, the researcher must carry it out with honesty and integrity (Legge, 1998). Certain ethical principles are the primary concern when carrying out a piece of research, most of which relate to primary research. The researcher conducted documentary reviews from secondary data. There was no need for ethical approval before conducting this exploratory investigation because the documentary evaluation used secondary data sources that were already in the public domain. However, secondary data analysis has its own set of ethical challenges that require careful consideration.

One of the key ethical considerations in research is informed consent, which means that research participants must be fully informed about the nature and purpose of the research, the risks and benefits, and their rights before agreeing to participate (Tripathy, 2013). In secondary data analysis, the original research may have obtained consent from participants for specific purposes that may be different from the current research project. Thus, the researcher must ensure that the use of secondary data does not breach the original consent

given by the participants. If the original data contains identifiable information, the researcher must seek ethical approval to obtain permission to use the data for the new research purpose. Privacy and confidentiality are important ethical considerations in research, especially when dealing with sensitive data or information (Tripathy, 2013). In secondary data analysis, the researcher must ensure that the data sources are not disclosed or used inappropriately, and that the data are de-identified or anonymised to protect the privacy and confidentiality of the participants (Tripathy, 2013). However, some secondary data may contain identifying information that cannot be de-identified, such as small-area data or linked data, which raises ethical issues about the protection of the participants' privacy and confidentiality. In such cases, the researcher must seek ethical approval and take appropriate measures to protect the participants' privacy and confidentiality, such as restricting access to the data or using secure data storage and sharing methods.

Data ownership and acknowledgment are important ethical considerations in research, especially in secondary data analysis. The researcher therefore ensures that the data sources are acknowledged and properly cited to give credit to the original researchers and data collectors. If the data is not freely available, the researcher must obtain explicit, written permission from the data owner or original research team before using the data for the new research purpose (Abell et al., 2008). Data ownership and acknowledgment also apply to any copyrighted or proprietary data, such as software or online data repositories, that the researcher may use in the research project. However, the researcher is only using de-identified data which is freely available online for general public which eliminates the issues of informed consent, privacy and confidentiality. Grey literature, although it may encompass conventional secondary research methods, was restricted to the public domain by the researcher.

Data quality and reliability are important ethical considerations in research, especially in secondary data analysis, where the researcher has limited control over the data collection and measurement processes. The researcher must ensure that the data used in the

research project are accurate, reliable and relevant to the research questions (Savage, 2019). The researcher should also evaluate the methodology, sampling design, data collection instruments and data quality indicators of the original research to ensure that the data are fit for the new research purpose. In addition, the researcher ensures removal of any biases, errors or omissions in the original data, and takes appropriate measures to address or minimise their impact on the new research findings.

Plagiarism, researcher self-reporting and inaccuracies in research findings presentation are further key ethical concerns with secondary data use (Saunders et al., 2019). It was suggested by Awasthi (2019) that researchers should not present content taken from secondary sources as their own, as this would be academic misconduct known as plagiarism. In order to avoid accusations of plagiarism, the researcher ensures that all sources cited in their work are appropriately credited. Abell et al. (2008) further argued that self-reporting raises ethical concerns because researchers offer their prepared interpretations of the research findings rather than documenting the exact facts from secondary sources. Therefore all the facts and findings from the documentary review will be cited appropriately so that the reader can quickly identify the manipulation of data.

3.9 Summary

The methodology of a research study is critical to ensure that the research design and methods of data collection and analysis align with the research question and objectives. Research philosophy, including ontology, epistemology and methodology, must be considered to determine the philosophical position of the study. The five different philosophical approaches to research are positivism, critical realism, interpretivism, postmodernism and pragmatism, and the chosen approach depends on the nature of the research question and the goals of the study (Saunders et al., 2019).

This chapter provides a detailed overview of the research methodology used in a DBA thesis. The study identified pragmatism as the most relevant approach for the research

question, as it can combine several research methods and stakeholder perspectives. The study also adopted an abductive approach, focusing on qualitative data collection and exploratory methodology to develop solutions for employee engagement in the spa industry in the UK.

Due to Covid-19 lockdowns, primary research was not possible, and the study had to rely on secondary research. Access to participants was limited, and online surveys and interviews were not feasible. Spa businesses faced staff shortages and illness-related absences after the lockdown periods. Therefore, the study used a documentary review and systematic study of grey literature to collect data.

The study used qualitative data gathered from online sources, which was analysed using thematic analysis. Thematic analysis is used to identify emerging themes related to employee engagement issues and challenges in the spa industry in the United Kingdom. King's (2014) template analysis is employed to identify these themes, with a priori codes derived from the literature review's conceptual framework. The final template will provide the structure for writing the results and findings of the study.

The section also discusses the importance of validity and reliability in research, as well as ethical considerations that need to be taken into account when conducting a study. The researcher ensured the accuracy and consistency of the data and conducted the research with honesty and integrity. Ethical considerations include informed consent, privacy and confidentiality, data ownership and acknowledgment, data quality and reliability, plagiarism and self-reporting. The researcher used de-identified data that is freely available online which eliminates the issues of informed consent, privacy and confidentiality, and all sources cited in their work were appropriately credited to avoid plagiarism. The findings were presented accurately, ensuring the validity and reliability of the study.

4 Chapter 4: Results of documentary review and thematic analysis

4.1 Introduction

This chapter presents findings and analysis of the research. The study aims to investigate staffing problems in the UK spa industry context. In order to find how to engage, attract and retain employees in the UK spa industry, it is essential to understand the key issues underpinning the spa issue. Therefore, the researcher looked to the current literature knowledge on employee branding, employee attractiveness and emotional labour in the UK spa industry. This presented the emerging research gap of the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic upon the sector and further clarified the limitation of HR theorising on the issues and challenges for employee branding and attractiveness due to the global pandemic. This not only limited the nature of this enquiry in terms of primary research but opened new lines of thinking in terms of new contributions to understanding the business issues of branding and attractiveness, and emotional labour.

The researcher conducted a documentary review incorporating 39 documents. These were identified as the top 39 documents using inclusion and exclusion criteria generated in Chapter 3. The grey literature selected for the study was included after examining the current literature from the literature review and following the methodological design following the prior systematic enquiry of Brewis et al. (2017) to verify the data validity. These documents were carefully identified by considering inclusion and exclusion criteria as presented earlier in Table 2.

There has been a series of lockdowns and there have been many changes in government policies and social lifestyles since the outbreak of Covid-19 in late 2019. It was a difficult time for managers, employees and consumers where robust management practice and intense emotional labour (Hochschild, 2012) was needed. Therefore, the researcher decided to include documents published after January 2020 and present to analyse how emotional labour is performed in the spa industry. A total of 39 documents have been identified after January 2020 to find and analyse the impact upon employee engagement, employer

branding and attractiveness of the UK spa industry. Here (Ons.gov.uk., 2021; Professionalbeauty.co.uk, 2021; and House of Commons Library, 2021) documents related to the beauty industry are also included because the spa and beauty workforce share a similar working environment and similar emotional labour. Also, the report by IBISWorld (2021), 'Health and Wellness Spas in the UK – Market Research Report', is rejected due to high cost as the researcher did not receive any funding and UWS library did not have any access to the required databases.

The study aims to investigate staffing problems in the UK spa industry to identify and develop a commercially available model for employee engagement within the industry. The objectives associated with the aim are:

1. To determine the key factors and importance of employee motivation, engagement and retention in the spa industry with a focus on the period of Covid-19
2. To identify the most commonly used employee motivation, engagement and retention strategies within the UK spa business in terms of the impacts of Covid-19
3. To explore the challenges faced by management in employee motivation, engagement and retention strategies during and after the Covid-19 lockdown periods
4. To investigate how to develop future employment attractiveness in the UK spa industry by using employee motivation, engagement and retention strategies.

The study intends to investigate staffing problems in the UK spa industry to identify and develop a commercially available model for employee engagement. Researchers expect to find the people management issues underpinning the spa industry and the key factors and importance of employee motivation, engagement and retention in the spa industry.

Secondly, currently used engagement of the workforce in the spa industry is explored.

Thirdly, challenges that management faces in employee motivation, engagement and retention strategies are identified. Finally, the research intends to identify what might be a commercially available model for employee engagement within the spa industry.

The search database for this study is mainly Google search engine. Initially, IBISWorld (2021) and Grand View Research (2021) were thought to be essential databases to search for documents. Various reports and articles from these databases could have been helpful in understanding the importance, challenges and possible solutions to staffing issues faced by the UK spa industry. However, these databases require a subscription to access their content. Since there was no funding for the research and the University of the West of Scotland (UWS) library does not have access to these databases, they were rejected. The number of results from Google's databases was large, which suggests that there are a lot of relevant articles. Expanded time periods and broader search phrases, as well as the fact that each database result was also autonomous, made this possible. Also, as the objective of the research is also to explore the impacts of Covid-19 on UK spa employment, only documents published between 2019 and 2021 were searched. Any documents published in beauty salons and spas are closely related as both are categorised as a well-being industry. There were limited documents found online regarding the spa industry in the UK. Both spas and beauty salons have similar work nature and have been affected similarly by the Covid-19 pandemic. Therefore any information or documents regarding the beauty salon industry were considered for documentary review. Also, many reports are required for purchase to access, which can be very expensive for research, and are rejected. Because of their length and the limited time available, books, dissertations and theses in human resources management were omitted from consideration, which was also noted by Brewis et al. (2017). The search uses different keywords, such as 'effect of covid19 on spa/ effect on spa staff/ issues of spa sector', to collect relevant information from different publications.

4.2 Thematic analysis

King's template was used to arrange, study and comprehend the qualitative data from the grey literature indicated in Table 1 (thematic analysis) (King, 2012). 'Template analysis' refers to a qualitative data analysis method that uses specific criteria (King, 2012). Most of the time, this involves transcripts of interviews, but it has been used for various other types

of text documents. Analyses frequently start with a set of a priori codes that highlight potential focus areas. These codes, however, can be changed or removed if they are found to be ineffective or inappropriate for the data being analysed. First, the researcher should go through the data and identify any parts that appear to tell them something relevant to their research questions, based on any predetermined themes. Such segments are coded if they are related to a priori themes. With no initial template in place, new themes are created when a subset of the data has been coded to contain important information.

'Themes' are characteristics of participants' stories that the researcher thinks are essential to the research question. These are things that people say that show how they think and feel about certain things (King, 2012). 'Coding' is the process of finding common themes in stories and giving them labels (codes) to help people find them (King, 2012). In template analysis, it is common to figure out some themes in advance, called 'a priori' themes (King, 2012). This is because a research project starts with the assumption that certain parts of the things being studied should be given more attention (King, 2012).

The process begins with the development of an initial template, which is essentially a set of codes or themes derived from the researcher's prior knowledge, the research question and a preliminary examination of the data. As the analysis progresses, the template is iteratively refined, and new themes may emerge from the data. This allows for flexibility and adaptability in the analytical process while maintaining a structured and systematic approach. The method is well-suited for analysing large amounts of qualitative data, such as written documents, which is a typical source of information in the study of the spa industry. King's template analysis allows for both inductive and deductive approaches, enabling the incorporation of existing theories and frameworks while still allowing for the emergence of new insights from the data. The iterative process of refining the template ensures a thorough examination of the data, reducing the risk of overlooking important themes or patterns. The use of a clearly defined template makes the analysis more transparent and reproducible, enhancing the credibility and trustworthiness of the study's findings.

The following steps were taken to conduct the King's (2012) template analysis for this study:

1. Data collection: A comprehensive dataset comprising interviews with spa industry professionals, case studies and relevant documents was compiled.
2. Initial template development: Based on the research question and a preliminary examination of the data, an initial template containing key themes and sub-themes was created.
3. Data coding: The data was systematically coded using the initial template. This involved assigning codes to relevant text segments and identifying relationships between different themes.
4. Template refinement: As the coding process progressed, the initial template was continually refined to accommodate emergent themes and to ensure all relevant aspects of the data were captured. This iterative process continued until a final template was developed that accurately represented the study's findings.
5. Interpretation and synthesis: The final template was used as a basis for interpreting the data and synthesising the findings. This involved discussing the relationships between themes, drawing conclusions and considering the implications of the findings for the spa industry amid the Covid-19 pandemic.

By following these procedures and guidelines, the study aimed to provide analysis of the challenges faced by the UK spa industry and the strategies that can be employed to boost employee engagement in a post-pandemic landscape.

This research set out to find solutions to staffing problems in the UK spa industry. The researcher specifies the three key issues regarding employee engagement (Kahn, 1990) in the UK spa industry: employer branding and attractiveness (Bethron, 2005; Alnaçk et al., 2014), emotional labour (Hochschild, 2012), and outcomes of emotional labour. The literature review informed these two topics. Therefore, it seems reasonable to suggest they

provided a starting point as the a priori key themes when analysing employee engagement in the UK spa industry. Various sub-themes have also been developed based on the research question and literature review which are listed in the following table.

Table 4: Initial Template

Themes	Subthemes
A. Employee branding and attractiveness	Economic factors
	Development factors
	Social factors
	Work–life balance
	Brand image
	Job demands
	Working conditions
B. Emotional labour and outcomes	Display rules
	Surface acting
	Deep acting
	Genuine acting
	Job satisfaction
	Burnout

For the study design, sources were evaluated based on their accessibility and their relevance. As a result of using search terms like ‘effect’, ‘issue’, ‘challenges’, ‘Covid-19’, ‘spa industry’, ‘beauty industry’, ‘employment’, ‘employee engagement’, ‘employee turnover’, ‘employee retention’ and ‘employee attraction’, it was possible to narrow down the search process and gather the most relevant documents for the study. The researcher identified 39 documents listed in Table 5 using a Google search engine considering the inclusion and exclusion criteria mentioned in Table 3 in Chapter 3. The following table provides a breakdown of the numerous source documents the researcher chose to include in this study, based on the earlier inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Table 5: List of documents identified after inclusion and exclusion criteria

Dates	Sources	Document
	Website materials	
01/06/2020	(Spa-uk.org, 2020)	Covid-19 re-opening guidelines resources
14/01/2021	(Eve Oxberry, 2021)	Beauty, hair and spa achieve Government representation under new Personal Care sector
01/04/2021	(Spa Industry Association, 2021)	Why Employee Welfare Should Be Your No. 1 Priority In 2021
25/07/2021	(Davidson, 2021)	Employees Refusing to Return to Work Due to COVID
01/08/2021	(Whitby, 2021)	Pandemic’s impact on US spa industry highlighted in ISPA’s 2021 Industry Study
02/12/2021	(Professionalbeauty.co.uk. 2021)	Coronavirus (Covid-19): support guide for beauty salons, spas and self-employed therapists
07/12/2021	(Page and McCann, 2021)	Emotional styling: How can hairdressers help?
	Newspaper and	

	articles	
15/04/2020	(Dean, 2020)	Covid-19 and 100 days that transformed the world: the 17 April edition of <i>The Guardian Weekly</i>
30/05/2020	(Kearney, 2020)	Coronavirus 30 May: at a glance
01/09/2020	(<i>The Economist</i> , 2020)	Covid-19 has forced a radical shift in working habits
23/09/2020	(<i>Independent</i> , 2020)	Coronavirus: Timeline of key events since UK was put into lockdown six months ago
14/12/2020	(Safi, 2020)	Covid Timeline
29/12/2020	(<i>Telegraph</i> , 2020)	Britain reports record number of daily cases
14/01/2021	(Eve Oxberry, 2021)	Beauty, hair and spa achieve Government representation under new Personal Care sector
08/04/2021	(<i>The Economist</i> , 2021)	The rise of working from home: The shift to a hybrid world of work will have a big impact on managers
08/04/2021	(Callaghan, 2021)	Feeling good: The future of the \$1.5 trillion wellness market
01/07/2021	(Kate Morgan, 2021)	The great resignation: How employers drove workers to quit
21/07/2021	(Volini et al. ,2021)	The worker-employer relationship disrupted
01/08/2021	(Williams, 2021)	Reimagining Work: Insights from Deloitte's 2021 Global Human Capital Trends Report
20/08/2021	(<i>The Economist</i> , 2021)	So far, ending pandemic unemployment aid has not yielded extra jobs
27/08/2021	(Christian, 2021)	The great resignation is here, and no one is prepared
08/09/2021	(de Smet et al., 2021)	'Great Attrition' or 'Great Attraction'? The choice is yours
01/11/2021	(Brignall, 2021)	'The great resignation': almost one in four UK

		workers planning job change
	Corporate reports	
01/04/2020	(McGroarty et al., 2021)	Global Wellness Trends 2020
28/05/2020	(Professional Beauty, 2020)	74% of UK beauty salons and spas are ready to reopen by July 4
01/06/2020	(Grzesk, 2020)	What's Next For Wellness
01/06/2020	(Murphy, 2020)	CV-19 Spa Report: June 2020
11/02/2021	(Leckie et al., 2021)	The effects of the pandemic on the hair and beauty sector report
	Government Reports	
24/11/2020	(Ons.gov.uk. 2021)	Hairdressing and beauty by district
14/01/2022	(Gov.uk. 2022)	Working safely during coronavirus (COVID-19)
21/06/2021	(House of Commons Library, 2021)	Beauty and Wellbeing Sector workforce
	Blogs	
14/01/2020	(Jenkins, 2020)	Is the life of a massage therapist's career really only 8 years?
15/01/2020	(Seago, 2020)	The recruitment crisis
16/02/2020	(Downton, 2020)	the challenges of spa recruitment
02/07/2021	(Jenkins, 2021)	How to handle a challenging massage client? Ask the Muscle Whisperer Series
30/09/2020	(Jenkins, 2020)	What was the biggest lesson you learnt as a business owner during Covid-19?

13/08/2021	(Young, 2021)	Why do we have a problem displaying honesty and vulnerability?
20/09/2021	(Young, 2021)	Where have all the therapists gone? A high turnover industry
03/12/2021	(Appointmentfix, 2021)	9 Ways to Motivate Your Salon Staff and Grow Your Business

The above table shows the list and types of documents identified for documentary review. Thirty-nine documents are identified after using inclusion and exclusion criteria generated in Chapter 3. This includes seven website materials, 16 newspapers and articles, 5 organisational reports, 3 government reports and eight blogs. All the texts are copied and pasted in Microsoft Word, and codes are assigned to relevant text and data using the comments function.

Theme 1: Employer branding and attractiveness issues in the UK spa industry

Employer branding and attractiveness remain crucial issues in attracting and retaining employees in the spa industry. Sub-themes generated under this theme include economic and development factors, job demands and working conditions, employee reputation, work-life balance, the shift from employed to self-employed, therapist shortage, and the 'great resignation' or attraction.

Theme 2: Emotional labour and outcomes in the UK spa industry

Emotional labour is another significant factor affecting employee engagement in the spa industry. Sub-themes generated under this theme include spa display rules, profit slavery, wage slavery, alienation and meaninglessness of the job, surface and deep acting, burnout, emotional exhaustion, depersonalisation, and personal accomplishment.

After reviewing the documents and following the King's template process, the sub-themes for further analysis were generated. This process involves refining and sharpening the

discussion on template analysis and thematic analysis, ensuring that both initial and developed templates are included and well differentiated. By incorporating initial and developed templates, the analysis becomes more focused and relevant, allowing the researcher to draw meaningful conclusions from the data. The developed template is illustrated in the following table.

Table 6: Emerging themes from thematic analysis

Themes and sub-themes	Sources	Documents	Publication date
Employer branding and attractiveness: -Economic and development factors -Job demands and working conditions -Employee reputation -Work–life balance -Employed to self-employed -Therapist shortage	(Jenkins, 2020)	Is the life of a massage therapist's career really only 8 years?	14/01/2020
	(Seago, 2020)	The recruitment crisis	15/01/2020
	(Downton, 2020)	the challenges of spa recruitment	16/02/2020
	(McGroarty et al., 2021)	Global Wellness Trends 2020	01/04/2020
	(Professional Beauty, 2020)	74% of UK beauty salons and spas are ready to reopen by July 4	28/05/2020
	(Grzesk, 2020)	What's Next For Wellness	01/06/2020
	(Murphy, 2020)	CV-19 Spa Report: June 2020	01/06/2020
	(<i>The Economist</i> , 2020)	Covid-19 has forced a radical shift in working habits	01/09/2020

-The 'great resignation' or attraction	(Eve Oxberry, 2021)	Beauty, hair and spa achieve Government representation under new Personal Care sector	14/01/2021
	(Leckie et al., 2021)	The effects of the pandemic on the hair and beauty sector report	11/02/2021
	(Spa Industry Association, 2021)	Why Employee Welfare Should Be Your No. 1 Priority In 2021	01/04/2021
	(<i>The Economist</i> , 2021)	The rise of working from home: The shift to a hybrid world of work will have a big impact on managers	08/04/2021
	(Callaghan, 2021)	Feeling good: The future of the \$1.5 trillion wellness market	08/04/2021
	(House of Commons Library, 2021)	Beauty and Wellbeing Sector workforce	21/06/2021
	(Kate Morgan, 2021)	The great resignation: How employers drove workers to quit	01/07/2021
	(Davidson, 2021)	Employees Refusing to Return to Work Due to COVID	25/07/2021

	(Christian, 2021)	The great resignation is here and no one is prepared	27/08/2021
	(de Smet et al., 2021)	'Great Attrition' or 'Great Attraction'? The choice is yours	08/09/2021
	(Young, 2021)	Where have all the therapists gone? A high turnover industry	20/09/2021
	(Brignall, 2021)	'The great resignation': almost one in four UK workers planning job change	01/11/2021
	(Appointmentfix, 2021)	9 Ways to Motivate Your Salon Staff and Grow Your Business	03/12/2021
Emotional labour and outcomes:	(Jenkins, 2020)	Is the life of a massage therapist's career really only 8 years?	14/01/2020
-Spa display rules	(Seago, 2020)	The recruitment crisis	15/01/2020
-Profit slavery	(Downton, 2020)	the challenges of spa recruitment	16/02/2020
-Wage slavery	(Spa-uk.org, 2020)	Covid-19 re-opening guidelines resources	01/06/2020
-Alienation:	(Jenkins, 2020)	What was the biggest lesson you learnt as a	30/09/2020

Meaninglessness of job		business owner during Covid-19?	
-Surface and deep acting		Beauty, hair and spa achieve Government representation under new Personal Care sector	
-Burnout	(Oxberry, 2021)		14/01/2021
-Emotional exhaustion	(Spa Industry Association, 2021)	Why Employee Welfare Should Be Your No. 1 Priority In 2021	01/04/2021
-Depersonalisation		How to handle a challenging massage client? Ask the Muscle	
-Personal accomplishment	(Jenkins, 2021)	Whisperer Series	02/07/2021
	(Davidson, 2021)	Employees Refusing to Return to Work Due to COVID	25/07/2021
	(Young, 2021)	Why do we have a problem displaying honesty and vulnerability?	13/08/2021
	(Young, 2021)	Where have all the therapists gone? A high turnover industry	20/09/2021
	(Professionalbeauty.co.uk. 2021)	Coronavirus (Covid-19): support guide for beauty salons, spas and self-	02/12/2021

		employed therapists	
	(Appointfix, 2021)	9 Ways to Motivate Your Salon Staff and Grow Your Business	03/12/2021
	(Page and McCann, 2021)	Emotional styling: How can hairdressers help?	07/12/2021

As shown in Table 5, the study's valid documents include publication dates, authors, and significant themes relevant to the investigation. To now, 39 documents spanning early 2020 to 2022 have been gathered. These documents were chosen because they were critical to the spa sector during the Covid-19 outbreak. They contain a wealth of information about the spa industry and employment. Employer attractiveness and emotional labour remain the main topic area. After reviewing the documents and following the King's template process, the following sub-themes have been generated for analysis.

Theme 1: Employer branding and attractiveness issues in the UK spa industry

Employer branding and attractiveness remain the critical issues in attracting and retaining employees in the spa industry. Seven sub-themes have been generated to further explore employer branding and attractiveness within the UK spa industry: economic factors (Eger et al. 2019); job demands and working conditions (Eaton et al., 2021; Downtown, 2020); therapist reputation (Taylor, 2021); work–life balance (Rhee et al., 2020; de Smet et al., 2021); employed to self-employed (Jenkins, 2020; Seago, 2020; Young 2021); therapist shortage (Seago, 2020; Raider, 2020); and the great resignation or attraction (de Smet et al., 2021). Economic development, work–life balance, therapist reputation (status), and therapist shortage (labour shortage) are the known concepts from the literature and are consistently found in the documents. Employed to self-employed is derived from the range of benefits for self-employed spa therapists, often mentioned in the documents. Finally, the great

resignation or attraction refers to the aftermath of Covid-19 on the UK labour force, which this research seeks to explore in terms of spa employment (de Smet et al., 2021).

Theme 2: Emotional labour and outcomes in the UK spa industry

Emotional labour is the focal point of the study. After the initial coding of the most closely matching documents, the researcher decided to merge two a priori themes. There are various pieces of information found regarding motivations and obligations for employees while performing emotional labour that leads to burnout, where initial coding of the documents helps to identify seven different sub-themes: spa display rules; profit slavery; wage slavery; alienation; surface acting and deep acting; burnout; and personal accomplishment. All sub-themes are drawn out from both literature and documentary reviews.

Table 7: Chronological map of events and documents published from January 2020 to December 2021

<p>15/01/2020: The recruitment crisis (Seago, 2020)</p> <p>14/01/2020: Is the life of a massage therapist's career really only 8 years? (Jenkins, 2020)</p>	<p>23 March: PM announce first national lockdown, ordering people to work from home</p> <p>26 March: Lockdown measures legally come to force</p>	<p>10 May: PM announce a conditional plan for lifting lockdown, people should return to workplace but avoid public transport</p> <p>30/05/2020: Coronavirus 30 May: at a glance (Kearney, 2020)</p>	<p>4 July: more restrictions are eased in England, including reopening of pubs, restaurants and spa</p>	<p>14 September: 'Rule of six' Indoor and outdoor gathering above six banned in England.</p> <p>22 September: PM announces new restriction including a return to working from home and 10pm curfew for hospitality sector.</p> <p>01/09/2020: Covid-19 has forced a radical shift in working habits (<i>The Economist</i>, 2020)</p> <p>23/09/2020: Coronavirus: Timeline of key events since UK was put into lockdown six months ago (<i>Independent</i>, 2020)</p>
<p>January 2020 February 2020</p>	<p>March 2020 April 2020</p>	<p>May 2020 June 2020</p>	<p>July 2020 August 2020</p>	<p>September 2020 October 2020</p>
<p>16/02/2020: the challenges of spa recruitment (Downton, 2020)</p>	<p>16 April: Lockdown extends for at least three weeks</p> <p>01/04/2020: Global Wellness Trends 2020 (McGroarty al., 2021)</p> <p>15/04/2020: Covid-19 and 100 days that transformed the world: the 17 April edition of <i>The Guardian Weekly</i> (Dean, 2020)</p>	<p>1 June: phased re-opening of schools</p> <p>15 June: Non-essential shops reopen in England but pubs, restaurants and spa remain closed</p> <p>01/06/2020: Covid-19 re-opening guidelines resources (Spa-uk.org, 2020)</p> <p>01/06/2020 What's Next For Wellness (Grzesk, 2020)</p> <p>01/06/2020 CV-19 Spa Report: June 2020 (Murphy, 2020)</p>	<p>3 August: Eat out to help out scheme introduced</p> <p>14 August: Lockdown Restriction eased further, including re-opening indoor theatres, bowling alleys and soft play</p>	<p>14 October: A new three-tier system of Covid-19 restrictions starts in England</p> <p>31 October: PM announces a second lockdown in England</p> <p>30/09/2020: What was the biggest lesson you learnt as a business owner during Covid-19? (Jenkins, 2020)</p>

<p>5 November: Second national lockdown comes into force in England</p> <p>24 November: PM announces up to three households will be able to meet up during a five-day Christmas period of 23 to 27 December</p> <p>24/11/2020: Hairdressing and beauty by district (Ons.gov.uk, 2021)</p>	<p>14/01/2021: Beauty, hair and spa achieve Government representation under new Personal Care sector (Eve Oxberry, 2021)</p> <p>6 January: England enters third national lockdown</p> <p>15 February Hotel quarantine for travellers arriving in England from 33 high-risk countries begin</p> <p>14/01/2022; Working safely during coronavirus (COVID-19) (Gov.uk, 2022)</p>	<p>01/04/2020: Global Wellness Trends 2020 (McGroarty et al., 2021)</p>	<p>28/05/2020: 74% of UK beauty salons and spas are ready to reopen by July 4 (Professional Beauty, 2020)</p>	<p>01/07/2021: The great resignation: How employers drove workers to quit (Kate Morgan, 2021)</p> <p>14/07/2021: Working safely during coronavirus (COVID-19) (Gov.uk, 2021)</p> <p>21/07/2021: The worker-employer relationship disrupted (Volini et al. 2021) (Davidson, 2021)</p> <p>02/07/2021: How to handle a challenging massage client? Ask the Muscle Whisperer Series (Jenkins, 2021)</p>
<p>November 2020 December 2020</p>	<p>January 2021 February 2021</p>	<p>March 2021 April 2021</p>	<p>May 2021 June 2021</p>	<p>July 2021 August 2021</p>
<p>2 Dec: Second lockdown ends and returns to a stricter three-tier system of restriction</p> <p>19 Dec: PM announces tougher restrictions for London and South East England, with a new Tier 4: 'Stay at Home' alert level.</p> <p>21 Dec: Tier 4 restrictions come into force in London and South East England</p> <p>14/12/2020: Covid Timeline (Safi, 2020)</p> <p>29/12/2020: Britain reports record number of daily cases (<i>Telegraph</i>, 2020)</p>	<p>11/02/2021: The effects of the pandemic on the hair and beauty sector report (Leckie et al., 2021)</p>	<p>01/04/2021: Why Employee Welfare Should Be Your No. 1 Priority In 2021 (Spa Industry Association, 2021)</p> <p>08/04/2021: Feeling good: The future of the \$1.5 trillion wellness market (Callaghan, 2021)</p> <p>27/04/2021: The future of UK employment in a post-pandemic world (Social Policy Association, 2021)</p> <p>08/04/2021: The rise of working from home: The shift to a hybrid world of work will have a big impact on managers (<i>The Economist</i>, 2021)</p>	<p>08/06/2021: Professional Spa and Wellness -Employee engagement highlighted at Spatec Europe (Professionalbeauty.co.uk, 2021)</p> <p>21/06/2021: Beauty and Wellbeing Sector workforce (House of Commons Library, 2021)</p>	<p>01/08/2021: Pandemic's impact on US spa industry highlighted in ISPA's 2021 Industry Study (Whitby, 2021)</p> <p>01/08/2021: Reimagining Work: Insights from Deloitte's 2021 Global Human Capital Trends Report (Williams, 2021)</p> <p>20/08/2021: So far, ending pandemic unemployment aid has not yielded extra jobs (<i>The Economist</i>, 2021)</p> <p>27/08/2021: The great resignation is here and no one is prepared (Christian, 2021)</p>

<p>08/09/2021: 'Great Attrition' or 'Great Attraction'? The choice is yours (de Smet et al., 2021)</p> <p>20/09/2021: Where have all the therapists gone? A high turnover industry (Young, 2021)</p>	<p>01/11/2021: 'The great resignation': almost one in four UK workers planning job change (Brignall, 2021)</p>			
<p>September 2021 October 2021</p>	<p>November 2021 December 2021</p>			
<p>13/08/2021: Why do we have a problem displaying honesty and vulnerability? 13/08/2021</p>	<p>02/12/2021: Coronavirus (Covid-19): support guide for beauty salons, spas and self-employed therapists (Professionalbeauty.co.uk, 2021)</p> <p>07/12/2021: Emotional styling: How can hairdressers help? (Page and McCann, 2021)</p> <p>03/12/2021: 9 Ways to Motivate Your Salon Staff and Grow Your Business (Appointfix, 2021)</p>			

The timeline mentioned above depicts the UK government's announcements and events in dealing with the pandemic situation, as well as crucial articles and newspaper reports from *The Economist*, *Telegraph*, and *Daily Mail* websites, which have covered the trends that have followed the spa industry's struggles in this Covid-19 period in detail. *The Economist*, the *Daily Mail*, and the *Telegraph* were chosen because they are widely read and widely distributed in print and online formats, making them accessible to readers worldwide. To give an idea of the breadth of publications, Table 7 lists a variety of papers, reports, blogs and other types of 'grey literature'. The selected documents are discussed to understand the relevance of the emerging material contributing to the research gap from the literature review.

4.3 Spa industry impact of Covid-19

Before the national lockdown and a furlough scheme, there were increasing Covid-19 infections in the UK and businesses were highly affected. An article by Kirsty Mawhinney and Rebecca Day (2020) published by Professionalbeauty.co.uk states that early 2020 was a worrying and stressful time for spa employees where social distancing was advised to businesses. However, spas are business models based around human contact, and the impact on the industry has been severe. Kirsty Mawhinney and Rebecca Day (2020) also state that employees' mental stress of potentially getting infected with a virus while working was enormous. It was also a worrying time for the employers where there was little revenue due to the impact of the Covid-19 outbreak, and they also needed to pay the employee's wages.

The first UK national lockdown was announced on 23 March 2020. All non-essential businesses were ordered to shut down or work from home, which significantly affected all businesses across the UK, including the spa industry, which was forced to close down until further notice (Institute for Government, 2021). The UK government introduced the 'furlough' scheme for employees, which allowed businesses to contact HMRC for a grant to cover 80 per cent of the wages of employees who are not working but are 'furloughed' and kept on the

payroll, rather than being dismissed. This grant could cover up to £2,500 per month (Bruce and Fisher, 2020).

In May 2020, the government released a conditional plan to lift a nation lockdown. Some non-essential shops were allowed to open on 15 June 2020, whereas spas in the UK were only allowed to reopen until 4 July 2020 with strict guidelines. It is recorded that 87 per cent of the employees were on furlough in the first lockdown, which lasted from 23 March 2020 until 15 June 2020.

It was a heated topic in the industry, particularly regarding the personal protective equipment (PPE) and sanitisation regulations required to operate appropriately once the business reopened. More than half (54 per cent) of respondents claimed that they would reopen as soon as the limits were lifted. However, only 13 per cent stated that they expected to be able to operate at total capacity after the restrictions were lifted, according to the research.

However, more than half (57 per cent) of respondents expressed concern about the cost and availability of personal protective equipment (PPE) for therapists. Just under three-quarters (72 per cent) of respondents feel it is important to them that masks are created sustainably. Only 17 per cent of those who took part in the survey strongly agreed that they were 'adequately prepared to train their staff in the usage of personal protective equipment'. Spas should remove testers from their retail displays, according to the majority (76 per cent), and retail products should be merchandised in a non-contact manner, according to the majority (78 per cent).

Seago (2021) states that the spa industry struggles to recruit employees because there is a lack of qualified therapists. Before beginning a career as a spa therapist, these aspiring practitioners must have training in the treatments or therapies they plan to give. Colleges in the United Kingdom provide a wide variety of programmes for an average cost of £600 (Job Guide – Spa Therapist, 2022). Working in a salon is a common way for young individuals to obtain expertise in the spa industry and expand their repertoire of treatments. A BTEC National Diploma in beauty therapy sciences or an NVQ level 3 in spa therapy are the most

common qualifications for therapists in the spa industry. Three or four GCSEs (A* to C or 9 to 4) or an NVQ level 2 in beauty therapy are normally required for admission to these courses (Job Guide – Spa Therapist, 2022). This qualification and its attached fees are the reason that entry cost is an initial barrier to entry into the spa industry.

In September 2020, the UK government announced the introduction of a National Skills Fund to assist adults in obtaining the training and education they need to enhance their employment prospects and contribute to the economy (Department for Education, 2020). However, the National Skills Fund did not cover qualifications and courses that lead to jobs as a spa therapist. Rider (2020) argues that the government abandoned the spa industry in the UK. The spa industry struggles to recruit employees but faces another more significant problem: retention.

Employees had been furloughed for around three months and forced to work after 4 July 2020. Rider (2020) reports that spa bookings were up by 32 per cent, but therapist availability was down 15 per cent in July 2020 compared to 2019. Rider (2020) argues that employees might have refused to come to work because of the risk to their lives and the people they live with. According to Davidson Morris (2021), employees have the legal right to refuse to return to work where they believe they will be at risk of severe and imminent danger by doing so. It could be an excuse for some employees where employers could not take disciplinary action against it (Davidson Morris, 2021). Given the changing context of the pandemic, it is worth evaluating the impact on employer branding and workforce attraction as a significant theme in response to the research question.

4.4 Employer branding and attractiveness issues in the spa industry

It is found that the UK spa industry is struggling to engage employees resulting in burnout and high employee turnover (Seago, 2020; Rider, 2020; Leckie et al., 2021). This theme explores why the spa industry is struggling to attract and retain employees and the effects of Covid-19 on retaining and attracting employees in the UK. Employer attractiveness remains

the critical issue in attracting and retaining employees in the spa industry. Seven sub-themes that explore employer attractiveness within the UK spa industry have been generated: economic factors, job demands and working conditions, work–life balance, therapist shortage, therapist reputation, employed to self-employed and the great resignation and attraction.

Previous research on employee branding and attractiveness found economy and development as the critical factors influencing employee attraction and retention, explored in the following subtheme (Eger et al., 2019).

4.4.1 Economic and development factors

According to Eger et al. (2019), the economic factor is perceived as a critical element that a potential employee looks at in an organisation. According to the Office of National Statistics (ONS), the mean average wage for full-time employees in the United Kingdom in 2020 was £38,600, whereas the median spa therapist salary is £28,000 per year in the UK. The spa industry is considered low-paid work, but it depends on the location and demand (Callaghan, 2021). The average salary of a spa therapist in London is £48,000, with potential income up to £60,000 depending on the working hours they provide, which is above the national average salary in the UK (Glassdoor, 2021). Seago (2020) and Downtown (2020) express that spa businesses can not offer higher wages and incentives to their employees, which is one of the greatest issues in the spa industry. Economic factors appeared to be an essential factor for employees, according to Berthon et al. (2005). In addition, Peri et al. (2015) and Khadka (2015) discovered that the most crucial factor in inspiring and engaging spa employees was the financial aspect, where employees' demand and employers' inability to offer higher pay has been found in the documentary review (Seago, 2020; Downtown, 2020). Santiago (2018) argues that it is not the salary that potential employees look at as the economic value but the costs and benefits involved in monetary value. Seago (2020) says that spa employers were struggling to match the wage demand of the therapist in Edinburgh, UK, because of high competition. In other words, it means that the therapist has the upper

hand in the salary negotiation. Downtown (2020) reports how Malvern Spa in Worcestershire, UK, is tackling the challenges of spa recruitment. Various new reward systems have been introduced for spa employees in Malvern Spa. These include: flexible working hours, a reward system for achieving target and 100 per cent attendance, a loyalty programme, bonus structures and competitive hourly pay. Downtown (2020) claims that introducing a new reward system is effective in retaining and attracting spa employees. This is supported by another study by Fernando and Nishanthi (2021), who argue that the reward system is positively related to attracting, retaining and motivating employees. Flexible working hours are critical demands of the spa employees (Seago, 2020), but there is a shortage of staff and a high demand for spa services (Raider, 2020). Some spas have also introduced a 'gold therapist' scheme which rewards staff for achieving target sales and 100 per cent attendance, which also means that employers are demanding employees to do longer working hours if they want to get the rewards (Murphy, 2020; McGroarty al., 2020). Also, the later loyalty programmes, bonus structures and competitive hourly pay are all monetary incentives. Tarigan et al. (2022) found that employees are no longer happy with monetary incentives, but rather prefer to focus on their own personal development.

There are also employee development issues for spa employees. Seago (2020) argues that there is a skill gap in the spa workforce. She argues that there is a shortage of therapists. Additionally, the industry is attracting fewer young people into the industry, and there is a skill gap. She claims that these young new graduates often lack professionalism and people skills and have a poor attitude towards work. Therefore, spa employers do not offer senior roles to new graduates even after three or four years. Seago (2020) further argues that young therapists keep changing their job as they are not offered senior roles. According to Alnaçk et al. (2014), people switch jobs for a development and growth value in work. The above finding suggests that employees are not getting a growth value and therefore have a higher risk of employee turnover. These findings also agree with the study by Mehta et al. (2014). They argue that employees stay for a shorter time if there is no place for a career

opportunity and tend to be less loyal to the organisation. Therapists are no longer able to rely on strong in-house training and a pleasant working environment to maintain them long-term, as they are required to meet high physical and emotional employment expectations in the spa business (Downtown, 2020). Therefore looking at job demands and working conditions will further explore the spa employment.

4.4.2 Job demands and working conditions

The Covid-19 outbreak has disrupted the global working condition, leading to higher job demand (Eaton et al., 2021). A recent report suggests that 89 per cent of workers said their work life was getting worse, 86 per cent said their well-being declined, and 56 per cent said their job demands had gone up (Volini et al., 2021). It is no secret that spa employees are expected to work long and unsocial hours. It is found that spa employees leave just because they are not allowed to take time off in the evenings, weekends and bank holidays (Seago, 2020). Seago further argues that working long and unsocial hours is the nature of a spa job, and therefore employees need to have a genuine passion for the industry to survive in it. Additionally, the spa industry is not the only job requiring employees to work long and unsocial hours. Downtown (2020) mentions that other professions, including doctors, nurses and chefs, have the same working conditions. Downtown (2020) expresses the necessity to control the working hours of spa employees, which in turn helps spa employers to attract and retain spa employees. This is supported by the study by Rhee et al. (2020), who find that leaders need to address the working environment and maintain work–life balance for employees, improving employer attractiveness and employee retention.

It is further mentioned that the spa job requires high physical and emotional labour, and it is also reported that spa therapists often suffer from physical and emotional exhaustion (Jenkins, 2020; Seago, 2020; Jenkins, 2021). Generally, a spa treatment lasts for 60 to 120 minutes, where the spa therapist's job requires intense physical energy, including frequently using hands and standing throughout the treatment. It is considered unprofessional to take a break during a single treatment. Seago (2020) explains that spa therapists usually wake up

physically tired in the morning, even after enough rest and sleep. Eventually, the physical demands of the spa therapist's job leads to physical exhaustion, which is one of the reasons for difficulties in attraction and retention of spa employees. Nikki Spicer, spa director at Vita Skin Spa, says that most spa therapists in the United Kingdom lack advanced training that promotes hands-free procedures. These techniques minimise the impact on hands and body, significantly extending a career as a therapist (Young, 2021).

It is found that emotional exhaustion is one of the crucial reasons therapists leave the spa industry. Jenkins (2020) explains that nothing will drain a firm more than demanding customers. It is important to establish clear limits with clients to have a promising career for an employee. She further explains that the time and energy spent pursuing money, responding to discount requests, or dealing with rude or abusive customers can compound a situation that could risk employees' commitment to a spa career. This is in line with Hochschild (2012), who argues that emotional exhaustion leads to employee burnout and intention to quit. The finding also shows that the spa industry has high job demands under extreme working conditions, causing employees to quit. This is also supported by Craig (2018), who raises the issue that a high workload can severely negatively influence both the physical and mental health of spa therapists, which increases employee turnover.

Alnaçk et al. (2014) argue that employee status and reputation play a vital role in employee branding and attractiveness. Therefore, by focusing on the reputation of therapists, the documentary review highlights further problems facing the spa industry.

4.4.3 Therapist reputation

This theme emerged from the documentary analysis and the literature review of employer branding and attractiveness (Alnaçk et al., 2014). The spa's fundamental value is to improve customers' health and well-being using spa treatments (Craig, 2018). Everyone wants to do good and feel good. People want to pursue a career where they feel valued and respected while working in a beautiful and peaceful environment (Alnaçk et al., 2014).

It is found that spa treatment accelerates the healing process, increases circulation, and may even help restore emotional equilibrium where customers see a therapist as a healer (Jenkins, 2021). After treatments, clients are relaxed and happy, which makes the therapists pleased, as they are the reason for it. They enjoy what they do and are motivated to continue a career that provides a sense of accomplishment while also getting wages (Jenkins, 2021). This finding supports the study by Alvi et al. (2014), where employees look for a sense of pride in their work and accomplishment, leading to employee engagement. Nevertheless, that is not the case for all where therapists' lousy reputation is a vital factor in the difficulty in attracting and retaining employees.

There have been reports that people visit spas and ask for sex services (Jenkins, 2021; Magdalene Taylor, 2021). This also means that some sectors of British society think of spa therapists as sex workers, which spa employees find disrespectful and humiliating. The spa therapist does not like or want to be called 'masseuse' or 'masseur'. Taylor (2021) blames the media for the bad reputation where 'masseuse', 'masseur' and 'massage parlour' are often portrayed as sex workers and prostitution in the movies and news. Magdalene Taylor (2021) argues that a bad social perspective is one downfall in engaging the spa workforce. This is supported by a previous study by Alvi et al. (2014), who state that employees seek a respected job. Further, Ballinger et al. (2016) argue that employees' prestigious reputation plays a vital role in employee retention, which is not the case in the spa industry.

The Covid-19 pandemic has disturbed the UK labour market, as everyone is questioning their life and work (de Smet et al., 2021). The following section will discuss the work–life balance of spa employees in further detail.

4.4.4 Work–life balance

Flexibility options and the ability to balance work and personal life are becoming increasingly important in the workplace (Rhee et al., 2020). The Covid-19 pandemic has taught us that employees crave engagement in the human aspects of work. De Smet et al. (2021) argue that employees are exhausted, and many are depressed. They want their jobs to have a

fresh and improved feeling of purpose. They want to develop social and interpersonal relationships with their co-workers and superiors. They desire a sense of shared belonging. Employees seek not only financial security, but a sense of purpose and meaning in their work from their superiors and co-workers. They want meaningful work. De Smet et al. (2021) also found that 64 per cent of the employees have the intention to quit their job.

It is found that the spa industry in the UK is struggling to provide a work–life balance to its employees. There is an increased demand for treatments with longer opening hours. Therefore, employees are expected to work long hours where most of the spa’s openings are 9 am to 10 am, seven days a week, so there are many evenings, weekends and bank holidays (Seago, 2020). Seago (2020) confesses that employees want to enjoy their evenings and weekends not always working, so a spa might struggle to meet the demands of both employees and customers. She notes that many employees simply left the job because they could not take the day off they wanted. This finding is related to Mitchell et al. (2001), who argue that the more connections employees have with their job and personal life, the more likely they will remain engaged, optimistic and devoted to the organisation. It is found that spa employers could not provide the work–life balance to their employees, leading to higher employee turnover, which agrees with Rhee et al. (2020), who argue that work–life balance is positively related to job satisfaction and has a more significant impact on employee turnover intentions.

Hochschild (2012) states that conflict in emotions occurs when an employee has to display specific emotions that contradict genuinely felt emotions. This shows that spa employees’ ‘psychological contract’ with the employer and the organisational display rules is to work long hours, especially on evenings, weekends and bank holidays, where employees’ genuine personal feelings are to spend their evenings and weekends at home with their families and friends (Seago, 2020). It shows a conflict between the therapist’s true feelings and organisation display rules. When employees feel alienated from the product commercialised of their feelings, they have no control over their personal feelings, influencing the intention to

quit (Hochschild, 2012). This is what Karl Marx's theory of alienation explained: employees are alienated from the product of their labour (Feuerbach et al., 1997). Therefore employees do not have the motivation towards the product or organisation but rather for the exchange value (wage). Also in the time of Covid-19 everyone is getting freedom of work including flexible working rights, work from home and lower working hours with high pay. Additionally, there are higher opportunities for work after Covid-19 than before (*The Economist*, 2020; Leckie et al., 2021). Sonar and Paliwal (2018) argue that employees tend to show continuance commitment (CC) to an organisation because of the scarcity of available alternative jobs. That is not the case with spa employees post-Covid-19. Also, these findings agree with Li et al. (2018), who explain that if an employee believes that another job offers more opportunities for satisfaction and fewer opportunities for dissatisfaction than their current role, and if their organisational commitment is low, they are more likely to leave the organisation. Therefore, here spa employees could negotiate better terms with another employer and reject the working conditions of the current one. However, what if 'employees' are not employed? The documentary review provides further illustration of the issues facing the spa industry by considering self-employment.

4.4.5 Employed to self-employed

Spa therapists can either work for a spa employer or be self-employed. There are pros and cons for being both employed and self-employed. According to Jenkins (2020), people choose a self-employed spa therapy career because it offers a flexible working schedule where the treatment is always in demand. Also, self-employed therapists have a higher potential income, up to £90,000 a year, according to a recent report (Glassdoor, 2019). That means self-employed therapists have higher 'economic value' and greater work–life balance than those working in a spa. Therefore a spa organisation is less attractive to the potential employees. According to the National Statistics Labour Force Survey, 60 per cent of spa therapists are self-employed, and that number is continually rising. Seago (2020) argues that therapists who work in a spa business for a while gain experience, and after some time, they

switch to self-employment. It is even easier to promote oneself on various mobile platforms like Treatwell and Trip Advisor, where they can charge a fraction of what spas do while they can afford it. According to an article published by Jenifer Young (2021), spa employees had been in lockdown for a long time and had time to reassess their lives and move to different careers. Additionally, those who did not leave the industry used time and money from furlough to become self-employed.

These findings suggested that spa employees shift from employed to self-employed for better work–life balance, flexible working hours, potential higher pay, and freedom of work. This shows that spa businesses are losing employees and cannot recruit as easily. The next sub-theme demonstrates further staffing issues facing the spa industry UK by considering therapist shortage.

4.4.6 Therapist shortage

The theme of therapist shortage emerged strongly from the document analysis, and it is also the primary pillar of the investigation. As the economy has strengthened, this concern has gained significance, putting pressure on the labour supply market. It is found that it requires months and years of training and education to be a qualified spa therapist. Seago (2020) explains that the spa industry struggles to recruit a therapist progressing from NVQ level 2 to 3. She further explains that she contacted a local college in Reading, UK, where she found that only four people were progressing into level 3, where she got only one applicant who had been trying to recruit two people in the last six months (Murphy, 2020).

The documentary analysis frequently found the issue of higher education and training costs underpinning the UK spa industry (Seago, 2020; Raider, 2020; Young, 2021; Jenkins, 2020; Jenkins, 2021). It is also found that spa employers invest heavily in ‘training bonds’ with spa firms struggling to retain workers. Training bonds are becoming more prevalent, typically mandating that a therapist who leaves within two years of completion of the course repay the employer for the cost of the course (Seago, 2020). Additionally, Seago explains that people do not want to sign up because two years is a long time to commit.

Covid-19 and the series of lockdowns have additionally had a severe financial impact on the spa industry (House of Commons Library, 2021). Rider (2020) argues that the government abandoned the spa industry in the UK during the Covid-19 pandemic. The UK government released the National Skills Fund in September 2020, which aimed to help adults train and gain the valuable skills they need to improve their job prospects and support the economy (Department for Education, 2020). However, the National Skills Fund did not cover spa therapy qualifications and courses that lead to jobs as a spa therapist. Therefore, it is difficult to attract employees but invest in 'training bonds'.

Employers in the spa industry placed a higher emphasis on employee perks, work–life balance and economic and professional development in order to adopt a more strategic HR approach (Seago, 2020; Rider, 2020; Young, 2021; Jenkins, 2020; Jenkins, 2021). However, spa companies must seek to strengthen the industry's brand and impression, address the issue of unsocial hours, develop a tiered compensation structure and begin marketing the industry to children as early as primary school. Some findings also suggest that spa employers blame Brexit for an employee shortage in the UK spa industry (Seago, 2020). Rider (2020) believes more government support is needed to solve the staffing problems in the UK spa industry.

Additionally, the Covid-19 pandemic disrupted the global workforce and the way people work. Industries across the globe were hit by a dubbed 'great resignation' where millions of people started to leave their jobs, with and without a job in hand. Therefore it is worth considering the impact on the spa industry workforce.

4.4.7 The 'great resignation' or attraction

As mentioned earlier, the reasons employees leave the spa industry include low pay, unsocial working hours, poor work–life balance, high physical exhaustion, emotional challenges, humiliation and lack of career progression where the nature of the job pressure can be challenging, especially for the younger generation. After the first lockdown in the UK, spa bookings were up by 32 per cent, but therapist availability was down 15 per cent in July

2020 compared to 2019. According to Sonar and Paliwal (2018), employees can only resign when they have a choice. Therefore it is essential to explore the historical question of why employees leave.

Morgan Lewis, a spa therapist cited in Jenkins (2020), stated that she felt tired and physically exhausted at the end of the shift when she would not have the energy to look after and play with her two-year-old son after work. She explained that after years of working as a therapist, she lacked the energy necessary to continue working fully. Eventually, she worked part-time as a spa therapist rather than leaving because she genuinely loved spa therapy. The findings also aligned with the continuance commitment (CC) theory by Culpepper (2014), who states that people develop emotional attachment after working in the same place for a longer time where they are hesitant to quit their job due to their emotional investment. However, this is the case of one staff member, while other findings suggest that 70 per cent of UK spa employees intend to quit their current job (Aaron de Smet et al., 2021).

Oxford Economics research discovered that it takes newly hired professional staff 28 weeks to reach peak production at the cost of £25,200 per employee turnover (Aaron de Smet et al., 2021). According to a recent survey on wage growth, 43 per cent of UK employers anticipate a 2 per cent increase in average pay over the next 12 months, while 25 per cent anticipate a 3 per cent increase. Rider (2020) asserts that the spa industry in the United Kingdom has been significantly affected by the Covid-19 pandemic and is not financially strong enough to offer pay raises. With the shortage of staff and the high demand for spa services, employees are expected to work overtime. Young (2021) also asserts that benefits (wage, bonuses, flexible working hours) that the majority of spa firms in the UK offer are relatively low compared to other large industries, which results in spa therapists switching careers. This is consistent with the findings of Hossain (2017), who asserts that employees' intention to leave is contingent on the organisation's offerings, including economic factors, working environment, performance appraisal and career growth, and Brown (2018), who

states that organisations could offer employees better opportunities, higher pay and more benefits.

Young (2020) claims that spa therapists were planning to leave their job before the government lifted the first national lockdown; they just did not leave because they were getting furloughed. At the end of the first national lockdown, other non-essential businesses were allowed to open on 15 June 2020, when Covid-19 cases were still on high alert and the spa industry was still forced to close. The fear of getting the coronavirus was enormous, and the future of the spa industry was uncertain. There was strict guidance on operating businesses, including use of PPE, maintaining social distance, employing a physically contactless service, sanitising and ventilation of premises. It is found that spa employers and employees were anxious about how they would be able to follow the government rules and guidance once they were permitted to open where the job demands physical contact and operation in a small unventilated room (Tague et al., 2021). Additionally, 46 per cent of the employees felt that the spa industry would not open following the lift of restrictions and another 27.7 per cent anticipated that there would be redundancies once it re-opened (Spa Association UK, 2020). The spa industry was only allowed to reopen until 4 July 2020. Raider (2020) reported that 13 per cent of spa therapists did not turn up after the ban was lifted because of the spa organisation's uncertainty. This aligns with the study of Ahmed et al. (2016) and Mürşide and Hamitolu (2018). They claimed that people are constantly on the lookout for stable organisations that offer opportunities for career progression. In the above case of the spa industry, however, spa employees left because they did not see a clear picture and were uncertain about the industry's future. These findings agree with the study by Katsikea et al. (2015), who argue that organisational and job insecurity positively and significantly influenced turnover intention.

Another report suggests that 36 per cent of the employees who quit did so without having a job in hand (Brignall, 2021). The Office of National Statistics (ONS) (2020) reported that in October 2020, the unemployment rate increased to 5.2 per cent in the UK, a record high in

the last five years. This also means that businesses across the UK, including the spa industry, had the opportunity to attract potential employees. Therefore the battle of the talent hunt reaches its limit high. It is found that employers across the UK are pushing their limits to attract employees where employers are offering signing bonuses of up to £10,000 and offering flexible working hours, including work from home, to entice new employees (*The Economist*, 2020).

Additionally, it is discovered that the National Skills Fund established by the government to address the UK workforce's talent gap did not cover spa therapists' qualifications and courses. Due to a high volume of employees leaving in specific industries, employers offer signing bonuses of up to £10,000 to entice new employees. Young (2021) argues that the spa industry is not in a financial position to offer attractive signing bonuses and higher wages.

4.5 Summary

Thematic analysis is used to determine solutions to the spa industry's workforce challenges (King, 2012). initial codes were generated by becoming thoroughly familiarised with the 39 identified documents. Two key themes ('employer attractiveness issues in the spa industry' and 'emotional labour and burnout') were developed by evaluating the initial codes and literature review. After generating themes, sub-themes emerged within the main themes. 'economic and development factors', 'job demands and working conditions', 'work-life balance', 'therapist shortage', 'therapist reputation', 'employed to self-employed' and 'the great resignation and attraction' sub-themes were generated under 'employer branding and attractiveness issues in the spa industry'.

To summarise this chapter, it is clear that the spa industry is operating in a challenging environment regarding employee engagement, attraction and retention. Therapist scarcity has been a significant problem within the UK spa industry. Seago (2020) blames colleges which are not able to produce qualified spa therapists. Raider (2020) believes that the

government is not doing enough to tackle the ‘therapist shortage’ in the times of Covid-19. Employee status and reputation play a vital role in attracting and retaining employees, and Jenkins (2021) and Magdalene Taylor (2021) blame the media for the bad social reputation of spa therapists in the UK. It is also found that most spa therapists leave spa careers because of high physical job demands. Economic and development factors play a significant role in attracting and retaining spa employees. Due to the impacts of Covid-19 on the spa industry, the current employee benefits are neither appealing to potential employees nor sufficient to retain current employees (Seago, 2020; ONS, 2020; Downtown, 2020).

Raider (2020) argues that treatment demand increased by 30 per cent following the pandemic, while employee availability decreased by 13 per cent. Due to staff scarcity and high demand for treatment, work–life balance has been a significant staffing issue in the spa business in the United Kingdom (Downtown, 2020; Seago, 2020; Young, 2020). It is reported that employees leave just because they are expected to work long and unsocial hours (Seago, 2020). Some spas are making a deliberate effort to tackle employees’ work–life balance by offering flexible working hours and incentives for 100 per cent attendance (Downtown, 2020; Seago, 2020; Young, 2020). Offering work–life balance to employees has been a successful strategy for some employers. However, most spa employers cannot offer flexible working hours due to high demand and staff shortage, which worsens the staffing issue (Raider, 2020; Seago, 2020).

Covid-19 has affected not only the spa industry but also workforce behaviours. Following the ‘great resignation’, there is a battle for attracting and retaining talent among UK businesses which has resulted in offers of pay raises, great benefits and signing bonuses (Miles Brignall, 2021). A great range of employee benefits has been introduced by some of the spa businesses across the UK to tackle employee attraction and retention (Young, 2020). However, other spa employers suggest that the spa industry was not financially able to offer pay raises and other benefits, which worsens the situation (Downtown, 2020; Seago, 2020).

The importance of employer branding is essential for the spa industry. Spa firms have provided a broader range of employee benefits to address the issue of staff attraction and retention, and issues such as employee training and development, work–life balance and employee reputation are receiving increased attention in plans. Employers are enhancing working conditions, fostering a more pleasant work culture and emphasising employee happiness as they compete against both internal and external competition.

It is also found that spa therapists are prone to high emotional exhaustion (Jenkins, 2020; Downtown, 2020; Jenkins, 2021; Magdalene Taylor, 2021). Raising wages and offering attractive benefits are the primary tools that spa businesses have used. However, emotional labour plays a vital role in attracting and retaining valuable employees. Therefore, the emotional labour theory (Hochschild, 2012) will be analysed in the next chapter, allowing a richer exploration of the staffing issues within the UK spa industry.

5 Chapter 5: Discussion

5.1 Introduction

The previous chapter presented the study findings; this section progresses to the discussion about the examination of employee attractiveness, retention and engagement through the lens of emotional labour (Hochschild, 2012). The intention is to demonstrate how emotional labour is encountered in the spa industry and how it affects employees' job satisfaction and burnout related to employee intentions to quit. Hochschild's (2012) emotional labour theory emerges as an essential theme in exploring spa industry staffing from the grey literature identified within this study. It plays a vital role in employee engagement and burnout. Seven different sub-themes were further generated through a documentary review to explore the staffing issues in the UK spa industry.

5.2 Spa display rules

Emotional management is critical in the spa industry, as the services frequently emphasise relaxation and happy sentiments. As a result, body language, facial expression and communication are critical components of the service. Spa services have specific display rules. Hochschild (2012), therefore, argues that employees need to suppress their true feelings and show appropriate emotions as dictated by the display rules of the organisation.

Display rules are a set of guidelines for how people should behave in certain situations, such as the workplace, to determine what emotions are suitable and how they should be exhibited in public (Okabe, 2018). Spa employees do not receive professional training in emotion management, although the spa business does offer customer service training. The spa sector offers two types of training: orientation and on-the-job training. All newcomers acquire the necessary social skills, tasks, required behaviours, beliefs and attitudes in order to function in an organisation. In the spa industry, not all display rules are written in employee manuals or training courses, and it is the 'psychological contract' between employee and employer (Okabe, 2018).

A spa is a place for tranquillity and well-being where a smiley face, politeness, friendly behaviour, kindness, compassion and courtesy are the essential display rules of the organisation (Page and McCann, 2021). The employer communicates and enforces display rules during selection and performance evaluations where spa managers must ensure that spa employees follow the rules, stay within the established parameters and perform their responsibilities as intended. These display rules serve as goals for employees, directing their attention and motivation toward emotion regulation when conflicting feelings occur, similarly demonstrated by Hochschild (2012). These display rules are monitored and reviewed by managers and employers through customer feedback and online reviews.

Additionally, it has been found that spa businesses have introduced reward systems to motivate employees to meet sales targets and provide excellent customer feedback (Spa-uk.org, 2020). These reward systems also act as an emotion monitoring system where employees are obliged to perform great emotions that meet the organisational display rules to get a reward. Otherwise, there could be a disciplinary action, as explained by Amissah et al. (2021).

Organisational display rules are also dictated by government policy and society (Leckie et al., 2021). For example, after the outbreak of Covid-19, there was a massive fear of getting the virus (Tague et al., 2021). Spa employees needed to ensure that the spa premises and treatment were safe for visitors and clients (Gov.uk, 2021). Clients were asked if they had any Covid-19 symptoms (Professionalbeauty.co.uk, 2021). There was little confirmation if the customers were telling the truth or lying; therefore, employees continually had the fear of getting the virus from a customer (Tague et al., 2021). On top of that, employees needed to make sure customers were feeling safe at the same time. Here, displaying a calm emotion is the display rule of the spa organisation and employees are obliged to suppress their anxiety, stress or fear. They need to display calm behaviour, finish treatment and move on to the next customer.

This observation of the contrary position of the spa services and the spa workers is hugely important as an observation of the study in terms of the organisation holds the critical influence on display rules where all these display rules are created to deliver excellent customer service and maximise profit. Therefore, to explain how employers and employees engage in emotional labour, the following themes, 'profit slavery' and 'wage slavery', will be explored.

5.3 Profit slavery

The theme of profit slavery emerged in the notion that a business's primary mission is to maximise shareholder value, and everything else is secondary. As Milton Friedman (2007) clearly stated, 'the business of business is business'. Consequently, local communities and society suffer due to this obsession with efficiency and profit.

Like every other business, the spa industry's primary goal is to make a profit, and Kahn (1990) defines employee engagement as a tool to maximise profit. There is a high demand for spa services but a low supply due to a shortage of staff within the industry (see Chapter 4.8). Additionally, Covid-19 and the series of lockdowns during the outbreak have significantly affected the UK spa industry, both financially and in the industry workforce. The spa industry is struggling to generate profit because of the shortage of therapists and the effects of Covid-19 (Raider, 2020; Seago, 2020; Young, 2021; Appointfix, 2021). In turn, spa employees are forced to provide the highest possible customer service to survive in this challenging environment. It is found that, before the Covid-19 outbreak, there were limited benefits and offerings for spa employers despite the shortages of staff. Employers gave less priority to employee well-being and engagement and only started offering attractive benefits after employee retention got out of hand. These findings also show that employees are seen as a profit-making machine rather than humans. This is strong evidence that profit is the primary objective of the spa organisation, where employee engagement comes after profit. This is also supported by Feuerbach et al. (1997) and Hochschild (2012), who state that managers and employers are under constant pressure to extract more value from their

employees. Thinking about this further in terms of the notion of earnings links, wage slavery helps illustrate the position of the workforce in terms of the provision of service and the contradictory notion of service provision for employees and their motivators.

5.4 Wage slavery

It is a fact that everyone's existence is contingent upon a wage, salary or profit. One may argue that employees are wage slaves, while employers are profit slaves. The median spa therapist salary is £28k per year in the UK, whereas the average salary in London is £48k potential income, up to £60k depending on working hours (Glassdoor, 2021). Working harder and more working hours means they could earn more money.

According to Collum (2021), income potential is one of the main reasons people choose to work in the UK spa industry. Eger et al. (2019) state that 'economic value' is one of the key factors attracting potential employees. Spa employees engage in emotional labour in exchange for value, which is wage (Seago, 2020; Glassdoor, 2021; Page and McCann, 2021). This shows agreement with earlier literature where Hochschild (2012) claims that employees need to manage and perform certain emotions in the workplace, whether they like it or not; they have to do it, as they are paid to do so. Hebson et al. (2007) explain that employees' emotions are sold to customers for organisational profit, and employees are paid wages in exchange. Management of emotion is crucial in the spa industry owing to the fact that the spa is a place where people go to relax their mind, body and soul; therefore the spa employees' codes of conduct are designed to create a calm and friendly atmosphere that penetrates the entire facility, resulting in a delightful environment where attractive and polite people deliver the best in personal care without pretentious airs (McGroarty al., 2020; Spa Industry Association, 2021).

Spa therapists are getting paid at the median wage of £28k per year; it has been found that there was an upward trend in spa employees switching to self-employment or other careers during Covid-19 in search of better pay (Seago, 2020; Jenkins, 2020; Young, 2021).

Findings also suggest that even though work–life balance and organisational offerings are crucial to employee motivators, money is the main factor influencing employee job satisfaction and intention to leave. This study agrees with the previous scholar Bolton (2005), who argues that money is the primary motivation why spa employees perform emotional labour.

Jenkins (2021) shows the various experience of spa therapists in the UK. It is found that spa therapists face a challenging situation while dealing with annoying customers. She said that a customer booked their appointments and kept calling to cancel. Even though the employee got annoyed, she kept in touch with the customer and continued to be of support where possible, and eventually she gained a regular customer. It shows that the employee performed an effective coping strategy (deep or surface acting) because she did not want to lose the customer, which reflects the study by Hochschild (2012) which shows that employees are obliged to manage their rules for commercial purposes where the main organisational agenda is to make a profit (Butler and Russell, 2018). The above findings also agree with a similar study by Lee et al. (2014) which shows that emotional labour positively influences customer satisfaction.

It is, however, challenging to maintain a cheerful attitude or a smiley face at all times. Spa employees have to show a pleasant smile and maintain a polite environment, even if they have been mistreated, because they are given a salary. Hochschild (2012) argues that employees need to follow specific display rules dictated by the organisation, commercialised for customer satisfaction. Additionally, when there is a conflict between genuine feelings and organisational feeling rules, employees need to suppress their true feelings and display appropriate feelings that the organisation requires.

It is also found that some spa businesses have introduced the 'Gold therapist' scheme which rewards staff for achieving target sales and excellent customer care feedback (Downtown, 2020). The findings also suggest that an employee might engage in emotional labour because she wants to achieve target sales and does not want to get a bad review.

Otherwise, she would be in a position for disciplinary action, which might lead to losing a job. Igbojekwe (2015) demonstrates a similar study where performance appraisal and job security help employees engage more in emotional labour.

It is found that the organisation dictates the emotional display rules where employees engage in emotional labour in exchange for wages, rewards, incentives and job security (Downtown, 2020; Jenkins, 2021). As discussed earlier, employees want career growth, learning and development, status and respect (see sections 4.3, 4.4 and 4.5). However, all the findings suggest that their primary motivation is money. This also means that they are detached from the organisational rules. Downtown (2020) describes a therapist who was annoyed by a customer. She was not doing this job for the customer's benefit but for her own: either to earn more money or for fear of not getting money. This evidence clearly shows that the spa organisation dictated her emotions; where a product is a smile, a mood, a sentiment or a relationship, it begins to belong more to the organisation and less to the self. This agrees with Hochschild (2012), who argues that employers own the means of production in a capitalist society where employees hand over ownership and effective control of their emotions. Therefore employees become alienated from the emotional labour product, and the emotional labour process results in emotional exhaustion, burnout and intention to leave (Hochschild, 2012). These emotional experiences can be further examined through this notion of alienation and meaningful work.

5.5 Alienation: Meaninglessness of job

Karl Marx first introduced the theory of alienation in 1944, where he discussed four aspects of alienation of labour in a capitalist society. Alienation from the product of labour is one; alienation from the action of labour is another; alienation from one's unique humanity is a third; and alienation from others in society is the fourth (Feuerbach et al., 1997). Karl Marx famously argued that this essential relationship between employees and money generates alienation (Feuerbach et al., 1997). Hochschild's (2012) emotional labour theory explains two types of alienation. She argues that employees are alienated from the emotional labour

product and process. Spa employees are alienated from the result of their emotional labour simply because the capitalist owns and controls its disposal, not the employees.

It is found that spa treatment requires high physical labour and a lot of spa therapists feel physically tired every day and feel exhausted even to greet customers (Jenkins, 2020). On top of that, spa therapists have to face difficult customers. In order to do this they have to put a smile on their faces and treat clients nicely because it is expected by the business even though they are physically tired. Here therapists have to suppress their anger, frustration and exhaustion and put on a smiley face and make polite conversation because that is required by display rules of the spa business. According to Hochschild (2012), spa businesses sell those smiley faces and polite conversation (emotional labour product) to difficult customers where a therapist's emotion is alienated from that product. Here, a product of a spa facility is a good feeling, relaxation and being served by an attractive and polite therapist that customers pay for. These difficult customers have the upper hand and do not have an obligation to be friendly and polite to a therapist. In this uneven emotion exchange relationship, spa employees do not have the power of control over their own emotions. Hochschild (2021) similarly found that employees are alienated from this emotional labour process in her study.

Even under normal circumstances, the spa sector is infamous for having a high employee turnover rate. The physical demands of the profession and the emotional difficulties inherent in regularly performing the role of an unqualified counsellor are leading to burnout (Young, 2021; Page and McCann, 2021). Risk management has become more critical since the outbreak of Covid-19 and the surge in demand that has overwhelmed the business since strict rules were put in place when spas reopened. It is no secret that everyone was afraid of getting the virus. However, during the Covid-19 times, spa employees had to ensure that customers felt safe and valued with excellent service, which added even more emotional burden for spa employees with the potential to lead to emotional exhaustion. Strict rules were introduced: wearing personal protective equipment (PPE), face coverings and social

distancing were compulsory. The UK's government and Spa Industry Association released guidelines on the safety of clients and therapists during a pandemic (Gov.uk, 2021; Spa Industry Association, 2021). The guidelines for spa employees were to use PPE and mask, frequently wash and sanitise hands, clean and disinfect surfaces that are regularly touched, maintain a 2-metre distance as much as possible, and avoid physical contact if possible. However, the guidelines do not explain how to follow the rules effectively while the spa job demands the physical touch of working in unventilated rooms during the pandemic.

Spa employees have additional physical and emotional burdens to bear. Mayer et al. (2016) argue that employees need higher emotional intelligence to cope with high emotional management where its absence may lead to emotional exhaustion. Pujol-Cols et al. (2021) argue that emotional intelligence is developed by repetitive social interaction and repetitive emotional management. Lockdown has allowed some people to stop and reflect, allowing them to consider what they truly desire in life. Psychological researchers Maltz (2002), Lally et al. (2010) and Hill (2011) believe that human behaviours and habits change in 21 days. However, spa employees had been in lockdown and detached from employment for three months. After being furloughed for nearly three months, employees were again forced to follow the organisation's additional sets of display rules. This means that spa employees lack the emotional intelligence to cope with high emotional management. Understanding the impacts of Covid-19 on current spa employment can be gained by examining both surface acting and deep acting.

5.6 Surface acting and deep acting

When an employee suppresses their true feelings and alters their outward emotional display, they participate in surface acting (Hochschild, 2012). For instance, a spa therapist dealing with a difficult customer mentioned by Jenkins (2020) participates in surface acting by displaying a smiling face, positivity and composure while suppressing anger, frustration and exhaustion. Here a therapist is just following organisational display rules and faking a smile and composure to interact quickly and complete a job. The findings corroborate a previous

study by Hebson et al. (2007), which asserts that employees fake their emotions to expedite the encounter and accomplish the job. In that same situation, a therapist can show empathy and try to feel the discomfort and anxiety of that nightmare customer. Hochschild (2012) calls it deep acting, where employees change their true feelings rather than changing their display of emotion.

Jenkins (2021) shows the various experiences of spa therapists in the UK. It is found that spa therapists face a challenging situation while dealing with annoying customers. She said that a customer booked their appointments and kept calling to cancel. She said there could be a reason for customers to cancel an appointment and that reason could be their child, car, etc. She kept in touch with the customer and continued to be of support where possible, and eventually, she got a regular customer. Here, a therapist has every right to feel upset and annoyed but is obliged to talk nicely to the annoying client. The therapist performs deep acting, trying to feel a customer's emotion, thereby feeling and displaying positive emotion. Furthermore, the client is happy, and the therapist gains a valuable customer. This finding supports the results of Amisshah et al. (2021), where deep acting is positively related to consumer satisfaction. Deep acting also keeps the therapist away from his/her own negative emotions and their effects on self-well-being, which aligns with Humphrey's findings (2021), who reports that deep acting is essential in reducing emotional exhaustion. The following section on burnout as the effect of emotional labour sheds more light on spa industry employment challenges.

5.7 Burnout

According to Humphrey (2021), burnout can be measured by analysing three dimensions: emotional exhaustion, depersonalisation and diminished feelings of accomplishment. Emotional exhaustion is a type of role conflict in which people are pressured to act in incompatible ways with their genuine feelings (Pujol-Cols et al., 2021). Emotional exhaustion occurs when workers spend a significant amount of time interacting with others while experiencing severe psychological strain. Contact with others is frequently emotionally

charged and experienced in a tension-filled setting. Individuals may have a sense of exhaustion and depletion in the absence of any source of replenishment. They are physically incapable of facing another day or another individual in need. This can be draining physically and psychologically, leading to issues such as insomnia, PTSD and anxiety.

Not only do spa professionals require technical abilities, but research indicates that they frequently act as informal caregivers for clients and provide social assistance (Page and McCann, 2021). Client disclosures contain an emotional component that requires spa employees to handle client emotions while also controlling their own emotions, expressions and responses. Additionally, clients frequently share mental health difficulties, including anxiety, depression, daily stress and even suicide ideation. Clients also discuss their own identities, including revelations about their ageing, religious and political beliefs, homelessness, membership in the LGBTQIA+ group and financial struggles (Page and McCann, 2021).

It is found that spa employees also provide social advice to their clients by responding to disclosures by monitoring their own and their clients' body language, treating clients like family or friends, respecting the secrecy of disclosures and being client-focused (Page and McCann, 2021). However, spa employees are not routinely trained in their role of social and emotional support for emotionally vulnerable clients. They may face emotional burnout due to both the load of duty they bear and the process of emotional expression that characterises emotional labour. The report suggests that spa employees are emotionally drained (Page and McCann, 2021). Employees acknowledge feelings of emotional exhaustion and undervaluation in their roles, claiming that the spa industry includes more than just therapeutic services. Employees feel that responding to customers' emotions is part of their job. Seago (2020) reports that some spa employees express frustration by saying that is not what they signed up or trained for. To not lose customers to a competitor, they are doing it as a matter of course. It is not just one client, but the nature and high demands of the job force employees to produce emotional labour without time to process their feelings between

clients, leading to higher emotional exhaustion. Young (2021) claims that they enjoy their jobs, but they require assistance in managing their jobs' emotional side. Lack of training and support has significant consequences, as spa workers may face a reduction in their physical and mental well-being without adequate care.

Young (2021) explains that most spa therapists find it difficult and want to avoid treating vulnerable clients, such as cancer patients. Additionally, she argues that they do not want to make their client feel bad, especially if they are already going through a difficult moment, so they are in constant fear of offending others. It can be paralysing and end up inflicting more harm than good. Furthermore, she argues that rejecting someone because they have cancer is not morally right. This shows that there is a conflict between employees. Thus, Young (2021) urges spa therapists to enrol in the Advanced Cancer Awareness Certificate programme to stay current on the latest advancements in cancer treatment, such as proton and immunotherapy, which can help spa employees deal with cancer patients. These findings are supported by the earlier study by Hochschild (2012) and, more recently, Han et al. (2019). Both authors argue that employees' inability to cope with the emotional burden would lead to emotional exhaustion. In order to avoid or alleviate emotional exhaustion, Han et al. (2019) claim that employees engage in depersonalisation as a coping mechanism.

Depersonalisation is a negative affective state in which an employee experiences prolonged and severe exhaustion and strives to avoid further losses of personal resources by emotionally withdrawing from others and viewing them as impersonal objects rather than humans (Pujol-Cols et al., 2021). It is found that some employees frequently counsel their customers to communicate less during treatment in order to prevent developing an empathic relationship with their clients (Page and McCann, 2021). Some spa employees ensure emotional disconnection to their clients to avoid emotional exhaustion (Young (2021)). This means that employees do not want to hear clients' grief or personal problems. Instead, they want to finish their job and move on to another client. Additionally, some spas also display 'keep silent' signs in treatment rooms and advise employees not to share personal

information with their clients. They are encouraged by the employer to communicate as little as possible, finish the treatment on time and move on to the next customer. Staff members are actively urged to detach emotionally from their clients, allowing them to go on to the next client without delay, maintaining the business's flawless operation. This barrier separates the spa therapist from their client, a safeguard that allows employees to retain their emotional equilibrium. The spa therapist sees the consumer as a task rather than a human, demonstrating that depersonalisation has occurred to cope with emotional exhaustion.

However, it is not possible to avoid personal conversations with clients all the time. On top of that, employees want to help and give advice to their clients but cannot do so, and that is the conflict between their authentic self and organisational display rules. Hochschild (2012) argues that this conflict might lead to emotional exhaustion. Young (2021) states that some spa employees frequently want to refuse to serve vulnerable clients, such as those who have cancer, as they need excessive emotional support. Therefore, Young (2021) provides training facilities for therapists in dealing with vulnerable customers.

However, it appears as though depersonalisation begins with display regulations that prohibit the empathic connection with customers and progresses through the feeling rule, which permits deriding attitudes toward customers. Additionally, after training and encouragement, it appears as though depersonalisation occurs due to excessive exposure to the suffering of clients, resulting in emotional exhaustion and depersonalisation. This could also be considered a form of dissociation, in which some spa therapists do not experience the emotions they believe they should. By considering the need for accomplishment, the links between grey literature and the literature review in terms of motivation theory (basic Maslow) can be progressed.

5.8 Personal accomplishment

it is understood that spa employees have a sense of professional inefficacy (Seago, 2020; Young, 2021; Taylor, 2021). They feel they can not satisfy the demands of their employment,

that they can not provide the service they desire for their clients, and that the hard work they perform goes unnoticed and unappreciated by the organisation. A past study by Maslach and Leiter (2016) supports these findings by stating that individuals who have low self-esteem and believe they are unable to carry out their responsibilities are more likely to believe they have failed.

As mentioned before, spa employees lack the required resources and struggle to treat emotionally vulnerable clients, resulting in burnout. This aligns with the study by Mayer et al. (2016) who argue that when a job has an extensive emotional obligation and employees do not possess the required resources, it will likely lead to employee burnout. However, Young (2021) reports that every spa employee should have the education and training to deal with emotionally challenging clients. Young (2021) encouraged employees to participate in the Advanced Cancer Awareness Certificate (ACAC) programme to effectively deal with clients who have cancer. The ACAC programme contains various information and training regarding how spa treatment helps cancer patients. She further argued that employees who participated in the ACAC programme are now comfortable and pleased in dealing with cancer patients. ACAC gives employees the required resources to carry out their job where spa employees are encouraged to participate in deep acting as an emotional regulation strategy, resulting in personal achievement. These findings are consistent with a recent study by Bhowmick and Mulla (2016), who suggest that deep acting leads to a sense of personal accomplishment and job satisfaction, reducing depersonalisation and emotional tiredness.

However, not all spa employees have the opportunity to get training and education on dealing with vulnerable clients. It is also found that spa employees want to avoid treating emotionally vulnerable clients in the first place. It shows that they do not have the resources to fulfil their jobs and also have feelings of guilt about not being able to help their clients. This, in turn, forces employees to participate in surface acting, which leads to depersonalisation and emotional exhaustion.

Further evidence of a lack of personal accomplishment is compounded by a frequent lack of respect from the public, where spa employees feel humiliated. Humiliation is a feeling of being ashamed or losing respect. According to Kampen et al. (2013), humiliation in the workplace is a dark side of a business. Everyone wants and deserves to be respected, but humiliation in the workplace occurs when there is an unequal power relationship between customers and employees (Kampen et al., 2013). There is no doubt that there is an unequal emotional exchange relationship between employees and customers.

There has been a different public perception of spa therapists in the UK. Magdalene Taylor (2021) defined a spa therapist as a respected member of the health care profession who has obtained degrees or certificates, passed board tests and paid for continuing education programmes. The terms 'masseur', 'massage parlour', 'massage business' and 'massage house' began to be used in conjunction with commercial sex in news stories near the end of the nineteenth century, owing to the period's spike in widespread condemnation of prostitution (Magdalene Taylor, 2021). It is further mentioned in Magdalene Taylor's (2021) article that spa therapists do not want to be called 'masseuses'. Nowadays, it is a way for spa people to distance themselves from sex work, regardless of whether genuine 'sex workers' use the word.

Additionally, some places around the globe offer 'sexual service' in the name of spas, and Magdalene Taylor (2021) believes that might be why some people still think of spa therapists as sex workers. This is similar to what Hochschild (2012) argued when she found that passengers who have had a different airline experience expect the same thing from another airline. In the case of spa employees, it is an embarrassing feeling to be perceived as a sex worker. There has also been evidence of people coming to spa facilities and asking for sex services where employees found it humiliating and a sense of anger but had to resolve the situation professionally (Magdalene Taylor, 2021). Here, employees manage their emotions not just as required by the job but also to avoid the emotional burden of the situation. It can be said that the employee is participating in surface acting, whereas Amissah et al. (2021)

found that surface acting lead to emotional exhaustion and burnout. However, not everyone can suppress their shame and therefore engage in surface acting, which eventually leads to burnout and the intention to leave.

5.9 Summary and contribution of the investigation

Figure 3: Revisiting Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework presented here suggests that employee engagement and burnout are two opposite outcomes of employee motivation towards work, with emotional labour playing a crucial role in employee burnout which can lead to turnover intentions. Furthermore, factors such as economic, development, work–life balance, job demands, working conditions and employee status play a significant role in employee attraction, retention and turnover intentions. The framework suggests that employer branding and attractiveness strategies can increase employee engagement resulting in improved job satisfaction, employee retention, attraction and commitment.

Upon analysing the data and findings of the study, it can be concluded that the initial conceptual framework was a reasonable illustration of the study field. The findings of the study largely support the framework's central propositions, as they demonstrate that the UK spa industry is operating in a challenging environment regarding employee engagement, attraction and retention. Spa therapist scarcity has been a significant problem within the UK spa industry. Colleges are not able to produce qualified spa therapists in the UK where the

government is not doing enough to tackle the spa therapist shortage that arose during the Covid-19 pandemic. Spa therapists are also viewed as sex workers in some places within the UK, which in turn ruins the reputation of spa employees. Employee status and reputation play a vital role in attracting and retaining employees and in influencing employees' turnover intentions. The UK was hit by the dubbed 'great resignation' as a result of the Covid-19 pandemic, where the spa industry suffered a 15 per cent reduction in therapist availability. Economic and development factors, work–life balance, job demands and working conditions played a vital role in employee attraction and retention during Covid-19. The importance of employer branding is found to be essential for the spa industry. Spa firms have provided a broader range of employee benefits to address the issue of staff attraction and retention, and issues such as employee training and development, work–life balance and employee reputation are receiving increased attention in plans. Employers are enhancing working conditions, fostering a more pleasant work culture and emphasising employee happiness as they compete against both internal and external competition. However, it is also found that spa therapists are prone to suffering high emotional exhaustion (Jenkins, 2020; Downtown, 2020; Jenkins, 2021; Magdalene Taylor, 2021). Raising wages and offering attractive benefits are the primary tools that spa businesses have used. However, reducing emotional labour plays a vital role in attracting and retaining valuable employees.

It is clear that the spa industry is operating in a challenging environment regarding emotional labour (Hochschild, 2012; Bolton, 2005; Brook, 2009; Maslach and Leiter, 2016; van Dijk et al., 2017). The first theme, 'spa display rules', generated from the documentary review, is consistently used in the past studies of Hochschild (2012), Bolton (2005) and Brook (2009). It is found that spa employees have specific emotional rules they need to manage and display in the workplace. Similar to cabin crew in the study by Hochschild (2012), having a smiley face, politeness, friendly behaviour, kindness, compassion and courtesy are seen as extensions of spa employees' make-up and uniforms which are the display rules of spa employees, as dictated by the spa business (see section 5.2). This is supported by

Hochschild (2012), who argues that workers generally have to manage and regulate their own emotional reactions to maintain a caring work atmosphere and achieve other organisational goals. These spa display rules are regularly enforced and monitored by co-workers, customer feedback, sales targets and a reward system where employees are obliged to manage their emotions (see section 5.2). This is consistent with a previous study by van Dijk et al. (2017), who state that employees are required or even forced to modify their emotional expression as part of their job to enhance organisational performance.

The two themes of 'wage slavery' and 'profit slavery' are generated in the notion that employers are profit slaves and employees are wage slaves. The pandemic disrupted the industry's financial capabilities, where the National Skill Fund did not extend to the spa industry, and spa employers blamed the government for not doing enough for the industry (Raider, 2020; Department for Education, 2020). Due to therapist shortages and the additional impact of Covid-19 on the UK spa industry, spa employers are under immense pressure to extract more value from their employees (see section 5.3), which places profit before the well-being of employees. This is consistent with Milton Friedman (2007), who stated that 'the business of business is business'. Consequently, employees, local communities and society suffer as a result of this obsession with efficiency and profit.

It is found that the organisation dictates the emotional display rules where employees engage in emotional labour in exchange for wages, rewards, incentives and job security (see section 5.2). Employees also want career growth, learning and development, status and respect (see sections 4.3, 4.4 and 4.5). The findings suggest that their primary motivation is money. Spa employees view themselves as wage slaves who work long and unsocial hours in exchange for money (see section 5.4). This investigation reveals a parallel to Hochschild's (2012) study, in which employees are taught and trained to perform as servants in an environment where the customer is always right. Employees at a spa perceive themselves as servants who provide excellent service regardless of their own feelings. In order to assure customer satisfaction despite the fear of getting a virus, spa employees were required to

maintain a perpetual smile, politeness and friendly behaviour while suppressing fear, anger and physical exhaustion (see section 5.5). Additionally, spa employees are often viewed as sex workers where they have to suppress their humiliation and act in a professional manner (surface acting). Eventually, they feel emotional exhaustion but, on the other hand, adopt the axiom that 'the customer is always right', leading them to mask their genuine feelings while displaying the emotions and facial expressions that the business requires. These findings corroborate a previous study by Hebson et al. (2007), which asserts that employees fake their emotions to expedite the encounter and accomplish the job, which leads to emotional exhaustion. Moreover, spa employees do not have the right to reject customers just because they misbehave; therefore, they participate in surface acting to cope with management's ever-growing customer service expectations (see section 5.5). This suggests that, in most cases, spa employees are not able to display their authentic feelings or participate in deep acting, increasing the risk of burnout and intention to leave.

Spa employees are also required to act as informal caregivers for clients and provide social assistance. It takes years of training and education to become a spa therapist. Although the spa business does offer in-house customer service training, spa employees do not receive professional training in emotion management. Mayer et al. (2016) argue that employees need higher emotional intelligence to cope with high emotional management where the absence may lead to emotional exhaustion. There is a clear indication that spa employees lack the emotional intelligence to cope with some of their clients and participate in surface acting, leading to emotional exhaustion and to experience burnout and feeling 'phoney' (see sections 5.5, 5.6 and 5.7). This finding is parallel with the previous studies by Hochschild (2012), Petree (2014), Thwaites (2017) and Wang and Xie (2020), who identify emotional dissonance among employees because of surface acting where they experience burnout, feeling 'phoney' and 'emotional deadness'. Some spa employers are encouraging their employees to participate in higher training and education such as ACAS to enhance emotional intelligence to deal with vulnerable clients.

Those who participated in the training successfully participated in deep acting, which reduces emotional exhaustion and enhances personal accomplishment (see section 5.7). The finding is consistent with the study by Bhowmick and Mulla (2016), who suggest that deep acting leads to a sense of personal accomplishment and job satisfaction, which also reduces depersonalisation and emotional exhaustion. However, problems with the spa industry are that it costs money for additional training and education on how to treat different vulnerable clients. The finding suggests that most spa industries are not financially capable of providing further training and education to their employees. Furthermore, most spa employees do not want to engage in further education and training, which is costly. Instead, they want to avoid vulnerable clients to stay away from any emotional exhaustion. However, there has been a mixed finding among spa businesses where most spa employers do not give the 'right to reject the customer' to their employees and are obliged to serve (see section 5.7). This suggests that employees put their well-being and cost of training before their clients, and on the other hand, employers put profit before employees' well-being. This also means that employees view their clients as impersonal objects rather than humans to reduce emotional exhaustion. On the other hand, spa employers view their employees as a mere instrument for profit. Marx called this phenomenon a 'human nature alienation', which refers to capitalism's detrimental and distorted impacts on our species where humanity is thwarted by its need to put profit before all else (Feuerbach et al., 1997).

The current service job is now socially planned and thoroughly organised from the top down (Hochschild, 2012). The product of a spa facility is a good feeling, relaxation and being served by an attractive and polite therapist that customers pay for. Customers have the upper hand and do not have an obligation to be friendly and polite to spa therapists. In this uneven emotion exchange relationship, spa employees do not have the power of control over their own emotions; therefore, Hochschild (2021) argues that employees are alienated from this emotional labour process. Spa employers often try to suppress their employees' negative emotions, which are often the result of clients treating them disrespectfully or with

anger, while at the same time burying any authentic anger or humiliation they might feel (see sections 5.2, 5.3, 5.4, 5.5 and 5.6). For Hochschild (2012), this organisational effort to control the emotional labour process is an estranging experience for employees.

The apparent contribution of this study in terms of adding to the conceptual territory lies with the following conclusions supported by the discussion that the spa industry is operating in a challenging environment when it comes to the area of emotional labour. Spa employees are alienated from the service and process with money being their primary motivation to work, either the incentive of getting money or the fear of not having enough. On the other hand, spa employers prioritise profit before their employees' authenticity and well-being. Since the Covid-19 outbreak and resulting shortage of therapists, spa employers have begun to more effectively emphasise employee well-being and motivation. Some spa employers across the UK have highlighted a need for additional training and education to enhance employees' emotional intelligence. Due to the cost attached to this additional training and education, however, the majority of spa employees are not able to access it. Therefore, an employee participating in more surface acting and depersonalisation to cope with the specific situation leads to emotional exhaustion, feeling phoney, burnout and intention to leave. Despite the feelings of burnout and intention to leave, employees are motivated to follow organisational display rules and suppress their authentic selves by faking and matching not just to earn money but also for fear of losing a job. However, things changed slightly after the Covid-19 pandemic and the 'great resignation' where thousands of job vacancies became available across the UK. Employees have less fear of losing their job. Since they have been their authentic selves for months, during a national lockdown, employees are now searching for their authentic selves in their workplace upon returning. Organisational offerings such as higher wages, incentives, rewards and flexible working hours have been somewhat effective in keeping in a loop for spa employees who love their spa job. On the contrary, it poses a greater threat of the future of the spa employees who intend to quit and are ready to change their careers.

6 Chapter 6: Conclusion

6.1 Introduction

In conclusion, the research here intends to provide insight into the UK spa industry's staffing issues to identify and develop a commercially available model for employee engagement within the UK spa industry. The theoretical frameworks that helped guide the development of this study were employee engagement (Kahn, 1990), employer branding (Ibrahim et al., 2018), employer attractiveness (Ronda, 2018) and emotional labour (Hochschild, 2012). In spa literature, emotional labour and employee engagement are rarely discussed. Blau et al. (2013), Khadka (2015), Peri et al., (2015) and Craig (2018) previously shed light on spa job demands and the importance of employee engagement but these studies only looked at the physical side of the employee research. Looking through the lens of emotional labour (Hochschild, 2012) was important. The Covid-19 pandemic has disrupted the workforce within the UK spa industry. The more pressing concern is how the industry will adapt and what shape it will take in the coming years. The emergence of the pandemic presented a new research gap concerning the impact of Covid-19 upon the spa sector and further clarified the limitation of HR theorising on the issues and challenges for employee engagement, emotional labour, employee branding and attractiveness due to the global pandemic. This not only limited the nature of this enquiry in terms of primary research but opened new lines of thinking in terms of new contributions to understanding the business issues of employee engagement, employer branding, attractiveness and emotional labour. To address these concerns a qualitative methodology was considered appropriate, and with this in mind four research objectives were developed:

1. To determine the key factors and importance of employee motivation, engagement and retention in the spa industry with a focus on the period of Covid-19
2. To identify the most commonly used employee motivation, engagement and retention strategies within the UK spa business in terms of the impacts of Covid-19

3. To explore the challenges faced by management in employee motivation, engagement and retention strategies during and after the Covid-19 lockdown periods
4. To investigate how to develop future employment attractiveness in the UK spa industry by using employee motivation, engagement and retention strategies.

The purpose of this research is to ascertain the current state of employee motivation, engagement and retention in the UK spa business and to assess the influence of Covid-19 on spa employment. The thesis provides an in-depth discussion of spa employment by generating themes that emerge from the process of documentary review to identify 39 documents, which were carefully selected for the study to answer the research questions.

It becomes clear from the findings that the spa industry is operating in a challenging environment regarding employee attraction, motivation, engagement and retention (see Chapters 4 and 5). The researcher was able to examine the current state of UK spa employment by drawing on historical studies of employee engagement (Kahn, 1990), organisational commitment and employer branding (Berthon et al., 2005; Alnaçk et al., 2014) as well as Marx's theory of alienation and emotional labour studies (Feuerbach et al., 1997; Brook, 2009; Hochschild, 2012). What became clear from this research was that employee engagement plays a vital role in spa business success. It is also found that spa employers across the UK are suffering from a staff shortage due to a lack of employer branding and attractiveness (Seago, 2020; Downtown, 2020; Young, 2021). A further effect of Covid-19 and the so-called 'great resignation' has worsened the situation where spa employers are not financially able to afford better pay rises and organisational offerings, leading to higher employee turnover (Seago, 2020; Jenkins, 2020; Rider 2020; Department for Education, 2020; Aaron de Smet et al., 2021).

Additionally, working in the spa industry entails high emotional labour where spa employees are alienated from their work due to high emotional labour resulting in emotional exhaustion and burnout. This leads to a high number of employees having the intention to quit (see Chapters 5.5 and 5.7). The findings confirm that deep acting promotes job satisfaction and

surface acting promotes burnout (Jenkins, 2020). Spa job benefits and organisational offerings are helping spa employers to keep their employees in a loop from engagement to burnout for employees who perceive spa therapy as a career; however, the more significant question arises on how long can the spa industry keep these valuable assets in these conditions when there are plenty of job openings after the 'great resignation' (Seago, 2020; Jenkins, 2020; Rider, 2020; Department for Education, 2020; Aaron de Smet et al., 2021; Young, 2021; Professional Beauty, 2021).

When exploring the first objective:

1. To determine the key factors and importance of employee motivation, engagement and retention in the spa industry with a focus on the period of Covid-19

it is notable that therapist scarcity has been a significant problem within the UK spa industry. For the past few years, spa businesses have been addressing this issue because there are few certified therapists available. Seago (2020) blames colleges that fail to produce qualified spa workers. Raider (2020) believes that the government is not doing enough to tackle the 'therapist shortage' in the times of Covid-19 where the UK government introduced the 'national skill fund' to tackle the UK skill labour shortage, which does not cover the spa industry. Similarly to Khadka (2015) and Eger et al. (2019), employee status and reputation play a vital role in attracting and retaining spa employees where spa employees are often perceived as having low-paid and low-skilled jobs despite being required to have high-level training and education in the field (Jenkins, 2021). On top of that, spa employees often have to face the humiliation of being compared to sex workers. Magdalene Taylor (2021) blames the media for spa therapy's bad social reputation in the UK. These reputations and humiliation play a vital role in employees' demotivation, directly and indirectly, influencing low job satisfaction and quitting intention (Jenkins, 2021; Magdalene Taylor, 2021).

It is also found that most spa therapists leave their spa careers because of high physical and emotional job demands (Jenkins, 2020; Page and McCann, 2021). Craig (2018) made a

similar argument that spa therapists' physical and mental health might be seriously affected by high workloads, raising staff turnover. Economic factors play a significant role in motivating employees to engage in high physical and emotional job demands. This is supported by Peri et al. (2015), Khadka (2015) and Craig (2018), who observe the motivation factors among spa workers in different countries. There has been a difference in the pay scale of spa employees depending on the city where the spa business is located. Spa therapists can earn from little as £28,000 to as much as £60,000 a year, where more working hours means more money. The findings suggested that their primary motivation is money, where employees viewed themselves as wage slaves who worked long and unsocial hours in exchange for money.

With the further impact of Covid-19 and high spa job demands, spa employees are under enormous pressure to work long and unsocial working hours where the work–life balance of employees is emerging as the significant factor affecting employee engagement, retention and turnover within the UK spa industry (Seago, 2020; Young, 2021; and Raider, 2021). This is confirmed by Rhee et al. (2020), who believe that a good job is no longer defined by salary or career chances alone but rather by the flexibility of alternatives and the ability to reconcile work and personal lives.

It is clear that spa jobs require high physical job demands where high physical exhaustion has been one reason people leave the spa industry (Jenkins, 2020; Young, 2020; Page and McCann, 2021; Young, 2021). It is also found that additional training helps employees reduce their physical effort and helps them in career progression, which keeps them motivated and energised (Jenkins, 2020; Seago, 2020). This is supported by Mehta et al. (2014) and Alnaçk et al. (2014), who argue that training and development are vital in employee engagement.

Finally, employee engagement has been an important factor for spa organisational success. Economic factors, training and development, work–life balance, job conditions and job status are essential in attracting, motivating, engaging and retaining employees (see Chapter 4).

The second objective is:

2. To identify the most commonly used employee motivation, engagement and retention strategies within the UK spa business in terms of the impacts of Covid-19

When looking into what the spa industry is doing to address employee engagement, this study found a mixed bag of approaches in the UK. Most UK spa businesses have been applying the historical strategy of money motivation, where employers offer more hours in exchange for more money (See Chapters 4.4.1 and 5.4). Furthermore, employers offer a range of reward systems such as those introduced for spa employees in Malvern Spa in Worcestershire, UK. These include: flexible working hours, a reward system for achieving targets and 100 per cent attendance, a loyalty programme, bonus structures and competitive hourly pay. These rewards are offered to boost motivation among spa employees.

Customer feedback and reviews have been widely used in the UK spa business to monitor and evaluate employees. Excellent customer feedback and reviews lead to repeat custom and recognition, motivating employees to achieve rewards and perform at their highest potential (see Chapters 4.4.1, 5.2 and 5.4). Malvern Spa is proving successful at attracting and retaining spa employees by introducing a new reward scheme (Downtown, 2020). This is in line with the findings of Fernando and Nishanthi (2021), who posit that reward systems are positively related to attracting, retaining and motivating employees.

A spa job requires high physical effort, and spa employees are often physically and emotionally exhausted, leading to burnout and the intention to quit (Jenkins, 2020; Young, 2021; Page and McCann, 2021). The spa industry has widely encouraged the training and development of spa employees (Downtown, 2020; Seago, 2020; Jenkins, 2020; Young, 2021). Despite having a level 3 qualification, advanced training such as hands-free therapy can help reduce physical effort, thereby keeping employees motivated and engaged at work (Jenkins, 2020). Many spa professionals have to deal with emotionally fragile clients, such as cancer and stroke patients, which puts a strain on the staff's ability to deliver spa therapy (Young, 2020; Young, 2021; Page and McCann, 2021). Therefore, some spas are also

encouraging their employees to participate in awareness courses such as ACAC and stroke awareness courses. Young (2021) claims that these training courses provide employees with the knowledge and ability to deal with customers with relevant health conditions, which reduces unnecessary demotivation and burnout.

The third objective is:

3. To explore the challenges faced by management in employee motivation, engagement and retention strategies during and after the Covid-19 lockdown periods

The most notable challenges spa employers face are the shortage of spa therapists and the skill gap in the UK spa labour market (Seago, 2020; Raider, 2020; Downtown, 2020). As a result of the lack of workers, the work–life balance of spa employees has been adversely affected. Flexible working hours has been one of the critical demands of spa employees, but there is a shortage of staff and high demand for spa services (Raider, 2020). Long and unsocial working hours have always affected the work–life balance of spa employees, and the effects of the Covid-19 pandemic and further shortages in the workforce have worsened the situation. After the first lockdown in July 2020, Raider (2020) reported that spa bookings were up by over 30 per cent, but therapist availability was down 15 per cent compared to the previous year. In light of the therapist scarcity and Covid-19's increasing impact, it is clear that spa employers are under tremendous pressure to extract more value from their employees (Seago, 2020; Raider, 2020). The only way to boost supply is to have people work longer hours to keep up with demand. Spa organisational reward systems such as 'Gold therapist' schemes, rewarding employees for attaining goal sales and 100 per cent attendance, suggests that companies are encouraging employees to work longer hours to receive benefits (Downtown, 2020). While Downtown (2020) asserts that a company's reward system encourages employees to put in longer hours, it may have a negative effect, leading to employee burnout, as found by Aaron de Smet et al. (2021), who discovered that 64 per cent of employees plan to quit their jobs. This is supported by Rhee et al. (2020), who

argue that work–life balance is positively related to job satisfaction and has a greater impact on employee turnover intentions.

Loyalty programmes, bonus structures and competitive hourly pay are all monetary incentives (Downtown, 2020). Tarigan et al. (2022) claim that employees could not be easily satisfied with only monetary incentives; their preference has shifted from monetary concerns to self-capability. Covid-19 and a series of nationwide lockdowns have worsened the UK spa industry's financial difficulties (Seago, 2020; Raider, 2020). The 'great resignation' after lockdown created more job openings across the UK. There has been a battle for talent hunt where businesses across the UK are offering a wide range of benefits to attract talent (de Smet et al., 2021). It is clear that the spa industry is on the brink of survival and is not in a financial situation to offer higher pay, signing bonuses and other benefits (Raider, 2020). The current employee benefits are neither appealing to potential employees nor sufficient enough to retain current employees (Seago, 2020; ONS, 2020; Downtown, 2020).

An organisation's overall image and impression in the minds of its employees influences a variety of organisational outcomes, including retention, employee engagement, loyalty and improved talent attraction (Canhoto and Kietzmann, 2013). It appears that poor perception of the spa business by some members of the public is a significant barrier to engaging employees (see Chapters 4.4.3 and 5.8). This is because the spa sector is frequently equated to brothels, with spa therapists being considered as sex workers by some members of society (Taylor, 2021). It is clear that spa employees are humiliated by this image and reputation, negatively affecting their well-being (Taylor, 2021).

Working within a spa setting also requires high emotional labour. On the emotional side of work, spa employees are required to act as informal caregivers for clients and provide social assistance (Page and McCann, 2021). Examining this through Hochschild's (2012) lens of emotional labour, it seems that spa employers are required to follow organisational display rules by treating customers with smiley faces, politeness, friendly behaviour, kindness, compassion and courtesy regardless of what they actually feel, as they are paid wages.

Seen through the lens of Marx's theory of alienation (Feuerbach et al., 1997) combined with emotional labour (Hochschild, 2012), spa employees do not have control and ownership over their emotions and can feel alienated from their product, process and humanity. Although the spa business does offer customer service training, employees do not receive professional training in emotion management. Seago (2020) believes that these soft skills are learned through the various experience of life and sharpened by frequent job experiences (Page and McCann, 2021). It is found that spa employees are not equipped with the required resources to cope with high emotional demands; therefore, they are either avoiding challenging clients or engaging in surface acting, leading to emotional exhaustion (Jenkins, 2020; Page and McCann, 2021). The findings corroborate those of previous studies by Hebson et al. (2007) and Hochschild (2012), which assert that employees fake their emotions in order to expedite the encounter and accomplish the job with this surface acting leading to emotional exhaustion and burnout (Amisshah et al., 2021). They enjoy their jobs, but they require and desire assistance in managing the emotional side of their work (Young, 2021). They feel they cannot satisfy the demands of their employment, that they cannot give the service they wish for their clients, and that the hard work they perform goes unnoticed and unappreciated by the organisation. A past study by Maslach and Leiter (2016) supports the findings by stating that individuals who have low self-esteem and believe they are unable to carry out their responsibilities are more likely to believe they have failed. As a result of being exposed to so many grievances from clients, employees are also treating customers as objects rather than people (Jenkins, 2021; Page and McCann, 2021). As a means of coping with emotional tiredness, they are employing depersonalisation. This is supported by Pujol-Cols et al. (2021), who state that depersonalisation is a negative affective state in which an employee experiences prolonged and severe exhaustion and strives to avoid further losses of personal resources by emotionally withdrawing from others and viewing them as impersonal objects rather than humans.

While looking at research objective four:

4. To investigate how to develop future employment attractiveness in the UK spa industry by using employee motivation, engagement and retention strategies.

the study reveals that spa employers are trying to extract more value from their employees by offering monetary rewards and incentives to motivate them to invest long and unsocial working hours and perform excellent customer service (Seago, 2020; Raider, 2020; Downtown, 2020; Jenkins, 2021; Spa Industry Association, 2021). This affects the work–life balance and well-being of employees, leading to burnout, turnover intentions and further therapist scarcity. More practical, flexible working rules and strategies are needed.

Spa employees are often perceived as healers, and they enjoy their profession because it provides them with a sense of personal accomplishment by assisting others and making a positive contribution to society (Jenkins, 2021). Nevertheless, spa employees are being forced to suppress their authentic selves to follow organisational display rules, leading them to act more like wage slaves than healers (Murphy, 2020; Jenkins, 2021; Page and McCann, 2021). Since employees do not receive emotional management training, they lack the emotional intelligence to cope with high emotional job demands; therefore, they often engage in surface acting to complete the job. Lack of training and support has significant consequences, as spa workers may reduce their physical and mental well-being without adequate care, leading them to emotional exhaustion, depersonalisation, a sense of professional inefficacy and burnout (Grzesk, 2020; Jenkins, 2021; Page and McCann, 2021). The study reveals that employees would be more motivated and engaged if they had more expert technical and emotional management training to deal with their physical and emotional exhaustion; therefore, advanced training and education are required (see Chapters 4.4.1 and 5.8). This training will assist employees in dealing with physical and mental tiredness. It will also assist them in advancing their careers and developing personally, all of which will positively affect their level of commitment to their jobs.

6.2 Limitations of the study

In this section, limitations of the study are acknowledged. The initial plan of the study was to conduct primary research. However, secondary research has been carried out using documentary review due to the Covid-19 outbreak, lockdown restrictions and their effects. A survey and interview of employees and employers of the spa industry across the UK would have provided rich data in exploring the staffing issues within the spa sector.

The time frame is another limitation of the study. The initial DBA programme is for three years: one year for different modules and research proposals and the next two years for thesis writing. Usually, two years is enough and feasible for writing a DBA thesis, but the Covid-19 outbreak disrupted the progress of the research. At the end of the second year, the researcher was preparing for primary data collection by interview and survey questionnaire. Participants had verbally agreed to participate in the study. Then the pandemic occurred, followed by the first national lockdown. It was a time of terror and uncertainties where the researcher and supervisor had no other option than to wait for spa businesses to reopen. Online interview was considered a viable option for data collection, but access to participants was an obstacle that halted the research progress for nearly four months. Even with the reopening of the spa businesses after the first national lockdown, there were problems conducting face-to-face interviews with the participants due to Covid-19 restrictions. In the beginning, the researcher and the supervisor took a gamble by deciding to wait for additional restrictions to be eased for primary data collection. However, the gamble did not pay off as additional restrictions were in place, followed by the second and third national lockdowns. The third lockdown was lifted in March 2021, but there were still issues regarding access to participants and Covid-19 restrictions.

Further Covid-19 infection waves and additional nationwide lockdowns remained a possibility; therefore, the project was amended and secondary research was chosen for data collection. It was too late to start using primary research when things were normalising again. This study could have been improved if the researcher had decided to use secondary

research during the first or second national lockdown, where those squandered months may have been used better.

This would have allowed for the inclusion of more data sources where a more in-depth investigation might have been conducted by comparing the results across industries and countries. Even though this analysis was limited in scope by the time period, the included studies provided new information not previously available. Although it fills a conceptual gap through a documentary review, the study's scope was limited where the study only focuses on the spa industry, and a subsequent longitudinal investigation could provide more insight into the pandemic's later stages, particularly concerning other employment issues.

However, the investigation allowed for a contribution in terms of the gap between the literature review and the current period of post-Covid-19 restrictions which might not have yet been possible from interviews where participants were still grappling with the changes. Further the use of grey literature as documentary review allowed for scrutiny and emergence of themes that a historical literature review could not have captured given the lag on publication post-pandemic and within the industry.

6.3 Recommendation to practitioners and practice

Spas in the United Kingdom are not getting the attention they deserve from the government. The 'National Skills Fund' established by the government to address the UK workforce's talent gap should also cover the spa industry (Raider, 2020). Spa therapists require years of training and education but it is considered a low-skilled job by the public, which hampers the reputation of a therapist (Seago, 2020). This contributes also to problems in spa employees' attraction and retention. Additionally, various treatment brands and services are available in the UK that sound similar to treatments provided in spas that can be done with one-day training without any qualification (Taylor, 2021; Jenkins, 2021) or with no training and qualification at all, so with one day of training someone might call themselves a therapist, ruining a fully trained spa employee's reputation (Seago, 2020). Therefore, a firm

government policy and enforcement are required to help distinguish between certified and uncertified spa businesses and spa therapists.

The UK government introduced the 'flexible working' law where employees can request flexible working hours and days off (Gov.uk, 2021). However, the rules clearly state that employers can reject the application if 'flexible working' damages the business or the employer cannot find or recruit another employee to cover the work. Some spa employees are resigning because spa employers are exploiting employees by forcing them to work long and unsocial hours. Therefore, a strong government law should be introduced to prioritise employee well-being first and business performance second.

Although spa workers are well-trained and educated, they lack emotional training in dealing with vulnerable consumers (Page and McCann, 2021). There is a constant need for spa workers to be trained in emotional awareness. Only a few spas in the United Kingdom are encouraging their staff to participate in deep acting, where more and better deep acting training has to take place which leads to a decrease in emotional tiredness and an increase in the sense of personal success among workers.

6.4 Doctoral journey

It is believed that one of the best ways to learn is by doing (Gibbs, 1988). However, if the learner does not take the time to reflect on their experience and think about how they might improve for the next time, they will not be able to learn anything. In this situation, Gibbs's Reflective Cycle (1988) comes in handy. Gibbs's (1988) Reflective Cycle extends the experiential learning cycle created by Kolb (1975), which places theory and practice in an iterative circle. To improve one's performance, it is vital to reflect on one's experiences and activities. It may be especially beneficial if used to assess situations that are not going well so that one can learn from mistakes and improve performance in the future. Gibbs's reflective model is used to describe what has happened and how it has been assessed, analysed and evaluated. I decided to carry out my doctoral journey reflection in the five-step

cycle developed by Gibbs (1988): description, feelings, evaluation, conclusion and action plan.

The doctoral journey began as a way for me to grow from my former position as an assistant operational manager. My goal was to become a more effective manager and a better leader by learning about all the mechanisms of employee engagement, which would help me build a better workplace for my staff and help the company flourish. Working as an assistant operational manager in a UK spa, I had a clear idea of the subject matter I wanted to focus on. However, there was a dearth of current research in a critical area that affects everyone in the workplace, including employees, employers and customers.

As part of this doctoral journey, I had to overcome some significant personal challenges, including a period during which my father became very ill shortly after submitting my thesis proposal in my first year and tragically passed away at the end of my second year. Getting back on track with the project took several months. My doctoral journey has been riddled with a lot of difficulties and setbacks. However, the most significant problem I encountered involved changing methodology from primary to secondary data collection due to Covid-19 restrictions and national lockdown measures. I had been prepared for primary data research for around two years, and it seemed impossible to shift my mindset from a primary to secondary research paradigm. However, after a series of meetings and discussions with my supervisor, I eventually agreed and was able to produce themes to grasp the perspectives of staffing challenges in the UK spa industry based on this secondary data.

With extensive reading of both grey literature and peer-reviewed publications, I was able to learn a great deal during the research process, but identifying and collecting secondary data was challenging. There were only a few studies, news articles, research and reports available online regarding the UK spa industry, and most of the surveys and reports were too expensive to acquire. Since I was forced to conduct desk-based research, I had to rely on some beauty industry data and documents to fill in the gaps that share similar work-related features to the spa industry.

Another issue I ran into was underestimating the amount of time and effort required to complete thematic analysis, which includes transcription, translation, editing and analysis in all its forms.

The doctoral journey began as a way for me to grow from my former position as an assistant manager. Before joining the DBA programme, I was working as an assistant manager in a small spa business in London, managing around 60 employees for around two years. I was planning to open my own spa business in the UK in the near future but I had encountered staffing issues within the spa sector. To succeed in the spa business, I felt that I required higher knowledge and education in managing employees, which led me to join the DBA programme (Gibbs, 1988).

At first, I was excited and motivated to carry out the project as I had the experience of conducting a research project while doing an MBA. I was more confident and energised in researching employee engagement in the spa industry as it is the research area that I was dealing with every day at my workplace. Initially, I felt inexperienced and was intimidated by the sheer level of work that goes into a doctoral degree, such as extensive reading, writing, editing and analysing. I felt quite nervous, anxious and stressed as I had to do extensive work throughout the project, especially when changing my research methodology. I thought I was not confident I could produce the level of research that was expected. However, I felt more positive and was able to put the research concept into reality by reading numerous research textbooks and journals and engaging with my classmates, supervisor and other research specialists. Similarly I sometimes felt incompetent and was embarrassed about what I considered my limited ability to carry out and focus on my study. I even thought of dropping the DBA programme in the middle of the project. Later on, I realised that I was not alone in my embarrassment, as I discovered that all of my classmates were experiencing the same thing because we were not the research experts.

After my father passed away at the end of my second year, getting back on track with the project took several months. When I needed a diversion, having my doctorate studies at

hand gave me an objective to work towards. I believe that this project has helped me re-evaluate what is most important while conducting research and how I came to begin and complete this study in the first place.

The doctoral journey has made me more aware of the difficulties in conducting research and given me a better grasp of the theoretical and practical gaps that exist in the research process. The whole experience has been fascinating, exciting and educational for me.

There were many ups and downs throughout the doctoral journey. When I think back on the time when I had to alter my research approach, it is evident now that I am capable of handling the pressure and hard effort required to back up my initial research. However, I was under much stress with an immense volume of work near the end of the journey because of my poor time management skills and procrastination during the Covid-19 lockdowns. I was disappointed in myself at the time that I was not able to change my research methods from a primary to a secondary research approach. However, after reading King's template (2012) and looking at the grey literature adopted in Brewis et al.'s (2017) menopause studies, I managed to collect relevant documents and generate themes for the study. I am aware that despite my lack of prior experience working on such a large-scale project in terms of time, effort and volume of work, the findings will have significant beneficial ramifications for spa employment. While conducting the study, I came to realise that it was a substantial educational experience where I was able to put research theory into action based on the findings of the study. Not just the research findings but the theories of Khan (1990), Marx (cited in Feuerbach et al., 1997) and Hochschild (2012) have broadened my perception and knowledge of employee engagement, motivation and overall work–life balance. Based on the amount of time and effort I devote to research topics, I believe that a flexible approach to research is critical for amateur researchers like myself to get a unique learning experience. As a result of my research, I can say that the entire process has been a learning experience for me overall.

For my thesis to be supported and balanced, I needed to collect detailed qualitative data about the employment situation in the UK spa industry. After experiencing the challenge of changing the research approach in the middle of the doctorate journey, I was left with two options. Either I had to change back to my initial primary research approach or stick to the agreed secondary approach, especially after the third national lockdown was lifted in March 2021, when I was struggling to produce a secondary research approach that would best answer the research questions. I decided that secondary research was the best option because I still had to wait until it was safe in spa establishments to conduct interviews and for further restrictions to be lifted before conducting primary research. An additional wave of Covid-19 cases and a subsequent national lockdown were very likely, but this did not occur. Later in the doctorate journey, I was disappointed because if I had changed back to primary research, it would have been possible to conduct the interviews I initially proposed. However, it was too late at the time. On reflection, I realised that worrying over the past does not help in the present and future but only causes stress. I should not have overanalysed the situation, which led me to an analysis by paralysis.

I had already decided to change to a secondary approach and I should have focused more on my studies rather than generating confusion and regretting my choice. Eventually, after a series of meetings with my supervisor and reading the work of Brewis et al. (2017), I finally managed to produce a secondary research approach that best answers the research questions. When I was working on this research, I was able to locate and work with other fellow classmates who had been in comparable situations so that I could obtain a better knowledge of how they tackled the obstacles, their sentiments and their preparations. Most of them stuck to their initial primary approach and managed to do online questionnaires and interviews during the national lockdowns, as the Covid-19 pandemic and the national lockdowns did not impact their study sector. However, my sector, the spa industry, was affected hardest by Covid-19, and it was not wise to gamble and wait for the easing of Covid-19 restrictions.

Even though I had adequate time to complete my study, I was unable to organise my time well. During the lockdown period, I had an abundance of time to work on my thesis, which led me to procrastinate even more. I felt isolated from both my work and my studies. I was completely cut off from the university, my teachers and my fellow students, with the exception of one monthly online meeting with my supervisor. I had little motivation and focus on my studies. I remember feeling distracted from my studies and I enjoyed the lockdown by watching movies until 5 o'clock in the morning, playing online video games with my friends and having frequent barbecues in the garden while procrastinating. The good thing about lockdown is that it allowed me to reflect on my life and it also helped me relate both personal and professional life to Marx (cited in Feuerbach et al., 1997) and Hochschild's (2012) theory of alienation which gave me much more understanding of the theory. This not only helped me on developing themes for my study but also changed my perception of looking at work, money, capitalism and employee–employer relationships. This gave me the motivation to work on my research. I knew that I would need a lot of help in this area if my performance were to improve so that I could manage and organise time and my emotions in the future.

As a Nepalese researcher focusing on the subject of spa industry employment in the UK, the research process has honed my research and communication abilities, as well as my critical thinking and knowledge of the topic of study. From now on, I will proceed with caution when selecting appropriate subjects for my thematic review based on my previous qualifications, which have affected my ontological approach to investigating how to construct this study. My confidence rose due to this experience, and I learned that it is acceptable to make mistakes. During the self-analysis, I discovered that my poor time management stemmed from a lack of preparation. There is no point in regret. My inability to adequately prepare for such situations was shaped by my fear of having to face them; as a result, I needed to create a learning and support intervention to address the problem. I recognised that I needed to be more patient and confident in my choices rather than regretting or being worried about them.

The doctoral experience has been one of the most difficult, challenging and gratifying experiences of my life as a researcher. I had no idea what to anticipate and felt like I was immature and was not ready when I first started, but I was gradually gaining more and more confidence and knowledge as I went along. Several times along the process, my supervisor stepped in to provide a hand and get me back on track. As a researcher and as a person, I believe that I have grown as a result of the experience.

I do not think anyone can entirely prepare for a doctorate, but if I can better my time management and emotional management in the future, it will be much simpler and easier. I am aware that procrastination was a massive roadblock in my doctoral journey, and I needed to address it. When I read Scott's *How to Stop Procrastinating: A Simple Guide to Mastering Difficult Tasks and Breaking the Procrastination Habit* (2017), I realised that my lack of self-efficacy, lack of confidence and fear of failure led me to procrastinate even more frequently. Now that I have done the research, I have come to realise that I was never an expert in doing research. Being ashamed, stressed and frustrated in my lack of self-efficacy was unnecessary as I carried out this project to learn new things where learning how to do research is part of the process. If I want to be more confident, motivated and successful in the future, then I need to remember that it is all right not to know things, and it is never too late to learn where mistakes and failure are the processes of a learning curve.

7 References

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8 Appendix

8.1 Examples of Coded Text

Amy Downton, spa manager at The Malvern Spa in Worcestershire, which won PB's Spa of the Year: Midlands 2016 Regional Award, explores the challenges of spa recruitment and how incentives that promote a good work-life balance can attract the right therapists to your business.

One of the biggest challenges of running a successful and profitable spa is the difficulty of recruiting and retaining a group of world-class therapists. You'd think there would be therapists lining up to work in beautiful spas, keen to train, learn and develop – right? Wrong. This simply isn't the case.

When it comes to recruiting the "right" therapists I've experienced the struggle first hand. For me, I want staff who are passionate about treatments and products, and who are eager to take on the challenges of holistic massage and advanced body treatments. Unfortunately, this has become harder and more difficult to find, particularly in the past two years. Long hours, physically demanding treatments, having to work weekends and late shifts, and the perception of lower paid wages in the industry are all factors which put potentially fantastic therapists off working in a modern, busy spa.

The simple fact is that great product house training and a nice working environment is not enough to sustain therapists anymore, maybe in the short term but definitely not in a medium or long-term basis.

We must adapt and listen to what our staff need in order to gain a committed and sustainable team. A team who feel motivated and passionate about providing the best treatments to clients.

It took me a while to establish exactly what these factors were but now I've implemented a variety of new initiatives to promote a better work-life balance for staff. These include:

- Sociable shift times
- Great incentives such as our in-house "Gold Therapist" scheme which rewards staff for achieving target sales, great customer care feedback and 100% attendance
- Loyalty programmes which involve increased therapist remuneration based on length of service to the company
- Bonus structures
- Competitive hourly pay.

Now I'm finding myself in a much better situation to recruit, as well as retain, great therapists for the long term.

Comment 1: Suman Tamang (ST) - Job Demand, working condition

Comment 2: Suman Tamang (ST) - Reward system

Figure 4: Coded Text 1

How You Can Look After Yourself When Your Job Is To Look After Others?
Wellness & Wellbeing, May 21, 2021

Guest writer, Gail [Donnan](#), author of *The Gateway: A journey to reclaim your power from stress and anxiety*, writes about how you can look after yourself, when your job is to look after others.

When you look up empathy in the dictionary it reads “the ability to understand and share the feelings of another”. Therapists can fall into an exhausting trap of [feeling for](#) another rather than feeling [with](#) them. As a therapist myself, I have experienced times with clients that has brought my excessive emotional empathy out in droves and it is easy to feel yourself starting to become emotionally invested and drained.

Empathy actually requires complex [skills](#) but we have a choice when to use those skills. Empathy has a [filter](#), it is not fixed and should contract and expand with life events. Sympathy, kindness, altruism and prosocial behaviour are all welcomed life skills, but we don't need to reconstruct the thoughts and feeling of another individual and our job as therapists is not to hold that kind of power.

I work in integrative health and psychotherapy, once my client [leaves](#) I do not mull over what we have discussed until the time comes to prepare their notes for their next session so my empathy must have a filter and can obviously be controlled.

Two hundred and fifty years ago, Adam Smith famously described the way observers might feel watching a tight rope walker. Even while standing on solid ground, our palms sweat and our hearts race. In essence, we experience the tight rope walker's state as our own. This captures the scientific model of empathy and how our mirror neurons help you understand the intentions and actions of clients.

There are different types of empathy:

- Cognitive
- Emotional
- Compassionate

Cognitive empathy is being able to put yourself into someone else's shoes and see their perspective without engaging with their emotions, leading by thought rather than by feeling. Emotional empathy is when you can literally feel the other person's emotions alongside them which causes us personal distress and anxiety. As therapists, we need to be careful investing emotionally in an outcome where we have little or no control. It is possible to become overwhelmed by emotions (empathy overload) and we may need to work on our self-regulation and self-control to manage our emotions because we can't see where our life starts and the other person's ends. We may feel our co-workers or managers don't feel the same or are uncaring— [this results](#) from over-protection from empathy overload or excessive empathy.

Compassionate empathy is feeling someone else's pain and taking action to help. Like sympathy, compassion is about feeling concern for someone but with some action to help and is the type of empathy that is usually most appropriate. As a general rule, clients who want or need your empathy don't need you to understand, or to feel their pain, become anxious or worse burst into tears alongside them. They need you to understand and sympathise with what they are going through and help them to take appropriate action. For

ST Suman Tamang
burnout
Reply

ST Suman Tamang
Emotional exhaustion
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ST Suman Tamang
Emotional exhaustion
Reply

ST Suman Tamang
Deep acting
Reply

ST Suman Tamang
Burnout
Reply

ST Suman Tamang
Surface Acting
Reply

ST Suman Tamang
Emotional Coping strategy
Reply

Figure 5: Coded Text 2

me this means being a caring, professional person who respects their own personal boundaries and I am very transparent about this with clients that unintentionally push those boundaries.]

Cause and effect of excessive empathy

Excessive empathy or hyper empathy is having a higher amount of empathy than average and is generally found in sensitive, emotionally reactive people. Many people who have a caring role have slightly longer antenna than others and pick up on every emotion vibrating in the atmosphere! There are many reasons for excessive empathy, sometimes we learn to become hypervigilant as a child and we learn to read body language and sense atmospheres quickly for a safer life, we may not have been shown compassion or may have lower levels of cognitive empathy and self-esteem and have poor personal boundaries.

Tips to lessen the effects of excessive empathy:

- Set better personal boundaries, perhaps buddy up with a colleague to work on this together
- Try to avoid gaining your self-worth from caring or pleasing others – work on your own self-esteem
- Deep breathing exercises
- Metaphorically 'zip up' before and 'discharge' after every client (Reiki practitioners are taught to do this)
- Use Mindfulness Self-Compassion (co-founded by Kristen Neff)
- It is ok to say no
- Use meditation to relax and detach from work

[The above lessons are especially relevant for those welcoming cancer patients to their salon and spa. It can be useful to review this advice, alongside the information received in theory training, when you signed up for your postgraduate diploma in oncology touch. Remember that you became certified on an accredited course where it is possible to welcome cancer patients and be insured to do so. You have received the training required and a tutor has assessed you as skilled in this area.]

Meditation

When I need to clear my head after a session with a client, my go to would be meditation. It is free, it can done anywhere even in between clients or on a quick loo break. "Meditation is not the throwing of a switch and catapulting yourself anywhere, nor is it entertaining certain thoughts and getting rid of others. Nor is it making your mind blank or willing yourself to be peaceful or relaxed. It is really an inward gesture that inclines the heart and mind (seen as one seamless whole) toward a full-spectrum awareness of the present moment just as it is, accepting whatever is happening simply because it is already happening. Meditation is not about trying to get anywhere" (Kabat Zinn 2006).

The therapeutic benefits of essential oils can help both your clients and yourself to unwind and relax. When you enrol this month on the Balanced Body and Mind course, you learn to enhance the wellbeing of your clients and receive £432 worth of free skincare with uplifting, soothing properties.

ST Suman Tamang Emotional management training
Reply

ST Suman Tamang Training and development
Reply

Figure 6: Coded Text 3

Recruitment has never been the easiest thing for any business owner but for beauty businesses even more rests on your staff. Your salon's reputation, relationships with clients and product houses and, in fact, the survival of your business, are all heavily reliant on the quality of your therapists.

So after months of hearing people from all areas of the industry warning that the market is heading towards a **recruitment crisis**, it's time to investigate just how salon and spa owners have found themselves asking the same question: where have all the therapists gone? "There's a chronic shortage of therapists, I don't know where they've all gone," says Kieran Fowley, director of the Zen Lifestyle salon group, based in Edinburgh. "Four years ago, if we had a vacancy we'd get two dozen CVs through, but now we're excited if we get any at all, and we're having to interview candidates whose CVs we wouldn't have even reached the second page of before."

He says that in Edinburgh the situation has got so bad that salons are having to raise wages, often over and above what they can afford to, in order to compete. "A lot are now advertising salaries on job ads and they never used to do that," he adds.

And the shortage stretches further than Scotland. Sarah Harris, owner of Virgo Beauty near Reading, even struggled to recruit a therapist progressing from NVQ Level 2 to 3. "I contacted local colleges and got one applicant, who I took on. She told me only four people from her course were progressing onto Level 3," says Harris, who has been trying to recruit two additional therapists since January.

Of the therapists that do apply, an even smaller percentage is ready for the salon floor. "If I watch someone fresh out of college do a manicure, it's usually of a standard that any member of the public would be able to do," says Harris. Employers are often quick to blame further education colleges for their recruitment struggles, but is the finger pointing justified?

Under pressure

"I've been in recruitment for 15 years and the difference between the standard of therapist coming out of college back then compared to today is huge," says Michelle Caheny, senior spa and beauty recruitment consultant at Spa and Beauty Connection. "But it's funding cuts; it's the reduction in mandatory teaching hours. Beauty therapy is a vocation and I think that's been forgotten right at the top of the chain."

With increasing pressure on the education system to deliver salon-ready therapists under time and cost restraints, it doesn't help that both the number and standard of applicants onto beauty therapy courses has also dropped drastically. "You get used to being battered a bit by the industry," says Joan Scott, director of Trafford College in Manchester.

"But recruitment is dwindling for us too, which is worrying me. We always used to have a steady pipeline and we could be selective and say 'you're not quite right for this', but now we've had to widen the net a bit, especially given the demand for jobs, because the beauty industry has exploded," she explains.

The beauty industry is booming, with more salons setting up shop and new brands entering the market than ever before. The demand from clients is clearly there, but without the supply of therapists to meet it, the industry could be about to enter unknown territory.

"If I look around Edinburgh there are a lot more beauty businesses than there were 10 years ago," says Fowley. "There's enough demand but just not enough therapists to go around. On top of that, menus have really expanded. We do about 100 treatments and we need our therapists to be able to do everything."

With increased demand for treatments comes longer opening hours, creating yet another hurdle to recruitment. "Due to consumer demand more salons are open late and on Sundays and bank holidays now, but when you think about the longevity of a therapist sustaining those working hours...it's difficult, they don't have a life," says Caheny.

Fowley agrees that Zen's therapists are expected to work long hours: "Our hours are 7.30am-10pm and 9am-6pm on weekends, so there are a lot of evenings and weekends. But those hours need to be there to accommodate client demand," he says.

Figure 7: Coded Text 4

Attitude problem

Ask any salon owner what would be on their therapists' wish lists and better working hours would likely come a very close second to higher pay. Many owners put this down to generational changes in attitudes towards a work/life balance.

"[Young therapists] don't want to work weekends or evenings. This generation is so used to having everything they want; they go away for fancy weekends and to festivals, they want a certain lifestyle so they want their weekends and evenings," says Harris. "I see CVs where a therapist has had seven or eight jobs in one year. When I ask why they left a job it's because they weren't allowed to take the holiday they wanted. Sometimes they just walked out like it's not even a job," adds Caheny.

It's disheartening to hear so many accounts of new therapists with little respect or enthusiasm for the industry they're entering. "The generation coming out of college now wants to know what we can do for them first and foremost. They don't come prepared to stick out their first job for a decent amount of time and try to prove themselves; they don't mind changing jobs after a few weeks if it isn't exactly what they want," says Fowley. Colleges are steadily absorbing these concerns and understanding that in most cases they have to focus more on teaching soft skills such as professionalism, people skills and attitude towards work. "Some of them are 16 and they haven't even had a part-time job. We've got to get them ready for the world of work from scratch sometimes," says Scott. "We try to encourage them to get jobs on their CVs while they're at college and develop those soft skills".

Pointing the finger

Salons don't get off scot-free when it comes to placing blame for the therapist shortage. "There are graduates who are talented and passionate but employers just won't entertain their CVs. Ten years ago, a lot of new graduates were employed but that just doesn't seem to be happening now," says Caheny.

"Equally, junior therapists aren't being offered promotion to senior roles after three or four years, so they're losing interest. A lot of people leave beauty therapy by the age of 25," she adds.

With salons struggling to keep hold of staff, training bonds are becoming common-place, usually requiring that a therapist who leaves within two years of training re-pays the cost of that course to the employer. "It scares a lot of them; for an 18 year old two years is a long time to sign up to, but therapists should see it as a positive thing because it shows that the employer is investing them. If it was standard across the board they wouldn't have any choice," says Caheny.

Employers are having to offer more and more to show therapists they'll be valued in order to attract them in the first place. "We find it increasingly hard to attract good therapists and we've already got a very good commission scheme, plus incentives with our product houses and benefits across the entire business," says Karen Wilkinson, group head of spa at The Bannatyne Group.

"We now have to work harder at creating partnerships with other businesses in order to be able to offer attractive benefits, because gone are the days you could put a job ad online and be inundated with 20 or 30 CVs."

Fowley says retention tools are a big focus for Zen Lifestyle too, especially given that competitor salons are "actively trying to poach our staff". He continues: "We honestly do try so hard to make it a happy, fun and productive environment where therapists get a lot of opportunities."

Money talks

Ultimately, there's no shying away from the issue that wages for beauty therapists are often comparatively low. "I think salary is the problem – people perceive it as a low-paying industry," says Harris, while Fowley adds: "It would be great if we could all pay our therapists £30,000 a year but the reality is that no one will spend £100 on a manicure, so there's only

ST Suman Tamang
work/life balance
Reply

ST Suman Tamang
Development factor
Reply

ST Suman Tamang
Economic factor
Reply

Figure 8: Coded Text 5

so much you can pay and still have a viable business, especially with all of the increasing business costs of late."

The pay issue would be an obvious explanation for a drop in therapist numbers if it weren't for the fact that salaries have actually increased in the past five years. Research conducted by Professional Beauty in 2014 and again in 2016 found that the average salary of a therapist in London increased from £16,000 per annum in 2012 to £20,250 in 2016, and from £14,000 to £16,229 for those outside of the capital.

It's entirely possible that despite this increase, the average salary just isn't enough to sustain a young adult in comparison to the snowballing cost of housing and living in general. [This could explain why many qualified therapists are spending a short amount of time in salon before going it alone and setting up a mobile business, taking themselves out of the job market. "A lot of people are now just doing it themselves, because it does offer a lot of flexibility and it can sustain you really well. Some brands now don't even require you to have therapy training; they'll set you up at home after a one-day course and you're away," says Harris. "Then you can be at home all day promoting yourself for free on social media so you can charge a fraction of what salons do because you can afford it." More professional brands now offer packages for mobile therapists, and with portable tools like at-home UV lamps and handheld microdermabrasion devices, it's easier than ever to give a salon-quality treatment in the comfort of the client's home.]

Action stations

The changes set to come with Brexit also pose a threat to the flow of international workers larger salons and spas have enjoyed. "We've always had three to five Irish therapists at any one time, and we have a very good Slovakian receptionist with a therapy background. It worries me that, post-Brexit, jobs with us might not be so attractive to them; that they won't feel that Britain is such a friendly place to be," says Fowley.

While the recruitment outlook may seem bleak, it's important to remember that client demand is on the rise, and beauty is an industry that's well versed in quickly adapting to change. Harris is developing a LinkedIn network for local salons and spas to connect and communicate, making it easier to headhunt directly and share information on therapists looking for roles.

Similarly, Caheny has teamed up with business consultant Valerie Delforge on a Facebook group called Keeping up With the Beauty Industry, specifically for therapists. "It's a portal for them to bounce ideas off each other and feel more a part of the industry. There are so many resources directed at salon and spa owners and managers, but therapists don't get any networking events or anything to make them feel involved in the industry," she says. Caheny believes employers need to be more open to taking on graduates to induct them into salon life "so they become energised and interested. The graduate is a blank canvas and having one on your team is an advantageous position for you," she adds. Taking on a promising Level 2 learner on a part-time basis so they can become acquainted with what will be expected of them in the salon environment could well turn out to be a win-win for you both.

Bannatyne spas do just this: "Learners do a hosting job to get them engrained into the business and they might pick up a few treatments they're already qualified in. We're keen to nurture passion, and we've retained quite a few of them so far," says Wilkinson.

Salons seeking out older therapists could also consider advertising job shares to allow working mothers a more viable way to return to the salon.

Educators hardly need any more demand on them, but everyone we spoke to agreed that it would be hugely beneficial to employers if "it was widespread that learners got even a bit of basic commercial training and knew what to realistically expect when they start a job; what a day in the life of a therapist is like," says Wilkinson.

The experts agree that to reignite enthusiasm and commitment for the profession, it's high time we worked to elevate the status of the beauty therapist, highlighting inspiring career journeys and role models to encourage pride and respect in the job. Wilkinson says: "Therapy needs to be introduced as an industry with so much potential where you can have a

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Suman Tamang

Employed to self employed

Reply

Figure 9: Coded Text 6